

**COMPREHENDING THE FACTORS RESPONSIBLE
FOR CREATING SUCCESSFUL LEADERSHIP AMONG
WOMEN LEADERS IN THE UNITED KINGDOM'S
FINTECH START-UP SECTOR**

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DECLARATION

This work has not previously been accepted in substance for any degrees including DBA, DProf, EngD, PhD or comparable academic award and is not being concurrently submitted in candidature for any other degree.

This thesis is the result of my own investigations, except where otherwise stated. Other sources are acknowledged by explicit references.

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DEDICATION

To My Greatest Strength & Blessing: My Husband

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ABSTRACT

In the present era, women have shown their proficiency in every sphere of the corporate environment and have developed competencies in achieving greater efficiency at the workplace. The FinTech start-up sector is also witnessing an increase in the number of women employees. However, despite a quarter of representation of women in the FinTech start-up sector, only one-seventh is placed among the board of directors. In this context, this study aims to evaluate the phenomenon of female leadership within FinTech start-up companies in the UK's financial sector. The main aim of the study was to identify the factors responsible for successful female leadership in the UK's FinTech start-up sector. The literature review revealed that there are four critical factors responsible for the outcome of female leadership-individual, organisational, social and technological. This was further examined using primary research. For this purpose, the researcher used a mixed-method comprising of both quantitative and qualitative approach. Under the quantitative approach, the researcher surveyed 100 employees working in the FinTech start-up sector through a close-ended questionnaire to examine the factors that impact the success of female leadership and the shortcomings under women leadership. On the other hand, under the qualitative analysis, the researcher interviewed the 5 managers through an open-ended questionnaire to understand the effectiveness of women leadership, leadership strategies and the challenges faced by women leaders. The findings indicated that women often face challenges in terms of the vertical limits created by society. All the factors significantly impact the leadership performance of females in the UK's FinTech start-up sector. In addition to this, women often find it difficult to handle family and job responsibilities. Further, the findings indicate that women are more creative and need to be motivated. Lastly, organisations can play an important role in successful female leadership by adopting new management and leadership styles that provide women with equal opportunities.

TERMINOLOGIES

FinTech sector: Technology-enabled innovation in financial services that could result in new business models, applications, processes or products with an associated material effect on the provision of financial services (Financial Stability Board, 2019).

Glass Ceiling: The term glass ceiling is used in the context of women leadership wherein women face the invisible and unbreakable wall for rising to the leadership positions. These walls are barriers to the progress of women. These can be social barriers created by society and the environmental barriers in the form of strict laws and initiatives. Other barriers include the work-life balance and lack of career planning (Gandhi and Ranaa, 2017).

Sticky Floor: Women who are working at the lower management positions in the corporations face structural barriers within the corporations. Additionally, sometimes women are reluctant to take over a higher level of responsibilities. These factors could hinder women's career progression in contrast to their male counterparts. These structural barriers are often referred to as the sticky floor (Ahmad and Naseer, 2015).

Gender Stereotypes: A gender stereotype is defined in terms of the attributes or pre-conception of the attributes wherein men and women have defined the specific roles, which ought to be performed by them. This term is the generalised view of the characteristics of men and women through which society assign them different responsibilities (UN, 2014).

Gender Neutrality: Gender Neutrality is the term associated with policies, languages and other social considerations wherein males and females are not distinguished in terms of their roles. In other words, the gender differences do not affect the roles played by women and men in the society. This term is also associated with offering equal opportunities to the males and females (Rajan, 2017).

Leadership: Northouse, (2007) defined leadership as “The influence that particular individuals (leaders) exert upon the goal achievement of others (subordinates) in an organisational context”

Statistical discrimination: A phenomenon where decision-makers use observable characteristics such as group identity as a proxy for unobservable, but outcome-relevant, characteristics (Levitt, 2010).

Social role theory: The social role theory states that “Individuals have been identified as males and females and they occupy different roles in the social framework and are usually judged against the parameters against which they ought to behave” (Eagly, Wood and Diekmann, 2007)

Role congruity theory: Role congruity theory looks at how people are evaluated in terms of the characteristics that are perceived to align with the groups’ typical roles for men and women (Anderson, Goodman, & Schlossberg, 2012, p. 76)

Institutional theory: Institutional theory provides conceptual frameworks for examining the nature of external demands and the internal reactions of organisations (Burnett et al., 2016).

SRI Report: The SRI Status Report is the reporting tool, which is published annually to communicate to the European Commission and interested parties, the results achieved by the SRI in reaching the set targets. (cocir.org)

Future Fifty Scheme: Tech Nation Future Fifty is a leading programme that enables the UK's most successful late-stage technology companies to come together, build a powerful and supportive network, and problem-solve with peers.

Trickle-down effect: The trickle-down effect is a model of product adoption in marketing that affects many consumer goods and services. It states that fashion flows vertically from the upper classes to the lower classes within society, each social class influenced by a higher social class

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

FinTech: Financial Technology

CIPD: Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development

FTSE 100: The Financial Times Stock Exchange 100 Index

GDP: Gross Domestic Products

ExCo: Executive Committee

BAME: Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic

MSCI World Index: Morgan Stanley Capital International world index

STEM: Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

OECD: Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development

COO: Chief Operating Officer

CFO: Chief Financial Officer

CEO: Chief Executive Officer

CMO: Chief Marketing Officer

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Chapter: 1 INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

The inception of age of automation following the technological advancements has profoundly impacted the lives of millennial workers globally. All the spheres of existence, spanning from personal experiences to the working of economies, have been influenced by the tools and techniques of information technology. The members of the present generation are expected to reshape the economies, restructuring the way business is done and services are delivered (Goldman Sachs, 2007). The financial services sector is one of the aspects of the present economy which has also been touched by the digitisation processes, and this meet up of technology and finance has led to the evolution of the Financial Technology sector, also referred to as the 'FinTech' sector. The FinTech sector includes the companies which offer technology-based solutions to enhance and optimise the delivery of financial services (Ancrì, 2016). Also, the era of start-ups have provided a host of new services to the customers of the financial sector such as allowing next-generation systems for payments, peer to peer lending, smart investment options, robotic advisory systems involving artificial intelligence build upon algorithms, and financial planning systems (Ancrì, 2016; Punater and Shankar, 2016).

1.1 Background to the Research

1.1.1 Start-up sector in the UK

The UK is considered as a place where start-ups find favourable ambiance to grow and prosper. While in 2015, there were approximately 608,000 start-ups in the country, it grew further to 660,000 in 2016. Government level support and favourable regulatory environment are considered as the major factors that support the growth of start-ups in the country every year (Bounds, 2017). In recent years, the government has undertaken a number of measures to give the start-up sector a boost, which include provision of several funding routes, encouraging competition among investors, maintaining an online database for providing information related to taxation, registration and licensing of start-ups, easing of visa norms to invite overseas talent for upliftment of the sector, and upgrading their infrastructure to provide non-stop digital connectivity using superfast internet (Macaulay & Carey, 2019). A start-up here refers to the beginning of companies that aim to apply innovative approaches to business problems and are highly scalable (Janáková, 2015).

Technology start-ups in particular have seen enormous growth in the UK. According to (Posser, 2018), 10,016 software companies were registered for the first time in the UK in 2017, as compared to 6,300 firms in 2016. Out of this, 4,238 belonged to London region. The author postulates that this is accredited to ease in obtaining finance and availability of loans at cheap interest rates. In addition to this, the UK government is undertaking other measures to encourage the start-up arena, such as inaugurating a UK-India tech hub in London for promotion of cross-border technology transfer. This initiative is aimed at boosting tech start-ups irrespective of the outcome of Brexit (The Hindu, 2019).

1.1.2 Introduction to the UK's FinTech sector

The financial sector of the world has become extremely dynamic and is thus experiencing a sea of changes. One of the major changes is the emergence of FinTech firms. FinTech is an

abbreviated form of the term financial technology. The distinctive feature of FinTech firms is that they provide alternate financial solutions for banking services and non-banking financial services (Vijai, 2019). These FinTech firms have brought about innovations in usual financial services like asset management, lending, and insurance by leveraging digital technologies. Through the introduction of digitisation, the FinTech firms endeavour to accomplish their core purpose of boosting service development in domains like payment, wealth management and trading (Gimpel, Rau, & Röglinger, 2018).

The emergence of FinTech start-ups can be traced back to the period of the 1990s when the Internet-enabled e-commerce commenced together with innovative services like dynamic web services, standardisation of financial services, and integration of e-business technologies in the sphere of enterprise applications. In the later years, further innovation was brought about in the FinTech sector through the emergence of mobile channels, cloud-based services and big data analytics that made the sector more commercialised and consumer-oriented (Alt & Zimmermann, 2014). Thus, today the FinTech firms have become the key innovation drivers of the financial sector that offer core financial services like consumer-oriented banking, insurance and so on (Alt & Puschmann, 2012). The development of the FinTech from a niche to continually expanding financial ecosystem calls for analysis and evaluation across the different financial hubs all over the globe. Among all the financial hubs, The UK (London) has invariably presented itself as the world's top financial centre and is hence seen as a fertile ground for analysing the innovative FinTech sector (Finch, 2017). The FinTech scenario in the UK has been showing perpetual progress, of the availability of superior financial infrastructure, appropriate capital, and technologically enabled base of customers (Langley, 2017). The sector benefits from a pool of well-trained tech professionals possessing unrivalled financial expertise, however, future concerns regarding the maintenance of a healthy pipeline of the talent pool are evident. The capital investment scenario is suitable concerning the early stage development, but later growth stage developments face constrained investments.

The UK presents itself as highly supportive of the sector's policy regime. The Financial Conduct Authority's tax incentives and other government programs promote innovative business procedures, and the UK's FinTech ecosystem had been ranked as the leading

ecosystem (Gulamhuseinwala and Kotecha, 2016). The UK FinTech sector was estimated to attract an investment of £6.6 billion in revenue in 2015, with £524 million in investment (Ernst & Young, 2014). Sizing the FinTech market of the UK, the industry has currently been generating £20 billion annually (Ernst & Young, 2014). Payments which are also the largest micro sector in the FinTech sector where they alone have been generating £10 billion, followed by financial software micro-sector with £4.2 billion and data and analytics with £3.8 billion (Gulamhuseinwala and Kotecha, 2016).

Leadership by women is looked at by a majority of women as a symbol of accomplishment and achievement. Exemplary cases and images of women leadership in the new age culture provides hope and strength to take up steps to face the world and lead. Thus, to carry on with the research, various publications and real-life saturations will be used as the mode of knowledge and in case of motivation real-life survey help in understanding the ground situation.

Specifically, in the case of the FinTech companies of the UK, it has been found that the total value of all the FinTech firms of the country taken together surpasses the economy of entire France. Presently, the total value of FinTech start-ups in the UK surpasses over £50 billion. The massive growth of the FinTech firms in the UK has further resulted in infrastructural development, the increment of capital base and talent availability in the country (Saks-McLeod, 2019). Since 2008, this particular sector of the UK has been growing at a rapid rate in terms of the maturity of the FinTech firms, investment, and employment. Although a majority of employment generated in this sector is concentrated in London, Edinburgh, and Manchester.

As far as functions of FinTech workers in the UK are concerned, workers are focused on product delivery account for the largest percentage of the workforce in this sector. Their numbers constitute 40% of the total workforce of the FinTech sector of the UK. This is followed by the financial services (FS) experts who constitute 30% of the workforce. The business development and corporate support staffs of the FinTech sector of the UK constitute 20% of the workforce, while the leaders and executives of the sector constitute 10% of the workforce (Baldwin, 2016). However, one of the related problems of the FinTech start-ups of

the UK is the gender disparity in the workforce where female representation is only 30%. In this, only 17% of the females hold the post of senior executives. The management also maintains differential attitude towards female workers when compared to white males of the UK FinTech sector. Only 20% of the women are less likely than white male workers to win endorsements from the firm for ideas that might fetch the firm greater market opportunities (Brett, 2019). Thus, it can be concluded that FinTech companies contribute significantly to the GDP of the UK. However, the gender gap persists as a problem where the worth of including women workers and exploring their potentials is not recognised appropriately. So, it is essential to estimate if further positive changes can be brought to the sector through schemes and programs that encourage women in leadership roles. Nevertheless, there is a paucity of studies on this topic. Therefore, the current study shall attempt to address this theme in particular.

1.1.3 Growth of the female/women leadership in the UK's FinTech start-up sector

The UK's FinTech start-up sector has continued to grow in terms of business processes and technological innovations but the address of gender diversity in the sector is still an issue to be focused upon (Maule and Duhaime, 2015). Although the UK has been ranked third in Global Entrepreneurship Index, the sector does not present a fair representation of female talent concerning technology, besides the poor representation of women in leadership roles (Gulamhuseinwala and Kotecha, 2016). The address of these issues is necessary to avoid the instances of gender bias, bringing in the reality of gender equality (Maule and Duhaime, 2015). The presence of diversity is necessary for the optimal development of any sector, and the FinTech sector particularly continues to drag in the female leadership agenda.

It has been observed that the companies having fair gender diversity produced financial returns above the national industry mean standards. With respect to the UK, women are quite underrepresented in leadership roles, with only 12% representation in the executive roles (Hunt, Layton and Prince, 2015), with overall representation in the labour market accounting for 72.5% as compared to 83.7% representation of males (Roland Berger Strategy Consultants,

2013). Furthermore, 21% of the women held senior roles in 2016 which has comparatively gone down from 22% in 2015 (Langley, 2017). Again, the number of businesses with no women in senior management in the UK is 36%. In the UK, 9% of the women hold the position of CEOs, whilst 23% as HRD, 21% as CFO, 11% as CMO, 8% as COO and Sales director exclusively (The UK Government 2012; AAUW 2016a). Thus, the growth of women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK has not changed significantly as only 23% of the women represent the board members and 14% as an executive.

1.1.4 Existing female leadership and it's growth

As mentioned in the previous section, the number of women representing the board of FinTech companies in the UK is nearly 23%, whereas the number is much less for the executive level. If not in the corporate or FinTech sector, the Government of the UK has laid down certain action plans to improve the women's representation in the political world (Innovate Finance, 2014). The current status of women as leaders in the UK's political background stands at 19.4% as members of parliament and 30.8% of the women as local councillors in England. 46.7% of the women also represent the Welsh Assembly, whilst 34.8% and 13.9% of the women represent the Scottish Parliament and Northern Ireland assembly respectively (OECD 2016; The UK Government 2012).

Additionally, it was found that 5% of the population in the UK's political leadership belongs to the black, Asian and minority ethnic (BAME) women with 0.3% of them as members of parliament (The UK Government 2012). With this regard, the UK government has changed the laws by imposing Equality Bill thereby providing transparency to the general population and encourage other women to take a stand in political leadership.

In the corporate world of the UK, 41% of the total population is represented by females which is quite decent (Global Strategy Group, 2016; Teow and Jain, 2017). Hence, when it comes to the CEO positions, 1 out of 20 are women, and in executive level, 1 out of 10 are women. One of the start-ups in the UK, Innovate Finance, which is a FinTech company had listed the

powerful women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK (Innovate Finance, 2014). They perceive that people look up to leaders and their achievements in life, which acts as a very important driver in boosting dormant women to take up challenges and become a leader.

In another report, it was found that CIPD had engaged in initiatives to improve the population of women in the corporate world with a target of 40% of directors of FTSE 100 companies to be women and 20% of executive directors of FTSE 100 companies to be women by 2020 (CIPD, 2016; OECD, 2016). However, it is also expected that the current status and position of the women in the UK will rise by above 30%. This is possible with the current initiatives taken up by the Government and the other institutes to provide empowerment to women.

1.2 Problem Statement

While conducting the study, the major problem that was identified is that even though various empirical sources exist on gender disparity across the workforce of the UK, there is a dearth of specific researches that address the problem of shortage of women labourers in the FinTech start-ups of the country. Nonetheless, as women contribute approximately 40% of the country's GDP so it becomes essential to identify the significance of women in FinTech start-ups of the UK so that their potentials can be optimally harnessed.

The FinTech sector of the UK, as explained above, has contributed immensely to the growth of the economy for the last two decades. In addition to this, the number of technology start-ups in the UK has reached its peak in 2018, which includes a considerable number of FinTech start-ups as well. The success of a start-up depends greatly on its leadership, as identified by many researchers in the past. For instance, (Yang, Pu, & Guan, 2019) postulate that leadership affects the climate within the company, employee morale, level of commitment and loyalty towards their organisation, which affects the organisational performance. However, since the leadership styles are different, their level of impact also differs. Moreover, leadership among men and women is not uniform, as studies have shown. The factors affecting leadership of women in start-ups differ from those that affect men. As a result, it is pertinent to identify and

understand these factors and also how they affect the organisation's performance. However, there exist no researches on understanding the factors affecting successful female leadership in FinTech start-ups of the UK, and how they affect the organisation. In this context, it can be stated that successful leadership constitutes setting organisational goals, helping employees, redesigning the organisation, monitoring its progress, and ensuring its longevity (Belchetz & Leithwood, 2007). Thus, due to the shortage of adequate number of prior researches in this specific topic, only limited information could be considered worthwhile for providing the necessary data required for carrying out the present study.

1.3 Rationale of the study

The rationale behind the research proposal is that gender disparity at the executive level of business organisations is very common. This is even though many types of research and reports recorded that companies with female executives had helped the company to achieve higher revenues than men. Thus, it is important to determine the factors that influence female leaders and executives in their successful leadership skills. The current statistics show that the number of women leaders in the executive and other higher level of the industry has been plummeting. Even after various initiative and brilliant examples of the pros of female leadership in an organisation, men still dominate.

In specificity, the FinTech sector is still growing at a steady rate where very fewer women act as leaders or even hold the position of executives. However, in this regard, it is also reported that businesses that are led by women had helped in improved long-term economic gains and had also boosted the GDP. The UK has been found to have benefitted from women employment in contributing to the GDP by 9%. Again, while women constitute 50% of the total population in the UK and 40% of the country's GDP. On the other hand, males constitute 60% of the country's GDP (Bulman, 2016). Even though only 10% of women find themselves in leadership roles in the firms of the UK (Baldwin, 2016), men dominate in the managerial posts by and large. On average, the percentage of males in the workforce of the UK who occupy managerial and leadership positions are almost 50% to 80% higher than that of female workers

(Jericho, 2017). There are a number of reasons for this gap, such as perceived inability to devote as much time at work as their male counterpart, perceived lack of aggressiveness and stealth, perceived unlikeliness to undertake immense work pressure, and high emotional intelligence quotient (Bennett, 2019; Millard, 2018). Recent researches have suggested a number of measures to drive a change in this trend. A critical measure among these is to encourage more women in Science, Technology, Engineering and Medicine (STEM) education which can play a key role in bridging the gender pay gap and enabling more women leaders (Ahmed, Ahmed, & McKay, 2015; Botella, Rueda, López-Iñesta, & Marzal, 2019).

According to different authors, women account for only a quarter of the enrolments in STEM courses, which affects their participation and growth at the workplace. Common barriers faced by women in the workplace included lack of a mentor, lack of female role models, gender bias, unequal growth opportunities as compared to men, and a large gender pay gap for the same skills. Women leadership has not only improved the economy of a country but also the capability of improving the workplace policies and environment, creating a more diverse workforce. Also, the wage gap is well maintained between the diversified workforces. Thus, it was important to know and understand the factors that help in successful leadership amongst women in the UK's FinTech Start-ups.

1.4 Research Questions

Based on the background research on the concepts of female leadership, and the current status of female leaders in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK, the present study will attempt to address several questions:

1. What factors are linked to create the contents in which female leaders can emerge/ succeed in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK?
2. What role are such factors likely to play in influencing leadership behaviour among female leaders in the UK's FinTech sector?

Following the conceptual query, the present study will attempt to answer the current scenario with regards to leadership in the FinTech start-ups of the UK. Furthermore, the factors that influence leadership qualities amongst females will also be addressed. Besides, the existing programs to develop leadership among females in the FinTech start-up sector will also be studied upon and addressed. And lastly, the steps that can be taken to enhance leadership in the FinTech start-up sector.

1.5 Objectives of the research

Existing literature on female leadership has typically focussed on the glass ceiling problem, and gender disparity that various industries have faced or are facing, in the UK and other countries of the world. In 2008, a report on female leadership, its impact, and factors contributing towards it was undertaken by McKinsey & Company but was not focussed on a single country or sector (Desvaux and Devillard, 2008b). A 2012 World Bank report on gender quotas and female leadership existing in different parts of the world has focussed on the impact of having quota systems in different spheres of life on female leadership (Pande and Ford, 2012). However, very limited studies exist concerning the concept of female leadership and the factors that drive their leadership behaviour, suggesting that very little attention has been given to this subject area of research.

In the case of studies in the UK, there are no specific researches undertaken on the factors contributing to female leadership in any sector within the country. Considering the growing significance of gender parity and equal pay in the UK, and the significant contribution of FinTech sector towards the UK's GDP, it is important that female leadership, their factors, and their significance are studied. This research aims to evaluate the phenomenon of female leadership within FinTech companies in the UK's start-ups sector. The major objectives that will be addressed in this research study are:

- i. To determine the factors that creates successful leaders amongst females in the UK's FinTech start-up sector.
- ii. To determine the role played by these factors in influencing female leadership in the FinTech sector.
- iii. To determine the role of STEM education in encouraging a higher participation and growth opportunities for female leaders in FinTech start-ups of the UK.
- iv. To propose a framework that explains the connection between drivers and successful female leadership within the FinTech sector of the UK.

1.6 Literature Review

1.6.1 Under-representation of women in senior positions

Several studies have been conducted in the financial sector of the UK to determine if women are under-represented and disadvantaged when compared to men (Lathi, 2013; Global Strategy Group, 2016). According to the Equality and Human Rights Commission, this is mainly characterised by a greater occupational concentration by gender than the economy as a whole. Women are prominent in administrative and secretarial jobs but are significantly under-represented in managerial jobs, including those at senior level (Grant Thornton, 2016). Moreover, the culture of long working hours imposed largely by peer pressure can make working in the sector difficult for employees of either sex who want to combine work and family life, even when employers claim to accommodate flexible working arrangements for parents (Innovate Finance, 2014; Oliver Wyman, 2014). In addition to the private sector, there is low female leadership representation in the government institutes too (European Commission, 2010).

The underrepresentation is due to constant reinforcement of political leadership as a male domain; how political systems identify and promote female candidates; and the choices that

women make for themselves that are shaped by their socialisation as well as the realities of political life (Flanagan, Goss and Ecker, 2017). Moreover, certain works of literature also shed light on the theories that identify the reasons for the underrepresentation of women as leaders. “Glass ceiling” is a theory that prevents women from rising to top jobs and “sticky floors” that glue women to lower-level jobs are typical explanations for why women are rarely seen in top positions (Klaile, 2013).

Another theory is statistical discrimination, a phenomenon where decision-makers use observable characteristics such as group identity as a proxy for unobservable, but outcome-relevant, characteristics (Levitt, 2010). The most common theory is that; employers who try to maximise their expected profit will discriminate against women if they believe that women on average are less skilled, less credible or less committed than men (Klaile, 2013).

1.6.2 Factors influencing the success of women leaders in senior positions in FinTech

Various factors impact the success of women leaders in a senior position, which can be divided into social factors, organisational factors and personal factors (Lathi, 2013). The most important factor that impacts success in women leadership is personal determination. Another most important factor is the help and support by the family, children and educational qualification (Aycan, 2004).

In the case of social factors, traditional gender roles are the foremost factor that impacts leadership amongst women in organisations. One of the most common examples is that women work less than men, in less demanding positions and earn less, are very much alive (OECD, 2016). The next part of the social factors is division in education and labour market, where students in the fields of social and health education are dominated by women while men dominate the fields of technology and transport (Frederiksen and Halliday, 2015). Also, it has been found that the number of women in some male dominated industries such as natural resources and environmental studies has increased to some extent, whereas the number of men in women's industries has not increased at the same rate. Despite the bigger role that women

have to play at home, their position in the organisational structure is lower due to a number of reasons as reviewed above.

Organisations play a big role in promoting female leadership (Lathi, 2013). After all, it is the organisation which hires or does not hire a female leader. Organisations and their internal culture affect women's career possibilities and they can act differently to increase diversity and support female leadership (Maule et al., 2015). The first sub-factor of organisational culture is business culture. Mentoring is another factor that has been proved to be an efficient way to enhance one's career development, especially women (European Commission, 2010; AAUW, 2016a). In most cases, managerial help has also been effective in developing leadership qualities and thereby become a successful leader.

Alongside all the other factors technological and physical infrastructure plays a vital part. Today technology is the language of everything. No one can escape it, as the world revolves around technology and technological innovation. In the technology world, what is new today will be obsolete tomorrow and one has to adapt and adopt it with the equal speed. Women leaders need to buckle up to walk alongside men who are considered masters of technology. According to one estimate only 7% females enrolled for computer science. Only 1 in 6 tech specialists in the UK are females. That is why this paper discusses the importance of STEM education for women and how the organisations can be instrumental in helping women.

The last part of the major factors that impact successful leadership amongst women is individual factors (Farley, 2014). The individual factors include networking skills, determination and confidence-building (Lathi, 2013; Farley, 2014). Thus, social skills play a big part in networking, and research supports that it is also the most important strength of female leaders. The networks can be official or unofficial, but in any case, they play an important role as it can be used as places to share, learn, develop and support each other and thereby help in successful leadership. The final part of the individual factors is confidence-building (Aycan, 2004; Innovate Finance, 2014). The confidence building has helped numerous females in becoming a successful leader. Furthermore, the gender division seen in the labour market might lessen in a long-term and it would open more doors for women to advance to management and also diversify leadership in male-dominated sectors (Farley,

2014). In addition, encouragement in taking more risks and trust themselves and their skills along with personality development and the ability to change according to the organisation induces women in becoming successful leaders (Innovate Finance, 2014).

1.6.3 Factors acting as moderators in the success of women leaders

Moderators are the mediators that provide access to women in becoming a successful leader (Lathi, 2013). Some of the characteristics of successful people, such as motivation, natural curiosity, courage, self-management, enjoying being stretched and rising to a challenge, personal will, and fortitude, drive, and flexibility may be innate, but there is no doubt that these characteristics also need to be nurtured and encouraged (Aycan, 2004; O'Neil, Plank, and Domingo, 2015; OECD, 2016).

Many employers give women access to courses in areas they can excel through career development opportunities, but that can often be in their mid-career (Aycan, 2004). Role models can be found close to home or in the people around them, as well as in those at a distance - seen only through the news in faraway places (Lathi, 2013; AAUW, 2016a).

The next part is the role of government in the women's success in being a leader. One of the most common reforms is the adoption of quota, which can be used for many purposes by the government (Klaile, 2013). Gender quotas ensure a certain number of positions for women, for instance in political parties or companies. Public policy that encourages women to be successful, workplaces that reward for encouraging and advancing women, education systems that educate women to the highest standards are just some of the things that are needed to help create an environment in which women are prepared and encouraged to rise to leadership (European Commission, 2010; Diversity Institute, 2012).

1.7 Methodology

In recent years, there has been a subtle rise of women in leadership positions across different areas of society and the corporate world (Levitt, 2010). This domination of female as leaders in the corporate and social world is found to increase in the last few areas of society and many research this phenomenon from different perspectives. Moreover, publications also indicated that teams with mixed-gender are more productive and creative.

Gender disparity is the greatest at some of the highest positions in the business world. 90% perceive that traditions and expectations for male leadership hold women back from full representation, which may explain why only 40% think women, should make up at least half of the top executives at these major corporations (Hoyt and Murphy, 2016). Hence, the main area of the study was the UK's FinTech sector as many pieces of research showed that the women leadership in the finance sector is minimal. The UK's FinTech market is currently worth \$28.8 billion in annual revenue with four companies from the government-backed Future Fifty scheme valued at more than £1 billion (Ernst & Young, 2014; Finch, 2017). Altogether, the Future Fifty companies have a combined value of £11 billion on the London stock market, with an average investment growth of over 63%.

In this research study, the main aim is to understand the influence of different factors on female leadership in the UK's FinTech sector. The study is being conducted using both the secondary and primary sources of information. The researcher aims at generating the primary data through the administration of the survey questionnaire to the existent female leaders in the FinTech sector. Another aim is to understand the challenges faced by them and the areas of improvement and the factors that influence them. The data collected from surveys are supported with interviews of the female leaders leading the chosen FinTech startups. The research could also be utilised for defining an appropriate direction for future studies, forming a standard scale of information to be improved and added upon.

1.7.1 Research Design

The research methodology is an essential part of the research process to guide the researcher in achieving the designated objectives and answering the research questions diligently. The positivist and subjectivist stance of epistemology and ontology branches of philosophical theories was adopted, to allow the researcher to examine the social reality of woman leadership as influenced by the perceptions and behaviours of the various social actors, following a structural approach (Carson et al., 2001; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009; Bhattacharjee, 2012).

Furthermore, the purpose of the research is designated to be descriptive and explanatory, to serve the systematic description of the problem statement and summarise the information, and to explain the relationships between different aspects of the scenario at hand (Kumar, 2011). The proposed study will follow the quantitative approach to collect the data, to examine the factors influencing female leadership on an industry-wide scale. The quantitative data collection will involve the collection of survey responses, leading to the generation of primary data, which facilitates the acceptance or rejection of the proposed hypothesis by the means of structured quantitative data. The present study will also involve the meta-analytic review of the already established results produced by various researchers to conduct secondary research.

1.7.2 Data collection approach

The data collection strategy will involve defining the sampling plan and sample size following the selection of an appropriate sampling technique for data collection. The present study will involve the collection of data from both primary and secondary sources. The collection of primary data will occur by first-hand administration of survey questionnaires to the women leaders currently working in the FinTech sector of the UK.

The questionnaire administration will involve subjecting willing women leader participants from the FinTech sector of the UK (target population) via digitised survey questionnaire, and the respective responses collected.

In the case of secondary data, the data collection for the meta-analytic study will involve the thorough inspection of previous studies reporting statistical results concerning the female leadership as affected by various factor. The secondary data was collected from newspaper articles, reports, publications, journal articles, books, and magazines, having due credibility (Saunders, 2003).

1.7.3 Data analysis

The quantitative data collected from the respondents and the statistically significant data accumulated from the analysis of secondary resources were analysed using statistical software packages. The survey responses were analysed for obtaining descriptive and inferential results using SPSS v21, whereas the already computed effect sizes obtained from the studies was subjected to meta-analysis using the Comprehensive Meta-Analysis software v3.0.

1.8 Justification of Methodology

The inferential mode of analysis of the collected information will thus help in drawing meaningful conclusions regarding the success of female leadership in the UK's FinTech sector. The researcher aims at presenting an informative scenario, which can be used as a guideline for the promotion of female leaders in the FinTech sector.

Reliability and validity of the data was checked by Normality, and Cronbach's test. The results will significantly contribute to the present limited information about female leadership in the FinTech sector. The factors that influence successful leadership skills in women was found accordingly and the research questions was addressed. Also, the current research will be

applicable for future studies, forming a standard scale of information to be improved and added upon.

1.9 Research Origin: Researcher's background

This section introduces the reader to the researcher. Providing background information about the researcher's work, which acts as a link that associates the reader on the topic of the study (Hopkins, 1998). The study will employ an exploratory approach to examine the factors influencing the success of women in leadership roles in FinTech start-ups. Employing exploratory study design allowed the flexibility to change the direction of study with the revelation of new insight or new factors that create successful women leaders in the FinTech start-up firms.

The researcher grew up in India in an orthodox Gujarati family, facing discrimination between a male and female child and it impacted her thought and how she perceived the real world. At a very young age, she eloped to get married and completed her graduation after marriage. That was the time she realised that being a woman does not make her inferior to men and she can empower herself with any knowledge that she desires to achieve. Women leadership became a passion for her and she decided to do something concrete in this field. She started mainly by proving to herself that she is no less than men, besides hard work and passion can be her most important allies.

She worked night shifts for 10 years in international call centres in India as a means to earn a better salary than traditional day jobs before deciding to come to the UK. Before coming to the UK she worked in JP Morgan Chase Bank in India for a little over 3 years. Subsequently coming to the UK she decided to work only with banks. She believed that banking is her forte. She completed her MBA and the MSc in finance in the UK. Alongside studying she worked for Nationwide Building society, HSBC bank, and Citibank over the period of 9 years in the UK.

Although she always thought traditional banking is her strength, she soon realised that banking scene is changing and more banks are adopting technology and investing huge sums to become technologically advanced. The Citibank Europe made one such investment in 2015 during the author’s employment with them. That was the turning point when the author was made to believe that the FinTech is the future of banking. She started by subscribing for ‘The FinTech Magazine’ and also attended a few seminars to understand the new phenomenon.

As 2016 came by she decided to do the DBA. The researcher had decided to keep female leadership in the heart of everything she wanted to do her research on. That is when she read about ‘women in business’, ‘women in leadership’ and how women are racing ahead of men in every sector. She met female Chief Commercial Officer of a start-up company Oh’pen during a job interview and came back without a job but with a lot of inspiration. She was aware the research needed to be done in the banking industry and female leadership, however, the research needed to be in something contemporary at the same time. Therefore, she decided to research women leadership in the UK’s FinTech sector.

1.10 Plan/Structure of the thesis

Table 1-1: Structure of the thesis (Researcher)

Title	Start time	End time	Duration
Introduction	1/09/2017	30/1/2018	4 months
Literature Review	1/2/2018	30/5/2018	3 months
Data Collection	1/4/2018	30/6/2018	2 months
Writing the report, RM, finding, conclusion 4-5 months	1/8/2018	30/1/2019	5 months
Abstract	1/2/2019	28/2/2019	1 month
First Draft	1/3/2019	30/3/2019	1 month
Second Draft	1/4/2019	30/4/2019	1 month

Final Submission	1/5/2019	30/5/2019	1 month
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Figure 1-1: Gantt chart for thesis submission (Researcher)

Table 1-1 and Figure 1-1 shows the structure of the thesis and research map for this study respectively. The figure depicts the important flow of this paper and how the research will progress. Apart from the plan/ structure of the thesis and Gantt Chart, the research map will give direction to the following chapters. Although there are dates and time allotted to each section of this research, the researcher expects the above dates to change slightly according to the changing research needs if any.

Apart from the above, Figure 1-2 below shows the Research map. The map depicts how the research will be carried out. It shows the stages of the entire research from the start to the end. The author started by drawing a circle in the middle of a blank paper to develop the idea. Then key words from interesting papers were connected to the questions such as why, how, when, who, what, under what circumstances etc. Before deciding the actual topic researcher narrowed down the broad questions into more specific issues factors related to the women leadership and factors responsible for the same.

Figure 1-2: Research Map (Researcher)

The process of developing this research began with examining the research problem, i.e. the unequal presence of female leaders in the FinTech workspace as compared to males, and the factors that affect their success in the workplace. The research gap for this problem was then established, i.e. the lack of empirical evidence. Following this the literature review was developed wherein key studies conducted on main elements of this research such as the start-up sector, leadership and female leadership were explored. After this, the initial proposal was developed stating the aim and objectives, purpose of the study and timeline for the research.

After approval of the synopsis, the data collection instruments were developed and invitations were sent out to the targeted participants for filling the questionnaire and answer the interview questions. This was after conducting the pilot test on the data collected wherein the validity and reliability was established. After the required primary data was collected, the writing process of the research was initiated with the literature review, research methodology, data analysis and finally the conclusion. While framing the conclusion, the researcher identified the critical shortcomings in this research and suggested recommendations for further studies in this area of research.

1.11 Conclusion

The main motive for this chapter was to give a brief overview of the FinTech sector in the UK and female leadership in the UK. Technological advancements have profoundly helped in advancing the financial services towards effectiveness and fast operations along with accuracy. However, the concentration of women in the financial industry is a niche, but evidence shows female leaders are more successful than male leaders. Various factors had acted in successful leadership among women as evident from the works of literature. However, moderators also act as a tool in the successful leadership of women. Also, the research methodology that was adopted in this study and data collection methods that was used have been discussed in nutshell along with aim and research questions. In the present chapter, the background and rationale for the study on successful female leadership have been discussed. Based on the background of the study area, the aim and objectives have been proposed, which will be addressed.

The literature review was discussed in brief, to establish the major factors that successfully contribute towards female leadership. Furthermore, a research methodology, stating the research design and hypotheses to be tested has been discussed. Consequently, the present chapter has discussed the thesis plan that explains the flow of different sections of the thesis on successful female leadership within the FinTech sector of the UK. In the next chapter works of literature and publications on these aspects will be discussed broadly.

Chapter: 2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction to the chapter

The chapter appraises the available literature relating to women leadership in general and in the specific context of the United Kingdom's FinTech start-up sector. The rationale of this chapter lies in that it examines the relevant concepts and theories linked to the research subject and identifies if there are any contradictions or gaps in the available literature.

The first section of the chapter underscores the theoretical framework by discussing the social role theory of sex differences and similarities, the role congruity theory, and institutional theory. The theoretical framework acts as the basis of further discussion on the subject.

The next section provides a brief overview of the concept of leadership and whether gender differences exist in leadership. For the purpose of this research, "gender" is classified as male and female. This section chronologically mentions various past researches on the subject to offer an understanding of the evolution and development of the debate around this topic. An evaluation of the present state of women leadership across the world, in the United Kingdom, and specifically in the UK's FinTech start-ups sector has been done in the subsequent section.

The chapter advances with the review of the importance of women leadership. This has been done through a critical review of whether gender diversity leads to better company performance and what all women can bring to the workplace. In the context of this research gender diversity refers to the equitable representation of male and female individuals in an organisation. Further, gender diversity in organisational settings is defined as the proportion of female and male employees that affect the way other employees work and communicate with each other (Joy, 2016). Involvement of both male and female leaders leads to diversity in the thought process, viewpoints, approaches, and execution. This gender diversity helps in effective decision-making. In order to have better decisions and strategic plans, a balanced

composition of female and male leadership is essential. This diversity in leadership, i.e. gender diversity helps in enforcing accountability too (Kebede, 2017). The purpose here is to establish the significance of gender diverse workplaces.

The next section includes a detailed analysis of the factors affecting successful female leadership. This section is divided into 5 subheads: firstly, the socio-cultural influence is discussed followed by the organisational, individual, political, technological and physical infrastructure factors.

Based on the above sections, the chapter then provides the conceptual framework and hypotheses for the research. This is a diagrammatic representation of the anticipated findings of the study. Finally, the chapter gets to an end in the form of the summary of the major themes and ideas investigated under the chapter. The summary also establishes the necessary link of the chapter with upcoming chapters in the study.

2.1 Conceptualising Leadership

2.1.1 Concept of leadership: Overview

“Leadership is one of the most observed and least understood phenomena on earth” (Burns 1978). This statement by Burns during the late 1970s cited in Daft, (2015) is indicative of the controversy around the concept of leadership. The section reviews the concept of leadership as it exists in the literature to conclude what leadership means and if the ambiguity of the concept could be resolved over time or it continues.

Theories of leadership have evolved with time (Horner, 1997; Khan, Khan, & Nawaz, 2016). Initially, Thomas Carlyle in 1847 in his theory said that leaders are born and not made, thus the person would have heroic potential and leadership qualities by birth only. This was the great man theory. Further, the trait theory came where leaders were based on personal, intellectual, and physical traits. In 1940, this trait theory was implemented for differentiating

military and non-military leaders. Though this theory included an important quality, it avoided environmental and situation factors.

Distinctions have been drawn between male and females at the workplace, which included the case of leaders as well. For instance Bales (Bales, 1958) was one of the earliest to suggest that women are more feeling-oriented and less task-oriented than men. However he also suggested that women were more concerned for the feelings of others and were less concerned for their own growth. In the years that followed more different types of leadership emerged such as transactional, transformation and authoritarian leadership in which it was asserted women contained all the qualities necessary for transactional leadership. Since women are more likely to encourage well-being of employees and discouraged unethical practices in an organisation, chances of organisational success is more (Borkowski & Ugras, 1998; G. R. Franke, Crown, & Spake, 1997)

In 1969, contingency or situational theory came which said that there is no specific style for a leader; instead, leaders are the one who can adapt to different situations and work as per relationship-oriented or task-oriented style. Later came the style and behaviour leadership theory, which stated that some style is required in a leader. This style could be democratic (leader take decision after consulting with subordinates), laissez-faire (subordinates take a decision), and autocratic (leader take a decision). Further, process leadership theories were introduced. This includes servant leadership, charismatic leadership, principle centred leadership, and learning organisation. In the late 1970s or early 80s came transactional theories which connected leaders and followers through an agreement i.e. both influence each other. Lastly, the leadership theory that came forward was the transformational theory. Under this, target achievement is done based on the beliefs, attitudes, and values of individuals. Hence, though with the development of organisation and need of an individual, leadership theories evolved still all theories are relevant.

Maslanka, (2004) while investigating the evolution of leadership concept and theories cites Warren Bennis who had proclaimed in the context of leadership during the mid-1980s that never in the past have so many people endeavoured to comment on something so petite designating towards the fact that leadership remains undefined. On the other hand, Northouse,

(2007) defined leadership as *“The influence that particular individuals (leaders) exert upon the goal achievement of others (subordinates) in an organisational context”*. It can be seen as the practice of working with people to perform novel things in a complex and dynamic global business environment. Mendenhall, (2008) cites Rost (1993) to explicate about the ambiguity of the concept of leadership. Though leadership depicts the influence-based relationship between collaborators and leaders to serve the mutual purpose but there exist contrasting characteristics of leadership. Industrial Paradigm Shift concept of leadership consists of leader traits or behaviour, good management, the fulfilment of a leader’s wish, usage of legitimate behaviour, and working on organisational goals. However, all these paradigm characteristics change in the case of post-industrial paradigm concept of leadership. It consists of the process based on influence behaviour that is distinct from the management and is not classified in terms of good or bad. Here, people other than managers are also leaders. Further, collaborator and leader interact with the intent of bringing real change mutually and the work is done for the fulfilment of leader and collaborator wish. Thus, Rost has claimed that despite being a popular subject of research, around 60% of the studies that have endeavoured to summarising leadership in concrete terminology between the 1910 to 1990 have failed to do so. Mendenhall, (2008) fortifies this argument by citing Ralph Stogdill (1974) that literature offers as many definitions of leadership as there have been authors who attempted to define it, indicating the lack of consensus over the concept. Mendenhall, (2008) argues in this context that defining a concept can be complex, time-consuming and expensive. Hence most scholars have dissected the concept into its sub-processes and components. This has led to the emergence of a leadership concept as that similar to its parts rather than reaching a consensus upon a holistic concept of leadership.

Monippally and Pawar, (2010) however offer a simple explanation of the concept leadership by defining it as the process of inspiring others. It has also been said, *“Defining leadership is a complex and elusive problem largely because the nature of leadership itself is complex”* (Daft, Kendrick, & Vershinina, 2010, p. 45). It is mainly concerned with inspiring people to handle the toughest challenge in front of them and encourage them to give in their best.

Leaders have an uncanny talent to see and fit all the different aspects of a situation together by influencing their followers. They manage to forge alliances, take advantage of opportunities, and efficiently accomplish goals. Effective leaders have a positive impact on others around them, which enables them to get assistance from others who have related needs for achievement. A somewhat similar notion of leadership has been put forward by Aubrey, (2011) who stated in an organisational context that leadership is essential to bind together the organisation towards a common goal through inculcating shared vision, showing the direction, inspiring the members, evoking commitment, change and loyalty.

Pierce and Newstrom, (2011) on the other hand assert that on the surface, leadership might appear to be a basic concept but it is hard to define it because it has been perceived in multiple contexts. They elaborate that while some in the past have conceptualised it as a psychological phenomenon that concerns with personal traits of an individual (leader); others see leadership as a sociological concept wherein leadership is the outcome of the process involving the leader, followers and the situation.

Additionally, leadership is explained in terms of what the leader does; from a stylistic perspective i.e., what style does the leader adopt; from a thematic perspective; and from where does the leader come from. Ironically, the term leadership has been employed to non-mutual exclusive areas. Pierce and Newstrom, (2011) also stated that a single perspective of leadership cannot be expected soon.

Giddens, (2012) acknowledges that despite the existence of exhaustive literature on leadership, the concept and definition of leadership is still a subject of contradiction. Leadership has been viewed by Giddens, (2012) as an interactive process wherein the leader provides the required guidance to the followers to pave their way towards a pre-determined goal in the specific situation or settings. Leadership is thus said to involve three components: the leader, the followers and the situation as shown in figure 2-1 below:

Figure 2-1: Leadership Components (Researcher)

One of the major arguments in the literature relating to the concept of leadership is whether management and leadership are the same or different? Algahtani, (2014) conducted one such study to review the literature to compare leadership and management and concluded that while both leaders and managers often perform similar roles, they cannot be treated as one. The study emphasised that the difference between the two should be recognised. The study reviews that in the past leadership has been described as a personality trait; a procedure; competency; and experience; or as an integral function of the management but a single definition has yet to evolve.

The above assertions made by Algahtani, (2014) have been confirmed by Batmanglich, (2015) as well that traditionally leadership has been defined in terms of the leaders' attributes while giving meagre consideration to the role of the followers in the entire process. It is only recently that a holistic approach towards leadership has started to emerge including all the stakeholders in the leadership process. Thus, the contemporary approach to leadership holds it as a psychological-sociological process. Elgie, (2015) also raised concern over the absence of a universally accepted definition of leadership while conceptualising leadership as an inter-

personal process, which involves both leader and the followers. Daft, (2015) proclaims that leadership is an evolving discipline.

Leadership can be regarded as an integral part of the social development as any form of assembly or group or community tends to function in the manner as is led by their leader. There have been various theories which seek to explain the phenomenon of leadership which have tried to define leadership in different ways and have attempted to recognise the attributes and virtues of a successful leader (Hawkins & Edwards, 2015). An analysis of these theories shows that a successful leader needs to possess a variety of qualities including intellectual stimulation, energy, self-confidence, assertiveness, dominance, motivation, honesty, integrity, and charisma. Thus, leadership can be considered as an activity in which an individual tries to get the commitment and promise of others with or without dependence on their formal authority and drives the group towards the attainment of the desired tasks.

Silva, (2016) encapsulates about leadership that it is complex and hard to define the phenomenon. Indicating the lack of consensus on its definition, Silva, (2016) cites Kellerman (2012) who proclaimed that “*there are approximately 1,400 different definitions of the words leader and or leadership.*” The evolution of the concept of leadership has been discussed in the study. Initially, leadership was essentially a personal trait and it was only after World War II that leadership was looked at as a process of influencing others through non-coercive means. During the 1990s the role of the followers in the leadership process started to gain significance. The contemporary definitions of leadership, however, emphasise the context as well. Silva, (2016) underlines the need for defining leadership in concrete words because it is a term that is used widely across different areas of activity. Silva, (2016) thus proposes a novel definition of leadership, which is assumed to fit well with the modern notion of leadership. The researcher believes that leadership is a process in which the followers accept an individual as their leader who through an interactive process influences them towards the accomplishment of common goals.

The discussion undertaken in this section confirms the vagueness of the concept of leadership. But for the sake of current research, it is assumed that leadership is a process of influencing the followers through non-coercive ways and the situation or the context also matters in

leadership. The next section outlines another dilemma of leadership if it is gender-neutral or not.

2.1.2 Gender and Leadership

UNESCO defines gender as the set of responsibilities and role, which male and female do have in cultures, families, and society. Further, it consists of the expectations about aptitudes, characteristics, and behaviour of men and women. Thus the gender analysis is based on the analysis of talents, experiences, knowledge, and needs of female and male to determine the policies and programmes which would help in fulfilment of needs (UNESCO, 2003).

The subject of gender and leadership gained significant research attention during recent years, particularly during the 1970s due to globalisation and the upliftment in the social status of women across the globe (C. Hoyt, 2010; Zosuls, Miller, Ruble, Martin, & Fabes, 2011). Like the very concept of leadership, the ambiguity surrounds the influence of gender on leadership because here too theorists differ widely in their opinions. While many believe males and females have distinct leadership styles and patterns due to biological differences; the literature provides evidence that there is no significant impact of gender on leadership because, in the organisational context, irrespective of the gender, roles assigned is to be performed. A few also argue that it is only the gender stereotypes prevailing in the society that have led to this (Bodla & Hussain, 2009; Alice H Eagly et al., 1990; Moran, 1992).

One of the early works in the direction of gender and leadership was done by Eagly *et al.*, (1990). The study hypothesised that organisational roles rather than gender influence the leadership patterns. The study also asserted that while social scientists maintain that no prominent distinction could be made in the leadership patterns of males and females; the authors of non-technical books are usually the advocators of gender differences in leadership styles. The study endeavoured to develop on this contradiction by revealing that both these groups based their notions on different data types (social scientists procured data from empirical studies whereas authors of non-technical books gathered data from managers or

based their ideas on their own organisational experiences) hence difference in opinions was obvious.

A meta-analysis based upon 162 studies conducted in the past in this area of gender differences and leadership styles between 1961 and 1987 was conducted to investigate the truth. The study deduced that although statistically significant there was only insignificant variance in the leadership styles of males and females in real organisational settings. The most substantial difference between male and female leaders as noted by the study was that men prefer the autocratic and directive style of leadership as against the democratic or participative style being preferred by their female counterparts. However, the study established the need for thorough research on gender differences in leadership in the future (Alice H Eagly et al., 1990).

In the same year, Acker, (1990) contradicted the viewpoint held by Eagly et al., (1990) by proclaiming that although feminists authors believe that organisational hierarchies are mostly gender-neutral, the real picture is different. The study highlighted that although such gender differences in organisational leadership are not apparent at times, they are immersed in the organisational culture itself. Acker, (1990) declared that masculinity pervades the organisational processes.

In the 2000s, an important study in the context of gender differences in leadership was conducted by Vecchio, (2002) who asserted that there have been exhaustive changes in the conceptualisation of this subject over the time. An elaborate review of past research on the subject was done and it was found that gender differences in leadership are vague. Vecchio, (2002) agreed there are certainly stylistic differences in the leadership of males and females but these are not significant in an organisational context.

In the same year, the UKI, (2002) highlighted the possibility that sex differences in leadership may be due to the inherent biological variations in males and females but these differences are insignificant unless these are reinforced by the socialisation process and/or the gender stereotyping that prevails in the society establishing the specific gender-related role expectations. The study also drew attention to that maybe researchers in the past had found it

invalid to manipulate the biological and socialisation factors that is why they failed to identify and tackle the underlying reasons of such gender-based differences in leadership.

Bodla and Hussain, (2009) researched Pakistani context and acknowledged that gender does influence the leadership patterns. The research argues that due to inherent gender characteristics, males and females lead differently despite being assigned the same leadership position in the organisation. Hoyt, (2010) also agreed to the gender differences in leadership and proclaimed that both men and women vary in their leadership traits and styles. But, Hoyt, (2010) also clarified that gender does not impact the effectiveness of a leader. Both males and females have distinct traits and if they are assigned roles that are congruent to their inherent traits, both can be equally effective as leaders in an organisational context. The study also underscored the role of gender stereotyping that often exaggerates the gender gap in organisations and lead to misconceptions about gender and leadership.

Jonsen, Maznevski, and Schneider, (2010) rejected the notion of significant gender differences in the leadership and stated that although many in the past have claimed about such gender-based distinctions, there is no strong empirical evidence about the same. The study also asserted that this is one of the leaderships relating debates that reveal inconsistency. Like Hoyt, (2010), Jonsen, Maznevski, and Schneider, (2010) also acknowledged the role of gender stereotypes in shaping gender-specific organisational roles.

Jackson and Parry (2011) cited in Schedlitzki and Edwards, (2017) affirm the gender differences in leadership based on the 'Great Man theory of leadership'. They stated that initially this theory was the guiding theory and meant to portray how male leaders have been performing throughout history. The theory, as the name suggests, was essentially masculine. Even many subsequent theories of leadership were male-dominated until during the 1990s when feminist characteristics also appeared in the leadership context. There has been a gradual realisation that feminist leadership could offer strategic advantages to the organisation enhancing its overall wellbeing. But this has also led to gender stereotyping in organisational leadership Schedlitzki and Edwards, (2017).

The review of the literature thus illuminates that gender and leadership is a disputed issue. Still, no consensus could be reached about the role of gender in leadership. However, biological differences between males and females and the gender stereotyping are significant in this regard. The upcoming section sheds light on the current status of women leadership.

2.2 Evaluating the present state of women leadership

2.2.1 Leadership across the globe

Talking about the women leaders in Africa, a qualitative study conducted by African Woman and Child Feature Service (2010) explored the political decision making and the role of females in the Eastern part of Africa. It was revealed that women's representation in Parliament is about 50% which is the highest in the world. Further, the report also explicated that Kenya and Sudan have a very low representation of females in political decision-making while Uganda, Tanzania, and Rwanda are best-performing countries in this context. Service delivery, gender, and institutional culture were the areas which were studied regarding the impact of a critical mass of women on them. And it was emphasised how females' movement in the 5 Eastern African nations promotes gender mainstreaming in all by-laws, strategies, and organisations. Additionally, the study also observes the quota system and the degree to which it either assists or hampers representation and participation of women in decision-making.

While the report by African Woman and Child Feature Service (2010) pointed out the women leadership in the developed country like Africa, Upadhyay (2010) talked about the women leadership in India which is a developing nation. Upadhyay (2010) mentioned that age, educational status, social class, geographical location are some of the different variables that determine women empowerment in India. Emphasising about women empowerment in India, Upadhyay (2010) also accentuated that though national, state and local (Panchayat) levels have policies on women's empowerment in various sectors such as political participation, education, health, economic opportunities, gender-based violence, etc. yet there are substantial gaps

between policy progressions and real practice at the communal level (Upadhyay 2010, Ghosh & Narendran 2017).

In the same year, Cheung & Halpern (2010) asserted that the advancement of women in the corporate world is not up to the mark even after many years of women's movement in various industrialised Western societies. Moreover, females are stuck in middle management in most of the organisations. However, in China which is having the second-largest economy in the world, women are in a better position. About 16.8% of the women in China are the heads of the Communist party, government departments, institutions, and other enterprises. Census and Statistics Department, Government of the Hong Kong Special Administrative Region (2007) in Cheung & Halpern (2010) explicated that in Hong Kong which is more westernised and economically rich distinct administrative area, women comprise 29.1% of individuals employed as executives and officers. This was witnessed when Hong Kong was reunified with China in 1997.

A year later, Trzcinski & Holst (2011) presented the scenario of leadership and managerial position in the labour market of Germany. They also threw light on gender differences in Germany. Trzcinski & Holst (2011) asserted that a flawless hierarchy subsists for males regarding how status within the labour market was linked with individual life gratification. Subjective life satisfaction was experienced highest by the men in the leadership position. However, in case of women, no statistically substantial variances were detected among females in high-level managerial ranks, females who functioned in non-high-level ranks, and females who are specific in household production, with no fieldwork at all. They also substantiated that male can "have it all", but the female must still select between profession and domestic work in Germany which calls for a debate.

Similarly, Homma, Motohashi and Ohtsubo, (2013) also talked about the participation of women in the organisations at a higher level. They examined the existing status of gender parity in educational associations in Japan and queried about the number of females participating in leadership accomplishments at society discussions and annual conferences, as these undertakings are indispensable in shaping systematic professions. Their study revealed

obvious prejudice against women scientists, and a necessity to elevate awareness and consciousness to move nearer to parity for upcoming generations.

Further, Markham (2013) examined the existing status of American women in politics and makes the case for the complete and reasonable contribution of women in communal life. He also reviewed the unswerving and unintended barriers that occur to inhibit female's political involvement and analysed approaches that have been used to upsurge it. Markham (2013) came out with an opinion that by raising the voice of women in society, improvement in the economy of that country takes place. The growing participation of women in societal issues leads to improvement in education and health performance of that country, along with economic development. Further, if the political contribution of women is increased and they are empowered then this will assist nations in developing significant democratic institutions that can then instigate to positively address matters associated with human rights, security, physical well-being, jobs, and social development.

In Russia, women were disheartened from achieving high-ranking monetary and party-political leadership ranks. Moreover, they were underpaid and there were no consistent means of security for those females who grieved sexual harassment at the place of work. Females were demanded to work upon a dual role in both the specialised and the household areas (HARDWICK, 2014).

While Cheung & Halpern (2010) pointed that women are occupying leading positions in China, Grass-Oguma and George, (2016) contradicted the same stating that in Chinese society traditional family structures linger to play a significant role despite modernisation. This resulted in the inclination of women towards their family role. Percentage of women in China occupying senior position is very low. This is evident from the fact that women occupied 8% of the ExCo positions in the Chinese firms while in North America and Europe the percentages are 21 and 16 respectively in the year 2016.

In the above section, a brief overview was presented concerning the present status of leadership roles played by the females across the globe. It was found that there are various facets which determine the participation of the women at the leading position in different fields. Females

frequently find themselves in a dual drag once they progress into leadership positions. They must be careful not to give the impression of being too masculine or too feminine. While also characterizing the male worker by displaying manly behaviours and steady obligation to the firm.

2.2.2 Leadership in the UK

For a long time, various scholars including Vinnicombe & Singh (2002) are emphasising upon a need to modify in the manner in which leadership development approach has been adopted by the various organisations. This is because they ultimately result in the multiplication of male leaders. Talking about the scenario of the female leadership in the UK, Vinnicombe & Singh (2002) explained that the hidden potential of women has not been properly explored and therefore handling diversity and evolving tomorrow's assorted leaders are significant responsibilities for leadership in the organisations of the UK. To enhance career opportunities and imbibe leadership qualities in women, there is an intense need for women-specific training in organisations of the UK.

The leadership role undertaken by females in politics was highlighted by Bochel and Bochel, (2007). They pointed out that the number of women that become council leaders as compared to men is less while they are equal in number to hold the position in the cabinet. They found out that in the UK, men are more likely to be accountable for the economic development, regeneration and corporate affairs while women are taking up positions in areas such as education, communal issues, and social services. In the consecutive year, female representation was also mentioned by Bochel & Bochel (2008) elucidating that there are both resemblances and dissimilarities in the manner that female and male councillors in leadership ranks identify of their starring role and characters.

However, the role of women leaders in the UK's construction industry and their professional obstructions was mentioned by Ginige et al., (2008). They mentioned that since many years there has been concern about the dearth of women leaders in the construction industry of the

UK. A research was carried out by Ginige et al. (2008) involving four case studies that were advanced around four female leaders in the sector to ascertain the starring role and the obstructions threatening them. The outcomes of the study revealed that the role of women leaders in the construction sector is yet to be amended both in terms of quantity of leaders and the importance of their starring role. Additionally, the study also discovered that women leaders in construction sector confront career obstructions which inhibit them from progressing in the direction of leadership positions.

While Ginige et al. (2008) talked about the leadership position of females in the UK's construction sector, a report by Learning and Skills Improvement Service (2009) highlighted the role played by females in the educational sector of the UK. The report intended to ascertain the career advancement obstructions for females and suggested the worthy practice that would guarantee that women are well signified at the top. This quantitative research entailed about 171 men and women who contributed in 8 provincial research proceedings and 470 females, primarily middle and senior executives, who replied to a virtual investigation. Lack of support from the colleagues, inflexible working hours, and discriminatory practices were some of the barriers that were faced by the women. However, respondents were very distinct about who they believed should take some accountability for boosting the employment of more woman high-ranking leaders and principals, narrating that college committees, principals, senior administration squads, management, and communal agencies all have a role to play.

A report by Government Equalities Office (2010) advocated that 51% of the population in the UK are women. 19.4% of them are members of the parliament, 30.8% of the women in England are local councillors, 46.7% of the women are the members of Welsh Assembly, and 34.8% of the females are members of the Scottish Parliament. The government of the UK is taking necessary measures to enhance the leadership participation of women in politics. They have altered the law to permit political parties to employ all-female shortlists in native, nation-wide and European polls. Moreover, they have also made arrangements for Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic (BAME) Women Councillors Taskforce to upsurge the count of BAME female councillors.

Further Baxter (2012) carried out a study in the UK to discover that single speakers can change the typical roles given to them according to the situational demand and make it influential conversational assets and thus achieve the objectives of leadership, though marked by sexual characteristics. The study was based on a Research Council-funded study of 14 high-ranking leaders entailing 7 male and 7 female each directing at least one high-ranking management summit in the UK. Kanter in Baxter (2012) stated that there are 4 accepted 'role traps' for female leaders in male-dominated companies mainly mommy, tame girl, seductress, and iron maid, grounded on familiar ancient epitomes of females in authority. The research also provided renewed visions for both management and sociolinguistic thinking.

Talking about the scenario of female leaders in the UK, Bierema (2016) pointed out that to assume leadership roles, females in the UK are well prepared. Though they have the determination and qualification, yet they do not fit into gendered structural images of perfect workers. While working in organisations, they find themselves in the double bind and there remains conflict between their work and personal life. Bierema (2016) also mentioned that existing human resource development (HRD) theories incompetently tackles the matters and challenges faced by female leaders since maximum leadership theories are built on fortunate white males hence, it is extremely important to develop new theories with women in the center.

Though all the above scholars predominantly mentioned about the gender disparity and dearth of women at leadership positions in organisations, Brosnan (2016) stated that the number of females in senior management has witnessed a little rise. However, they also mentioned that something is not right which resulted in a lack of females in senior positions. Pamela Harless in Brosnan (2016) pointed out that the meagre performance of the UK may be because of a wider philosophy of leadership that does not give significance to more womanly individualities.

In the above section, a brief review was presented about female leadership in the UK. To encourage female in taking leadership roles, there is ardent need to figure out where in their aptitude pipeline females are confronting with obstructions and dropping off the way to high-ranking leadership.

2.2.3 Leadership in the UK's FinTech start-up sector

Despite being more diverse and dynamic than conventional banking, the FinTech start-ups sector is still finding it hard to redefine the gender-based status quo. Women representation in the global FinTech start-up sector is quite low as compared to other sectors. In a recent study executed by DHR International, the head-hunters, it was deduced that as compared to the traditional banking sector where the women representation in the boardroom is 22%, only 8% women could find a place in the boardrooms of FinTech start-up sector globally. The results were ascertained based on the study of 268 such companies across 19 nations and the world's 30 biggest banks. The study attributed the low women representation in the industry to the fact that traditionally both finance and technology i.e., the parent sectors of the FinTech start-up sector have been male-dominated. National differences were however observed as on one hand there was only 4% of women leaders in French and Germany's FinTech start-up sector, in the UK, it was 8%. For a better gender balance in this industry, change must be initiated at the top and diversity in the workforce is welcomed (Arnold, 2017).

Innovate Finance has elaborated female representation in the UK's FinTech start-up sector. This is the organisation that portrays the nation's FinTech start-up community. It has been claimed in its 2016 Power List of women in FinTech start-ups that although gender equality is improving but at a very slow pace. However, it was pointed out that most of such improvement is taking place at the junior levels and it is still a challenge to find women leaders in this industry. More emphasis on STEM (science, technology, engineering, and maths) subjects in women education can improve the situation (Rutter, 2017).

Lack of venture capital options has been ascertained as the prominent cause of lesser women in the FinTech start-up sector in a recent survey published by Wayra and Astar-fanshave. The findings of the survey stated that financial services being male-dominated, men are 86% more likely to get venture capital than their female counterparts thus compelling the women to rely upon self-funding options and consequently demotivating women entrepreneurship in FinTech start-ups (Smith-Meyer, 2016).

2.3 Importance of women leadership

2.3.1 Gender Diversity (women) leads to better company performance

As mentioned earlier, gender in leadership has emerged as an area of research interest since the 1970s. Leadership has been regarded as a very broad concept, and there have been various theories, which identify different styles of leadership. Female leadership can be considered as just a single branch of this big model and has, therefore, been defined in various ways.

Certain people believe in the ability of the women to be and act as their leaders, while others may remain sceptical and regard it as a matter of equality and advocating the right of women to have the equal opportunities (Palmu-Joronen, 2009, p. 172).

Historically, women have been stereotyped with domestic roles of homemaking and childbearing while men have been typically supposed to be the breadwinners or the economic providers in the family (Blakemore, Berenbaum, & Liben, 2013; Njiru, 2013). While gender diversity is increasingly being recognised as essential in the corporate scenario, gender inequality is still prevalent in all spheres of corporate activity (C. Hoyt, 2010; Schedlitzki & Edwards, 2017). Gender inequality refers to the bias faced by women against men with regards to a number of factors such as participation in the workplace, benefits offered and pay scale, participation in education, etc. Discrimination is at the root of gender inequality. Inequality also pertains to distorted allocation of responsibilities among the genders at the workplace. Auditing, member of compensation committee, and decision-making power is not given to female employees. Thus, though gender diversity is applied in an organisation but still inequality persists (Rebérioux & Roudaut, 2017). This section offers a critical perspective on the outcomes of gender diversity on company performance.

According to a report by World Bank Group, (2014), women constitute around 66.6% of the total working hours globally, manufacture more than half of the world's food and bear and rear

children, still, there has been existing discrimination of the absence of adequate protection against it.

*Figure 2-2: Trend of female leadership globally (Thornton, 2012)
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From the figure 4 above, it can be seen that between the year 2004 and 2009, there was a steady increase in the percentage of women in senior management until it started reducing and went back to almost the same level of 2004. There might be variations in this data based on different countries, however, it has been seen that the global average level has not risen in recent years. In 2013, however, the percentage of the global average of women in senior management positions increased to reach back to the level it was in 2009. Also, it has been seen that the number of organisations with a female CEO has shown a positive increase globally. However, in 2011 the drop can be seen in the growth of female leadership globally. One of the reasons for this decrease is that in case of certain countries, as they grew richer, there is fewer financial constraints for a family and female prefers to stay at home for living a quality life. Further demographic transition led to increase in dependency rate thus mothers are forced to take care of family. This was mainly seen in case of emerging countries i.e. BRICS, APAC, ASEAN, and Latin America countries (Thornton, 2012). In 2012, the percentage of global companies

with a female CEO was 9% which increased to 14% in 2013 (Elsi Lahti, 2013). It was good news as the number of female CEOs had reached an all-time high. A solitary female CEO doesn't perform superior to her male partner while controlling for a particular gender in an organisation, however, a higher rate of gender diversity all through the organisation has a positive effect on performance. Furthermore in more recent studies by Peterson Institute for International Economics indicated that companies in the MSCI World Index recorded return on equity of 10.1% with strong female leadership and gender diversity annually, against 7.4% for those without gender diversification and female leaders. The same is depicted below in figure 2-3 below (L.-E. Lee, Marshall, Rallis, & Moscardi, 2013).

Figure 2-3: Women's leadership and accountability in an organisation (L.-E. Lee et al., 2013)

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Meier, Mastracci, and Wilson, (2006) claimed that more women at an organisation's base level enhance overall organisational performance. Adams and Ferreira, (2008) although proclaimed about multiple benefits of gender diversity to a firm's performance but overall they contend that the average impact of gender diversity on firms is negative.

A similar notion was put forward by Daunfeldt and Rudholm, (2012) who included data from 20,487 limited companies in Sweden during 1997-2005 to ascertain the impact of gender diversity in the boardroom on the firms' performance. The study alleged that in the past most studies have claimed that gender diversity improves firms' performance because gender-diverse board leads to a better understanding of contemporary diverse marketplaces; enhances the firm's innovativeness and market reputation; improves decision-making but they argued that usually these claims were based upon the data of large firms thus offered ambiguous results. Daunfeldt and Rudholm, (2012) also argued that most past studies have failed to consider reverse causality i.e. whether improved firm's performance is an antecedent or outcome of gender diversity. They, therefore, included firms of all sizes in their sample and studied reverse causality. The study concluded that an increase in gender diversity leads to negative returns on total assets after two years while it has no such impact during the earlier years. Daunfeldt and Rudholm, (2012) thus oppose the legal requirements of hiring women to the boardroom positions.

Pletzer *et al.*, (2015) although did not find a negative relationship between female representation on corporate boards and the firm's financial performance like Daunfeldt and Rudholm, (2012). But they deduced on the basis of meta-analysis conducted on the data gathered from 20 studies on 3097 companies that have been published in peer-reviewed academic journals that there is no significant relationship between women representation on the board and the financial performance of the firm, if other factors are not considered. The study, therefore, recommended that gender diversity should be considered for ethical reasons i.e. for being fair towards the females but it has nothing to do with the firm's performance.

In the same year, Post and Byron, (2015) also endeavoured to find out the impact of gender diversity on a firm's financial performance through statistically combining the outcomes of 140 previous studies. They concluded that the status of shareholders and that of the gender parity in a country affect this relationship. The study asserted that countries with greater gender equality tend to witness a more positive relationship between female board representation and a firm's financial performance. The study also put forward that countries where shareholder protection is high, higher female representation in the board leads to better accounting results.

However, Post and Byron, (2015) acknowledged that females surely lead to better monitoring and strategy implementation thus females must be given fair representation in the boardrooms.

Archer, (2016) however have an altogether different opinion than those discussed above like Adams and Ferreira, (2008) and Daunfeldt and Rudholm, (2012) suggesting that women in leadership positions in the corporate do lead to better company performance and that improvement in performance is significant as against the opinions of Pletzer *et al.*, (2015). According to the study conducted by the Peterson Institute for International Economics involving 21,980 firms in 91 countries cited in Archer, (2016), the impact cannot be assessed on the basis of a single female CEO in the company but for the positive impact on a firm's performance, gender diversity should be promoted throughout the organisation. Archer, (2016) also cites the conclusions drawn by the study executed by MSCI World Index which revealed that firms with strong female leadership have ended up securing 10.1% Return on Equity (RoE) per annum as against the 7.4% RoE recorded by the firms without female leadership. Like the Peterson Institute for International Economics, MSCI also established the need for more women throughout the organisation and asserted that at least 3 women on the board are essential to witness the positive results of organisational gender diversity.

According to the report by (Deloitte, 2015) technology, media, and telecommunication is the part of one of the industries which has seen women participation in the board at high rate. The report shows that due to trickle-down effect of having women in board led to encouraging other females, breaking stereotypes, and having quality in wage gap between women and men. Even the global involvement of females as board member though has risen at slow rate i.e. from 12% in 2013 to 15% in 2015 but still it shows some improvement. A study by Fortune 500 has also shown that the company having more involvement of female employees as leaders in form of board directors led to have higher return on assets (ROA) by 42%, return on equity (ROE) by 53%, and return on capital invested by 66%. (Molina, Lin, & Wood, 2015). This report was further supported by Qian (2016b) which states that if a telecommunication company has female leaders more than 25% then best ROE could be seen. This is represented in the figure 2-4 below:

Figure 2-4: Impact of % of female board members on Return on equity (Qian, 2016)

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In its SRI report, it claims that gender diversity often awards multiple benefits on the firms including enhanced productivity, higher innovation, decreased employee turnover, and improved decision-making and better employee satisfaction.

However, contrary to these findings by Morgan Stanley, Elsesser, (2016) put forward the arguments raised by great theorist, Alice Eagly that the most discussed benefits of gender diversity in the form of higher profits, higher CEO remuneration and better problem-solving could not be the outcome of mere higher percentage of women in the boardroom; there are in fact multiple factors contributing to these. Like Daunfeldt and Rudholm, (2012), Elsesser, (2016) raised the issue of reverse causality and the presence of many unknown variables that could have led to firms' better financial performance rather than solely attributing it to the gender diversity. Elsesser, (2016) also rejects the notion that women lead to better problem-solving and more productivity and stated that although adding women could help attain their perspectives as well on any organisational problem but that does not always mean better problem-solving; at times it only results into chaos in the organisation. Similarly, regarding CEO remuneration as well, it may be due to the presence of third variable Elsesser, (2016) claimed.

The discussion held in this section provides that although more women in the workplace should be promoted on ethical grounds as far as its benefits for the organisations are concerned, the literature is divided on this. The next section throws light upon what all women can bring to an organisation to critically evaluate the concept of gender diversity at workplaces.

2.3.2 What women can bring to an organisation?

During recent years, there has been mounting concern worldwide over the representation of females in the organisational context (Daunfeldt and Rudholm, 2012; Blakemore, Berenbaum and Liben, 2013; Njiru, 2013; Elsesser, 2016). The previous section shed light upon the multiple benefits an organisation can reap by hiring women at the leadership positions but at the same time, it was also underscored that merely hiring more women do not certainly lead to the improved financial performance of the firm. This section takes the topic further by reviewing what all the women can bring to an organisation apart from influencing the firm's overall performance.

Although women constitute around half of the global population, their financial participation across all the countries of the world is highly variable and seems to decline noticeably as one move up the organisational hierarchy of most of the firms. It has been seen that the participation of women has a positive impact on the financial as well as the non-financial performance of corporate. Catalyst, (2007) compared various Fortune 500 companies based on the number of women on their boards with the financial performance of their organisation. It was found on comparing the top and last quartile of companies with female representation, that there was a significant difference in the corporate performance of both the groups. Financially, it was seen that the return on equity of companies with high female employees increased by 53%, profitability increased by 42%, and the return on capital investment increased by 66% (Langowitz and Minniti, 2010). It was also discovered that organisations with a minimum of three women on the board produced the best outcomes.

A study was done by McKinsey & Co., (2007) stated that increase in women participation as leaders led to improve the financial performance of the company thus confirming that female

leadership does have impact on the performance of FinTech start-ups Industry. They found that those organisations which had the highest gender diversity i.e. more female leaders saw a much higher Return on Equity (10%), a better operating margin (48%), and a higher stock in their equity prices (70%). Thus, companies having higher proportion of women leaders tend to be the companies with best performance. Further, it has also been seen that having at least one woman on the board of a company decreases their probability of going bankrupt by 20% (Wilson and Atlantar, 2009). However, in case of the present study, the aim is to assess the factors affecting successful female leadership in the UK's FinTech start-ups organisations, rather than to assess the status of gender diversity in these companies.

Meier, Mastracci, and Wilson, (2006) asserted that women bring in distinct skills in the organisation and play a crucial role but unfortunately women have always been neglected and under-compensated in the organisations. In their research on “women in the boardroom and their impact on governance and performance” including US firms, Adams and Ferreira, (2008) stated that in a gender diverse boardroom, not only that female director have better attendance records than their male counterparts but the attendance of male directors also shows improvement.

A study by McKinsey “Women Matter” presented the analysis done by Eagly of the nine key leadership behaviours based upon the research of Bernard Bass and Bruce Avolio to identify the difference in male and female leadership. This study mainly determine that leadership behaviours of men and women are different and there is certain leadership quality of women that tend to improve the corporate performance. There exist about 9 leadership skills which affect the organisational performance i.e. expectations and reward, role model, people development, participative decision making, individualistic decision making, inspiration, intellectual stimulation, control and corrective action, and efficient communication. Study reveal that women in comparison to men demonstrate more frequently “people development”, “expectations and rewards”, “participative decision making”, “role model, and “inspiration”.. The figure 2-5 below gives a detailed account of the nine dimensions of leadership behaviour and the findings relating to gender differences in leadership behaviour (Desvaux & Devillard, 2008). Based on the classification of leadership behaviours, women tend to reinforce

leadership team, work environment and values, and accountability dimensions while men reinforce external orientation, and coordination and control. It shows that women leaders are more people and development focused while men are autocratic and controlling. Women believe in inspiring others and inclusive decision making, and men believe in individualistic decision making. Men also support corrective action and added control. Whereas men and women both are good in communicating and intellectual stimulation. If a company can implement effective leadership along with having diversity in gender, then that company would strategically attain an opportunity of developing their competitive edge. Thus, each gender play an important role in the organisation. Apart from improving the financial performance, gender diversity presence helps in acquiring competitive edge to differentiate the company from others.

Figure 2-5: Difference in adaptation and usage of leadership behaviours by Gender

(Desvaux and Devillard, (2008).

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The study also detailed into the organisational impact of the male and female leadership behaviours as cited in the figure 2-6 below. Figure 8 explains that the leadership traits demonstrated more by women lead to the development of leadership team, the establishment

of work environment and values, and motivation i.e. these are the distinct ways in which women improve the organisational performance if they are in the leadership positions. In a nutshell it is depicting that women provide direction, take accountability, provide coordination and control, they lead by example, encourage innovation, and develop people.

Figure 2-6: Organisational Impact of leadership behaviours applied more frequently by women. (Desvaux & Devillard, 2008).

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Lahti, (2013) elaborated upon the distinct skills that women bring in an organisation like Meier, Mastracci, and Wilson, (2006), Lahti, (2013) stated that while males are usually more aggressive, focused and demonstrate particular traits like competitiveness, and goal orientation; females are more process-oriented and social, and they like to get into the details of everything and involve everybody in the process. Unlike males, females adopt horizontal communication style which is based upon the principles of equality and team building. Lahti, (2013) also maintained that women tend to have a subjective view towards reality thus give

importance to intuitions, experiences, and feelings. It is also proclaimed by Lahti, (2013) that with more women in the organisation, the overall work environment is better and ethical.

Women are also said to bring in improved innovation and teamwork in an organisation if results of the study conducted by Morgan Stanley, (2016) are trusted. The study claimed that gender diversity results in better decision-making, widening the customer base and the development of novel goods and services.

According to the study, the benefits of more women in the organisation stretch beyond individual organisations to the nation as whole because it signifies enhanced labour supply, better productivity, improved earnings, and thus mitigated poverty especially in the developing nations. In the context of aging economies like the U.S., Europe, and North Asia, the study maintained that more women in the workforce ease the burden of a shrinking workforce. The findings of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) have also been mentioned in the study to reinforce the notion of more women in the workplaces which stated that with a 50% reduction in the gender gap, a 6% improvement in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) can be anticipated for the member nations by 2030.

O'Brien (2017) shed light upon that usually female leaders are more comprehensive in their behaviour and focus on individual development in the workplaces. These traits impart multiple benefits to the organisations in the form of better employee engagement, satisfaction, and retention. O'Brien (2017) also claimed that women welcome a multiplicity of ideas hence by hiring more women to the leadership positions, firms across the world have experienced multi-faceted benefits. Moreover, it has been seen that firms with more women on their boards execute better corporate governance policies and follow a more ethical behaviour (G. Franke, 2007). Producing more women leaders have a significant positive impact on a country's GDP and the welfare of next generations as well as demonstrated by Booz & Co., (2012) as this study calculated the estimated increase on a country's GDP after incorporating more female leaders in the economy.

It is evident from the discussion that whether or not women participation in the workforce can be quantified in money terms for the organisational performance but they do exert a positive

influence on the organisational well-being. The discussion revealed that though fewer women leaders exist in the organisation but eventually the global participation of women is increasing. Different companies have analysed the impact of having women leaders as board members and result depicts that presence of female and male leaders tend to have better decision making. As each gender has its own relevance in the management of the company, gender diversity gives the company a competitive edge along with improving its financial performance. Hence, with the evolution of economy, companies should also break the stereotypes related to women and by acquiring effective leadership behaviour and gender diversity should move towards becoming the better performer.

2.4 Factors affecting successful female leadership

Women now in the male-dominated industries, seek the opportunities to work as a leader by due to perspectives and many other reasons, they face various challenges which either affect their performance or force them to quit. This dominance of male exists from past and these challenges work as the glass ceiling for female. Though women are trying to break these barriers and enter in various fields like government, entertainment, technology, or justice, but still factors do prevail which discourage them. Study by Kendall (2018) state that with engagement in organisation and business culture, there exist some inevitable demand and supply side challenges, which women have to face. Usually traditional perspectives in the organisation prevails due to which male employees are more than female employees and even the organisation consider the male behaviour and traits as the suitable way of proceeding thus classifying women as non-suitable for leadership. Along with these demand side factor, double binds (the need of compromising your own beliefs and purpose due to organisational pressure) do exist for females. Further, stereotypes represent social factors which influence the leadership of females negatively. Apart from social factors, individual factors like underestimation of self-competencies, lack of self-confidence and motivation or acceptance of the stereotypes, tend to reduce the efficiency of female employees and even discourage them. Thus, all these challenges in the path of having successful and effective leadership by female,

worked as the base for this study. Hence, based on the findings of Kendall, this study is further done to identify the impact of social and individual factors on success of female leadership.

2.4.1 Society-cultural factors

The social role theory states that “Individuals have been identified as males and females and they occupy different roles in the social framework and are usually judged against the parameters against which they ought to behave” (A H Eagly, Wood, & Diekmann, 2007). Therefore, this theory propagates that males and females have different skills and attitudes and therefore, they behave in different manners. It mainly believes that differences and similarities between both the genders exist mainly due to the role distribution of men and women within the society.

The study by Kiamba (2008a) suggests that women aspire of attaining the leadership position in private as well as public sector. Inclusion of female employees is the fundamental human right in various countries and fair representation in an organisation but still there exists various barriers in the path of leadership for women. Usually a patriarchal system is followed according to which male members of the family has the decision-making power. Despite being educationally qualified, women are considered incompetent in making any decision. Further, women are classified as the domestic sphere and has the role of homemaker only. This is the basic boundary which each woman must follow. For pursuing a leadership profession, it is required to interact with other people and go out which is labelled as unfit for a wife or mother. These kinds of stereotyping also prevent women from entering in leadership profile. Even families don't support the working women and even sometimes remove the family support. In case of appointing a women employee, it is considered that they are not suitable for executive type profile as it requires more of hard work, stress, and long working hours, and as women has home responsibilities too thus, they can't perform this work efficiently. Male employees are much more superior in term of having capability of doing it. This categorisation of the abilities between male and female has worked as the base for analysing the effective leadership of female and determining the socio-cultural barriers in the path of leadership for female.

The social mindset has acted as an impediment in the way of women leadership since times immemorial. The conventional gender stereotypes of males going out of the homes as breadwinners while females are expected to stay at home to fulfil the domestic responsibilities of family and childcare are still evident in the 21st century. While modern women endeavours to achieve an equal footing with men by managing both work and home but literature offers evidence that socio-cultural factors pose specific challenges for the women (C. Hoyt, 2010; Kiamba, 2008b; Okafor, Fagbemi, & Hassan, 2011a).

In most countries of the world, females are regarded as inferior as compared to men. Due to this belief, women are denied access to job opportunities which are mainly reserved for males, including positions related to administration, property matters and other leadership roles. In today's society, gender roles are more clearly divided with men paying more emphasis on material success and assertiveness and women focusing more on the quality of life and modesty (Hofstede & Hofstede, 2005, p.112).

Societal factors include the various indirect factors that have an impact on organisational as well as individual behaviour. According to these factors, the standards, expectations, and customs are set by the society which affect individuals and organisations alike which negatively impacts female leadership. Societal factors are considered as the most tedious and time-consuming amongst the other factors to modify due to their effect on numerous dimensions of life and hence, are not easily controllable. The studies confirm the existence of stereotypes that women work less as compared to men or should be restricted to less demanding positions or be rewarded less (Sandberg, 2013).

Kiamba (2008) captured the socio-cultural perspective about the underrepresentation of women in leadership positions by stating that historically leadership is a masculine phenomenon and despite much advancement, the common belief is that men are better leaders than women. (Kiamba, 2008b) cited different authors including Gwendolyn Mikell (1997); Cheryl de la Rey (2005) to reinforce this argument that women are still striving to overcome the societal notions of gender and gender-based roles. While conceptually leadership is genderless but the commonly associated leadership traits like task completion, problem-solving, decision making, confidence, power, and vision are often assumed to be found

primarily in males. A study by Whitehead (2013) initially gendered organisation design was followed i.e. on the basis of assuming what a specific gender is capable of doing, entire organisation design is framed. This led to categorisation of all policies and roles in an organisation and building up a glass ceiling on the abilities. Though this system was beneficial for the male but for women there have been several stereotypes developed. (Kay & Shipman, 2014) stated that although there exist various barriers in the path of women leadership, but individual factors, particularly that of confidence, is critical. It is believed that there is lack of confidence in women and hence they are not capable enough to work as an effective leader. Thus, jobs of management and leadership is not assigned. This makes men the natural and superior leader while women less than men. Further, O'Neil & Hopkins (2015) explained that this lack of confidence assumption act as a systematic disadvantage for women as they get less opportunity to work as a leader. This gendered organisation culture focus on traditional masculine model and hence decrease the confidence level of women, led to self-doubt and self-blame, and even sometimes women exit from the organisation. However, if they continue then only few opportunities are available for women to reach at top level and develop new skills. Thus, this continuous influence of social and cultural beliefs led to treatment of women as an inferior and hence restricting them to the jobs which doesn't involve much responsibilities, power, and decision making. This study will thus explore how individual factors affect success of female leadership in the FinTech start-up sector.

Hoyt (2010) also discussed the conventional division of labour in the society wherein women are supposed to perform domestic responsibilities and child-rearing. The study acknowledged that although the situation has improved and men are increasingly contributing in domestic chores but the gap is still significant which compels women to sacrifice their careers and subsequently results in widening the skill gap and thus the leadership gap.

García (2012) although has the same notion as Kiamba (2008) and Hoyt (2010) but presented it in an altogether novel manner by not being sympathetic towards women for their lower representation at workplaces but by putting forward the male perspective on the issue. Like most authors argue women's lower participation in the workforce can be highly attributed to the domestic caregiver roles that society typically assign to them, García (2012) argued that

since men are stereotyped to be the ones going outside the home to earn a living for the family, they are left with no option but to outsource the family responsibilities to the women. García (2012) in the study stated that society treats men as inauthentic caregivers and elaborates that while women often face discrimination at the workplace for not being fit to work, men also face discrimination when it comes to performing domestic roles. García (2012) declares that this discrimination is at the roots of gender-based stereotyping in society. The study, therefore, recommended that there is dire need of role reversal between males and females to promote gender diversity in the organisations.

Okafor et al. (2011) proclaimed about the patriarchal society in Lagos, Nigeria that males dominate every sphere of women's lives. Societal stereotypes assume women to be less confident, less competent, less emotionally consistent, less analytical and thus as inefficient leaders. They are primarily supposed to take care of the family and children and those who dare to violate these social assumptions are often labelled as being greedy or selfish.

While Okafor, Fagbemi, and Hassan, (2011) explained the Nigerian scenario, Klaile, (2013) discussed the underrepresentation of women in leadership positions in Finland. This study also agreed about the prevailing gender differences that have now established as social norms. Thus, females give more importance to families whereas males show a high preference for careers.

Lahti, (2013) encapsulated that societal factors are indirect and often uncontrollable factors that affect both individuals as well as organisational behaviour. There are strong stereotypes in the society which translate into specific gender-based roles and expectations. Additionally, the study also claims about the conventional division of education and labour market which is largely based upon the traditional gender roles. Society assumes particular education and jobs are masculine while others are more suitable for females. The study brings into light the differences in governmental reforms as well which are gender role-based signifying that while a male can return to his original position and salary after paternal leave in Finland, the women usually suffer a loss of a job or a compromise in salary after their maternity leave.

The discussion undertaken in this chapter thus defends the critical role of the society and culture in the women's career advancement. It is evident that socio-cultural, gender-based

stereotypes are still prevalent and impeding women advancement to the leadership positions. The next section highlights the case of an organisation.

2.4.2 Organisational factors

A working woman or a woman in leadership always have a boundary in which she can work. Though it is considered that, now boundary does not exist but still it prevails in the working environment. Despite having the capability of reaching a higher position, females are still working at the level below male. Women can choose to work and manage family but still, the salary gap exists between male and female employee. Apart from societal pressure, business culture also affects female leadership. Organisational culture deals with beliefs, values, and expectations of the organisation. These cultures can vary i.e. they can be feminine or masculine, high or low performing, and collectivistic or individualistic. It is often noted that still companies do prefer male employees due to their belief of male being the safe choice for the company. Females are considered as someone who creates disturbance in the entire organisational culture. Further, male employees do have an organisational value of cronyism i.e. supporting their co-workers. Organisation's due to lack of trust and belief on female workers doesn't utilise them efficiently hence leading to a lack of resources for the company. These gaps in human resources affect the potential of the organisation. As the organisational setting is sometimes focused on the masculine way of thinking, thus this sometimes led to a consideration of some specific factors only. Female leaders usually have broader perception and thus provide with the clear and big picture of scenarios possible in a situation. Even the leadership style followed by an employee brings changes in the contribution of that person in the organisation. Thus considering all this information derived from this paper (Lahti, 2013), the impact of organisational factors on the effective leadership of females would be crucial to study. Hence, focusing on the aspects derived from the base paper this study has further evaluated the factors that affect the successful female leadership.

Organisations can have a huge impact in promoting female leadership as the ultimate decision of hiring or not hiring a female leader rests with the organisation itself. Organisations and their

internal culture have a huge impact on career opportunities for women and organisations have the potential to create a positive environment to increase diversity and promote female leadership. Early research in the context of the organisational factors was conducted by Rosabeth Moss Kanter (1977) cited in Moran, (1992). Kanter in their research examined the organisational settings in which women perform and concluded that it is not their inherent gender traits that obstruct their way to leadership positions, but it is the distribution of opportunity and power in the organisation. The study claimed that women don't reach success because organisational policies are unfair.

In the context of organisational factors, Ilagan-Bian (2004) cited in Njiru, (2013) highlighted that women are often the victims of organisational biases. Sexual discrimination is common at workplaces which obstructs their career path. It is also mentioned that women usually have to work harder, be more educated and competent to get noticed and achieve the same organisational position as men. This is the reason that females often imitate their male counterparts at the workplace in the hope to achieve leadership positions. These stereotypes and prejudice harm women's career development. According to the responses received in the survey by Talouselämä, (2013), more than 70% of women responded that traditional gender roles and expectations of women slow the career path of women. It was also noted, however, that besides men, women themselves had certain perceptions in their mind which acted as a barrier to their career development. Similar reports made from the survey published by the Zahidi & Ibarra, (2013), implied that there was a lot of variation in the culture of different organisations and a patriarchal corporate culture was seen as the most important hurdle for women to be promoted to senior positions. This result was supported by the survey conducted by Talouselämä, (2013) on female leaders' perceptions on the same issues. The most common response received by women in senior management on being asked about the most significant obstacle in their career development was the prevalence of male-preferring business culture.

However, Okafor, Fagbemi and Hassan, (2011) also acknowledged the influence of organisational factors on lower women representation in leadership positions. They stated about gender-based horizontal (women often being hired in comparatively lower status and lower-paying organisational roles) and vertical segregation (women mostly occupy non-

strategic organisational positions) in the organisations due to which women are lesser seen as leaders. Okafor, Fagbemi and Hassan, (2011) also asserted that women generally do not get equal treatment as their male counterparts during promotion and mentoring, etc. in the workplace.

Wage discrimination is yet another significant organisational barrier that discourages women from the leadership positions as highlighted by Njiru, (2013). The study claimed that despite having the same competencies women are often positioned at low in the organisation and receive lesser compensation for the same job. The study underscored the matter of sexual discrimination as well which is a subject of concern for promoting women leadership. Additionally, like Ilagan-Bian (2004), this study also agreed to the organisational expectations which compel the women to adopt the leadership traits of men to be successful. Njiru, (2013) therefore established the need for culture in the organisations but at the same time, it was also acknowledged that it is complicated and would take time.

In the same year, Lahti, (2013) stated that the internal culture and policies of an organisation significantly affect the career progression of women in the organisation. The study conversed about the business culture that it is the expectations, values, and beliefs that the leader in the organisation holds which develops the culture of the organisation. In organisations where the culture is masculine, it is often hard for women to succeed. Male-dominated work cultures usually prefer to promote males to leadership positions. Lahti, (2013) however supported the case of gender diverse organisations based upon the argument that women can bring multiple benefits with them which are advantageous for organisations in the long-run. Mentoring is yet another organisational factor that determines women's success in the organisation as Lahti, (2013) claimed that organisations putting more inputs in mentoring and coaching often help women to achieve leadership positions.

Important research in the same year was conducted by Klaile (2013) who postulate the influence of organisational factors on women leadership. The study explicates the case based on the theory of statistical discrimination, considering two kinds of discrimination: the glass ceiling and sticky floor. While glass ceiling refers to the invisible barriers that impede women's way to corporate leadership despite being equally competent as men; sticky floor refers to a

situation wherein women are discriminated in terms of the wage hike. Glass ceiling brings in gender disadvantage for women at top-level management i.e. systematic disadvantage exists for women in the organisation regarding to authority, vertical mobility, low-status jobs, and low income. This prevents women from reaching a higher position whereas male co-workers are promoted at those jobs. Further, the sticky floor is the wage discrimination at the bottom level i.e. despite being employed at the same level, men and women do have different pay-scale. Female workers are not promoted and provided with adequate resources at the workplace, which becomes barriers in their career advancement path. Hence, glass ceiling and sticky floor are barriers faced by women which restrict them from availing wage equality, promotion, and hiring opportunities (Kee, 2005; Plotnick, 2017; Ragoobur & Pydayya, 2015).

The section lays down that organisational culture needs to be improved to promote more women to leadership positions. The next section takes into review the literature on individual factors affecting women leadership.

2.4.3 Individual factors

With the advent of globalisation, the implementation of effective leadership has become very essential. There are various factors which influence the effective leadership, however, the study by (Alabi & Alabi, 2014) suggests that compared to the organisational factors, personal, individual, and situational factors do have more influence. This leadership effectiveness is further categorised based on gender.

Primarily, female leadership effectiveness is judged based on perception. As established in the previous section, for women leaders, the glass ceiling exists which prevent them from reaching top-level jobs. The study of (E. Lahti, 2013) suggested women by questioning their abilities make their growth slower. Due to lack of confidence, they refrain from participating in leadership opportunities and thus there is a lesser number of female leaders globally. Due to pressure from traditional views, female underestimate themselves, their skills and competencies. However, female do have courage and determination which helps in working

efficiently. Thus, this study classifies personal factors as barriers as well as the opportunity for growth, and further analyses the factors which affect the effective leadership of female in FinTech start-ups.

One of the main individual factors affecting women leadership can be considered as the “glass ceiling”. It can be defined as a barrier faced by women in the business world mostly at the top of the hierarchy which prevents women from reaching the same positions as men (Cotter et al., 2001). Several individualistic factors impact women leadership across the world. One of the foremost is the Glass Ceiling. Glass ceiling is perhaps the most commonly used allegory in regards to women/racial minorities’ progression in terms of career growth. Since this study is focused on women leadership, the minority aspect is ignored henceforth.

Coined in the 1980s, glass ceiling hints towards the strong existence of man-made impediments to prevent women from climbing up the corporate ladder to senior-level positions. Schedlitzki and Edwards, (2017) define it as that invisible obstruction that hinders the women from reaching the leadership positions despite their competency. It has been seen that women have the potential and capability to be promoted to higher positions but they face many challenges instead of getting ahead straightforward like men (Tanhua, 2012). According to the survey by Talouselämä, (2013), the attitudes of women towards themselves were considered as the second most important obstacle to women being promoted to senior management levels. The respondents answered that it had been observed that women lacked self-confidence and determination. This belief was also supported by others as some people believe that women themselves do not want to be leaders and are not willing to work for it as much as men and therefore, it has been considered as being the reason for the dwindling number of female leaders.

However, it is ironical that even after persistent efforts to empower women through political petitioning, jurisdictional alterations and a globalised wave of feminism, the picture of women’s headway is still blurred (Barreto, Ryan, and Schmitt, 2009). This is evident from the fact that still there is an on-going juxtapose across the globe wherein some academicians and practitioners opine that the practice of glass ceiling is very much intact, while a segment upholds the view that the developed nations have finally broken the glass ceiling; there is

another segment who maintain that women are striving hard to demolish the glass ceiling (Purcell, MacArthur, & Samblanet, 2010). Moreover, lack of networking can be considered as a major barrier of female leadership. Networking can be defined as building relationships and knowing people and it's been proven to be an efficient catalyst for career development. Networking helps in gaining various benefits, such as information about new job opportunities, what is happening in the business world, etc. It can also widen one's influence, power, and recognition (Lussier & Achua, 2013). Networking is exceedingly vital for any leader and especially for women to get ahead in their career. Networking is often found lacking in women leaders which act as a barrier to their progress.

Although it is evident that glass ceiling persists in varying intensities across industries and geographies, it won't be wrong to deduce that women themselves are indirectly contributing to its presence because of socio-cultural beliefs and practices. This is substantiated by a few studies. Akpinar-Sposito (2012) based on a comparative study of French and Turkish middle-level women managers concluded that glass ceiling impacts women who believe in the existence of the phenomenon and see it as a potent barrier. Some women have proved their mettle beyond the implied ceiling but it is nominal in comparison with the male counterparts. The barriers that exist perennially are cultural patterns, categorisation and typecasts and employer policies and practices. While Akpinar-Sposito (2012) presented employment specific perspective, Johns (2013) presented a rather holistic perspective of barriers by categorising them into four prominent realms: societal, governmental, industry and organisational structure. Though all influence women's advancement, the prominent factor that results in a glass ceiling is the implied restriction a woman feels while disposing of her duties for work and family with equal fervency, particularly, that of motherhood. It is more of an individualistic struggle that women go through.

The scenario presented by Johns (2013) was of a developed nation, but similar conclusions are drawn by Bombuwela and Chamaru (2013) in the context of Sri Lankan private sector organisation. It was found that although glass ceiling persists, the most prominent are the individual factors like low self-confidence, emotional quotient and cultural factors like the

pressure of playing the conventional role of “homemaker” with utmost efficiency hinder women’s growth considerably.

Based on the above discussion, the impact of the glass ceiling can be easily comprehended through the diagrammatic representation. The figure 2-7 below shows multiple factors like an individual, family, organisational, and cultural which are often combined to cause glass ceiling effect. Glass ceiling along with the demographic and environmental factors determine women’s career development.

***Figure 2-7: Glass Ceiling as an influencing factor in women’s career development.
(Bomuwela and Chamaru (2013)).***

Glass ceiling can be broken by women who embrace the leadership of highest excellence. Since leadership cannot be practised in isolation, the aspect of socialisation and networking warrants a focused approach. Since the personal traits of an individual are highly impactful in this case, it is obvious that it is regarded as a key individualistic factor. It is a proven fact that networking is an inevitable aspect of success as a leader. This holds more relevance in the contemporary globally connected business landscape. Ibarra and Hunter (2007) have advised networking as

a stimulus for managers to emerge as leaders. Networking needs to be done on three levels: operational, personal and strategic. Operational networking enables smooth disposal of in-house obligations while personal networking catalyses personal development. Lastly, strategic networking is crucial for business and career advancement. From the perspective of learning, Deloitte (2011) exhibit networking as a crucial source for learning and sharing of knowledge and experiences across departments, industries, and topographies. Networking enables leaders to seek inspiration and advice from senior leaders and excel. Whilst the above two studies have an organisational or individualistic perspective of networking, Meehan, and Reinelt (2012) see networking as the potent source to build social capital, stimulate community involvement, fostering creativity and innovation and reengineering systems. These networking advantages are immune to gender biases but hold a greater implication for women leaders as they are subject to several biases as discussed in the preceding paragraphs. Ibarra, Ely, and Kolb (2013) posit that while men are more into socialising, women usually refrain from it as they perceive it to be forged or purposeful. Thus, they need to develop a proactive approach towards network building keeping the broader agendas in focus. Adding further, Patel (2013) view networking from the lenses of gender differences and present that women are more insecure about their networking strategy and many a time, women are considered to be assertive and self-promoting.

Contrariwise, Erçetin and Bisaso (2016) analysed the condition of women leaders in the prevalent intricate scenario of social media networking. Women leaders are perceived differently by people and many a time, there is a sense of hesitation by people in developing social contact with them. Thus, scholars advocate women to get involved in more networking to enhance their visibility not only within their organisations but in professional and social circles as well. However, this is not possible by bringing about change in women's behavioural characteristics, particularly, confidence levels. Across the world, women have been experiencing a particular set of challenges as far as taking up leadership roles is concerned. These include the dual burden of work and family, self-reliance and assurance and the inherent implications of generalised perceptions and stereotypes. The key problem linked with women's self-confidence is their own underestimated opinion about self-competence and also the ability to conveying their confidence across. This can be understood by a simple assertion that women

regard themselves at par with their male counterparts while men always assume themselves to be superior to females. Moreover, as the corporate world is still a male-dominated set-up, females, in general, are regarded as the submissive and less-abled employees (Patel, 2013). Reasoning out the low levels of self-confidence amongst most women, AAUW (2016) expressed that cultures and upbringing deeply influence the way men and women comprehend themselves. A sense of male superiority persists across most cultures across the world. Hence, men are more outgoing and socialise with buoyancy, aggression and self-promoted while women are nurtured to be docile and refrain from such characteristics.

Hence, to leverage the advantages of gender diversity in business, KPMG (2015) advice the need to empower women to accomplish greater professional milestones. For this, three focal areas are recognised. Firstly, encouraging women to be more open to socialisation and networking along with fostering leadership. Secondly, confidence needs to be built by epitomising leadership through real-life success stories and lastly, adopting women-centric corporate development programs.

2.4.4 Political factors

Women to a larger extent are progressing in almost every sphere of life. Political factors play a dominant role in determining the success of female as leaders within a set-up which can be political or business oriented (Eagly, 2007; O'neil et al., 2008). Eagly (2007) asserted that success of women as leaders have escalated over the years as more and more people have either started accepting women bosses or were not affected by a leader's gender as seen in the figure 2-8 below. Thus, political factors including the various provisions in the law which favour the women are vital to this paper. One of the most important policies is related to maternity leave of female employees.

Figure 2-8: Preferences for male or female boss in Gallup polls from 1953 through 2006 (Eagly, 2007)

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Figure 2-8 above shows Gallup polls from 1953 through 2006, it was conducted to show the preferences for male or female boss. The study confirmed that the overall society experiences male dominance which makes it difficult for women to succeed. It can be outlined that there is the presence of partiality within the society thereby indicating the absence of decent governance. This was found to be true especially in the USA. Corresponding to this finding by Eagly (2007), O'neil et al. (2008) indicated the presence of two major political factors that had a strong influence on the success of women leadership. These factors were access and entry. As per O'neil et al. (2008) access has been a major concern as for women it was found that having entry to informal networks within an organisation was more challenging than it was for men. The network was found to be important as it played a strong role in impacting systems and power within the organisation hence determining the success of leaders and their leadership skills. Such inaccessibility of women restricted them from being successful leaders in the organisation. Like Eagly (2007), even for O'neil et al. (2008), entry issues were largely

faced by women in organisations. Partiality practices affecting women range from lower remunerations to fewer prospective of taking up stimulating and prominent projects. This gives women lesser opportunities for displaying their leadership skills and thus be successful.

The laws of most of the countries state that women must be entitled to return to their old position with the same responsibilities after returning from the maternity leave; however, usually, this does not happen. Losing one's job or receiving lesser remuneration are some of the risks faced by mothers returning to work after maternity leave (The UKkonen 2013). Maternity leave usually is an unnecessary break in women's careers and abate their place in the employment market and slow down the pace of their career development.

As per reports by Pande and Ford (2011) based on research conducted for the World Bank, women have been progressing relentlessly towards development and thus minimising the gap that is prevalent between the genders that are male and female. The progress is evident from the fact that from a complete non-participation till the late 19th century, today women have started playing an active role by the late 20th century. Irrespective of a holistic development within the society, Pande and Ford (2011) notified that women have not been able to take up leadership position not only in the political arena but also in areas of business. One of the reasons identified in this report has been the lack of policy supporting women empowerment thus motivating them to take up leadership positions.

The study progressed identifying that the male counterparts have been dominating and thus without the presence of appropriate policies like gender quota to support women leadership their participation would be to a larger extent get restricted. However, this was contradicted by Beaman et al. (2009) who in their research study found that such quotas resulted in the development of a negative mindset amongst male counterparts towards female leadership. In simple words, a forced leadership by females through such a mechanism was not accepted by males. This stems out from the social norm where the male is considered to be powerful and leadership is considered as a macho act. These males thus created issues while female leaders were pursuing their jobs thereby triggering their chances of failure.

Adding to the findings by Beaman et al. (2009), AAUW (2016) in their analysis of varied blockades and biases affecting women in leadership positions, notified that stereotyping to a greater extent influenced the perception of people thereby affecting acceptance of women leadership. This finding was made particularly in the context of the leadership of women in politics where they were perceived to be either mannish or lesbians by the voters and thus dejected to become a leader. The study also focused on the negative role played by media in the same and thus considered them integral in negatively affecting their success as leaders. This is evident from the issues on sexual orientation faced by Hillary Clinton and later been tagged as a lesbian media (Worthen, 2014; AAUW, 2016a). The outcome was her failure in presidential elections against Donald Trump in the United States in the year 2017 (Thiessen, 2017).

Figure 2-9: Women in the U.S.A. - Elected in Offices, by Race/Ethnicity, 2016 (AAUW (2016)).

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Figure 2-9 above shows women in the U.S.A, who were elected in different offices of power. It is evident from the numbers in the figure that higher the rank of the office, less are the chances of women to be elected.

Another perspective that focuses on factors hindering the success of women leaders is the lack of appropriate policies to support their education. This inability of the policy framework in Ethiopia and other developing nations thus prevents women from gaining requisite leadership skills as denoted by Hora (2014). Hora (2014) in their study accepted the presence of social and cultural factors that hinder women's inclusion in decision making thus prohibiting the cultivation of leadership skills in them. It was also brought to light that even privileges to access and use resources for women are restricted. The ability of women to perform leadership tasks is also questioned mainly as they are thought to be docile, obedient, enduring, and lenient towards work as well as lacking assertiveness. The study concluded that owing to the presence of such perception within the society the political mechanism and policy framework fails to provide the right platform to women to educate themselves and nurture their leadership skills. The outcome is a denial of appropriate rights to women which acts as an example of unskilled governance. Furthermore, another important policy that the government can introduce is the fixing of quotas to ensure a certain number of positions for women, especially in political parties or organisations (Piha, 2006). While fixing quotas for women, the government needs to specify the number of women that the companies need to employ in their management teams.

Based on the above discussions it is noticeable that there is a multiplicity of political factors that have direct implications on the success of female leaders. The same has been depicted in the figure 2-10 below.

Figure 2-10: Political Factors affecting Female Leadership (Researcher).

Based on the above research a mixed picture of political factors affecting female leadership success can be developed. These factors have implications for women leadership irrespective of the same being exhibited in the business or political scenario. The overall ratio of women leadership success though has changed over the years for which positive approach from political perspective has been responsible to a considerable extent (Eagly, 2007; O’neil et al., 2008; Pande and Ford, 2011).

Although the above studies have identified various political factors which influence the effectiveness of leadership, (OECD, 2017) states worldwide, governments are striving for gender equality. Purpose of government policies is to have balance among the distribution of gender in an organisation to work towards inclusive growth. The focus is to have equal access to all economic and public opportunities to both male and female to avoid loss of economy due to inappropriate usage of human capital. All institutions of government follow the mechanism

of implementing those policies, services, programmes, and budgets, which would benefit both genders. For this OECD has even given recommendations to close gender gaps in leadership and all public employment. Thus, political factors are not usually any gender-specific. They are generalised for reducing gender inequality and reducing the gap between the opportunities available to each gender. Hence, based on this study by OECD, political factors were not considered as one of the factors affecting female leadership in this research.

2.4.5 Technology and physical infrastructure factors

With globalisation and technological advancement companies from across the world have also undergone massive changes in their organisational culture. One such change has been the acceptance of women and their leadership across varied organisational levels. These advancements and changes have bestowed women with prospects to exhibit their leadership skills (Colwill & Townsend, 1999; Dahlvig & Longman, 2010). As per this, it is so because such changes result in the amalgamation of varied cultures for which unique leadership styles are required rather than unified ones. Thus, the chances of women taking up leadership positions have increased.

Ryan and Haslam (2007) though accepted that women leadership has progressed over the years but yet they confirmed the presence of a glass cliff for this gender segment within the society in their study. Following the research by them, it has been brought to light that women have lesser access to the inheritance of the infrastructural support system which men have especially within organisations. It has been seen that there are certain sectors like technology and physical infrastructure amongst others that are still characteristically prejudiced by gender and the reforms related to women have been slow. Furthermore, the lack of availability of infrastructure prohibits them from being effective leaders.

Along with infrastructure the backing networking system also fails to provide women with requisite support thus demotivating them to take up leadership roles. These findings were also accepted by Foust-Cummings et al. (2008) in their research study on companies within the

high technology industry-sponsored by IBM. The study concluded that these industries were primarily male-dominated which made female uncomfortable. Further within technology-oriented companies, it was found that women were more disappointed and dissatisfied with their technical jobs which thereby restricted them to take up leadership roles. The study, however, accepted a change within the technology industry with the widespread emergence of information technology as well as a change in organisational culture and orientation towards female employees. The change has motivated companies to recruit and select employees based on quality and qualification rather than being gender-biased as asserted by Foust-Cummings et al. (2008). This was similar to the findings by Jepson (2010) who made a comparative analysis of women leaders within engineering and those in other streams as seen in the figure below, which shows the percentage of men and women employed in high-tech operations that requires engineering of different categories.

Figure 2-11: Percentage of Men and Women Employed in High-Tech Operations -2008
(Jepson (2010))

The above figure 2-11 depicts the state of women in the high technology industry and justifies the supremacy of their male counterparts. Roomi and Parrott (2008) in a study on women entrepreneurship in Pakistan presented that with male dominance in this nation women were

forced to take a backseat. Women were not provided with appropriate facilities and did not have proper access to infrastructural facilities, business foundation and resources like land and capital. Women were also abstained from gaining expertise in information technology and thus in many cases forbidden to use the same. They also lacked proper training and assistance to nurture their technology-related skills or to use infrastructure optimally. This acted as a hindrance to the success of female leadership.

Bullough (2008) believed that in circumstances where women have been brilliant with technological support, they tend to become effective leaders in the form of entrepreneurs. This is in line with the findings by Roomi and Parrott (2008) who concluded that by removal of barriers and exposure of women to information technology they might emerge as successful leaders. The research by Bullough (2008) further highlighted that technology supports women to take up their business ventures and thus smoothly start and continue as entrepreneurs thus enhancing their productivity. This was considered as a global problem evident both in developing and developed nations which is evident in a research study by Roomi et al. (2009) in the subsequent year. Roomi et al. (2009) in their study on women leadership in a developed nation like England drew similar conclusions as to the study by Roomi and Parrott (2008) concerning Pakistan.

Highlighting the significance of information technology in a business Alam et al. (2011) notified that deployment of such technology is critical in modern-day business. The study further stated that women leaders with the help of information technology can trigger innovation within a business. These innovations would result in the development of business models on the premise of lower costs thus benefitting them to derive higher revenues from each customer. It has been seen that women stand out in the field of social welfare and health, whereas men tend to excel in fields of technology and transport. This division in the sector reflects the existence of gender discrimination in the labour market of various sectors and deepens inequality and differences in salaries between genders. Through such technologies, the direct and personal interaction between men and women has been curtailed thus limiting the discrimination faced by the later in the entire process. Within the cyberspace, gender factors like other demographic aspects of act and background become less effective. A further

amalgamation of physical infrastructure with technology in the form of computerisation and automation of offices has made it possible for women to handle higher workloads thereby enhancing their overall efficiency. Women are in a position today to balance their work and life thus enhancing the overall work-life quality which has motivated them to participate more actively and thus is successful.

In a recent study on leadership in India by Kumar (2015), it has been denoted that with the emergence of mobile applications as a part of advancement in information technology, women leadership has to leap forward towards development. This is similar to the findings by Alam et al. (2011). This technology as per Kumar (2015) has been a boon to women irrespective of their social and economic class thus empowering them. As per this study, technology has been considered to be of great advantage to female leaders within rural areas by providing them with a platform to interact and do business by gaining basic skills and qualification.

The above discussion highlights that along with societal issues women leadership success was restricted due to a lack of access to technology. With the development of opportunities within the technological sphere and its merger with physical infrastructure, women today are gaining capabilities of becoming effective leaders. Above studies have focused on the factors which influence the effective leadership and even discriminate the contribution of technological factors on gender basis. Thus, science, technology, and innovation are equally accessible to females and males today (H. Lee & Pollitzer, 2016), Gendered Innovation refers to the process of harnessing the power of gender and sex analysis for facilitating discoveries and innovation. This process identifies the nepotism in various opportunities based on gender and further helps in preventing them. Better access to STEM education and technology at work is enabling females to perform better at the workplace, hence technological factors have been considered for further analysis in this study.

2.5 Empirical Review

The empirical review presents various studies that included quantifiable data to investigate the importance of female leaders in the performance of an organisation. A study by Bodla & Hussain, (2009) attempted to bridge the gap in previous studies that have depicted the masculine and feminine leadership practices. This paper observed the followers' needs and preferences pertaining to leadership in American and European contexts during the last couple of decades. It also and examined the subject area for the behavioural scientists in Pakistan. Therefore, this study aims to explore the difference in opinions of both male and female subordinates regarding the different leadership styles. Also, it aims to determine the extent of the difference between male and female employees in their need for leadership in the banking sector of Pakistan. Consequently, the impact of the study for researchers has also been offered in this study. Therefore, it has been suggested that as female employees are increasing at the workplace, researchers ought to uncover multi ratings from different sources in future studies to increase the importance of their studies.

However, in another similar study by Wellalage & Locke, (2011) reviewed the relationship between the female board of directors and the financial performance of the companies in Sri Lanka. The main research objective of this paper was to investigate the impact of gender diversity in a company on its financial performance. To meet this objective, a dynamic panel generalised method of moment estimation was used. There were three variables used to measure gender diversity, namely the percentage of women on the board, a dichotomous dummy and the Blau index. Secondary data was collected after which a Tobit model was used along with regression analysis to investigate the impact of female board members on its growth opportunities. The results of this study showed that a significant negative relationship existed between the proportion of women on boards and firm value along with an increase in agency cost of the company. This result shall prove useful for the result in the current study to offer a recommendation that will help enhance women's leadership skills.

A study by Bullough (2008) focused on determining the global factors which affect the participation of women in leadership. A multi-level study consisting of cross-cultural data of both individual-level and macro-society was derived. The data is collected for 300 variables

consisting of political and business leadership from 213 countries from 10 different sources for period 2002-2007. Cluster and discriminant analysis was done for 7 different hypotheses which were framed to test the relationship between women in leadership and factors affecting it. The analysis results depict that the factors affecting women participation vary with the current level of participation of women in the leadership. Hence, each country should focus on the factors that significantly affect women participation. These results show that factors are there which affect women leadership and even contribution of each factor do vary with country.

Okafor, Fagbemi, & Hassan, (2011) on the other hand, investigated the barriers faced by women managers in the organisations in private as well as the public sector, which prevents women from being promoted to the topmost level of their professional career. To meet the research objectives, a sample of three hundred and ninety-seven (397) women managers including managers from all the major sectors of the Nigerian economy including manufacturing, banking, insurance, and the public service sub-sector was selected. Also, an additional sample of 50 male top managers working in public and government companies in Nigeria were selected to get a response from questionnaires as well as oral interviews to measure their perceptions regarding the barriers faced by women managers in their respective companies. The responses showed that a significant relationship existed between the gender stereotype of a woman manager and her career goals. It was also seen that women managers had all the qualities required to be a part of top management, yet the major factor which acted as a barrier for them included individual factors (gender-imposed) as well as organisational factors within their context of the operation. This study also provided recommendations regarding the removal of the barriers including the promotion of gender-sensitivity policies in the company, introduction of leadership training and development for women, promotion of education for women and their mentoring, among others. Also, skill development programs which mainly targeted women were recommended to produce efficient women leaders.

On the contrary, Schuh et al., (2014) tried to derive certain theoretical approaches in order to determine whether there was any difference between women and men on the basis of their levels of power motivation and whether potential gender differences in this motivation contributed to the unequal distribution of women and men in leadership positions. The results

of this study complemented by four previous studies showed that women consistently reported lower power motivation than men which, in turn, mediated the connection between gender and leadership role occupancy. The research methodology employed to meet the research objectives of this study included obtaining data from different samples (i.e., student samples and large heterogeneous samples of the employee), diverse operationalisations of power motivation and leadership role occupancy (self- and other ratings), and study design (cross-sectional and time-lagged designs). This study also discussed the implications of theory and practice as well as the different ways in which more equal gender distribution in leadership positions in companies could be achieved.

Paustuan-Underdahl, Walker, & Woehr, (2014) undertook a meta-analysis to address the debate of female leadership by quantitatively analysing gender differences in perceptions of leadership effectiveness across 99 independent samples from 95 studies. Meta-analysis is the procedure of examining multiple studies to determine the common effect that was seen in those studies and if not then determine the reason for variation in the effect. Thus in this study meta-analysis would provide information about the perception of people on the male and female leadership effectiveness. The results of data analysis showed there were no major differences in the perceived effectiveness of the leadership of men and women considering all leadership contexts. However, when other ratings were observed, it was found that women were rated as significantly more effective as compared to men. Disappointedly, on examination of self-ratings, it was found that men rated themselves as significantly more effective than women rated them. Furthermore, this combination also examined the control of contextual moderators which was developed from the role congruity theory. The findings of this study aided in extending role congruity theory by indicating how it can be supplemented with other theories in the literature, including the application of the theory to both men and women leaders. The objectives of this research were to expand upon and update a meta-analysis conducted earlier, which integrated relevant research conducted in the United States until 1989. Randomised controlled trial (RCT) was then completed by applying it to both male and female leaders, and by investigating the application of other theories in supplementing the different aspects of RCT. Also, an important point of debate raised in the academic discussion of gender

advantages in leadership effectiveness had been examined in this study, namely, the importance of examining self-reported and other-reported leadership effectiveness.

Towards reviewing the profile of effective female leadership, a study was done by Girdauskiene & Eyvazzade (2015). Due to globalisation, more focus is on teamwork and demographic changes in the workforce. This led to an increase in the relevance of managing a diverse workforce. As female leaders can be differentiated based on flexibility, empathy, their role in the business process, thus the analysis was done to determine the nature of female leader in the multicultural company. This analysis is based on the perception of 6 managers of Lithuania who have experience of 10-20 years. The analysis has shown that to be an effective leader female should be protector, professional, result-oriented nature, and should show care. This helps in differentiating the behaviour and ability of each individual thus depicting the effectiveness of female leadership. Similar to Schuh et al., (2014), Cook & Glass, (2014) tested three institutional-level theories that helped in shaping women's access to and tenure in top positions including the glass cliff, decision-maker diversity and the saviour effect. It was observed that women remained less in number in top leadership positions in various companies which also reflected a plethora of barriers that created a glass ceiling effect. However, it was seen that a few women did attain top leadership positions, which led scholars to probe the conditions under which those women were promoted despite the existence of various organisational, personal and societal barriers.

Previous scholarship tended to conceive individual-level explanations, suggesting either those women who attained top leadership positions were exceptional or that potential women leaders lacked key qualities, such as assertiveness. To test these theories, a dataset was created which included all CEO transitions in Fortune 500 companies over 20 years and analysed. Contrary to the predictions of the glass cliff, it was found that diversity among decision-makers and not the performance of the companies significantly increased the probability of women being promoted to top leadership positions. It was also found, contrary to the predictions of the saviour effect, that diversity among decision-makers increases women leaders' tenure as CEOs regardless of firm performance. This study made an important contribution to the processes

that shape and reproduce gender inequality in work organisations by identifying contextual factors that increase women's mobility.

A study by (Gipson, Pfaff, Mendelsohn, Catenacci, & Burke, 2017) suggest that despite studying leadership for the last 75 years, there are many things must be explored empirically. These studies attempt to differentiate leadership based on the gender which is affected by discrimination or stereotyping. Thus, via the framework of development, selection, performance, and leadership style, women's leadership effectiveness is analysed. The analysis reaffirms the presence of the glass ceiling effect. Though women are acquiring elite leadership positions, men have greater access to senior management level, and fewer development opportunities are available for women. Hence, this study depicts that women do face various challenges which prevent them from rising to top-level management.

Furthermore, Neck, (2015) tried to understand the factors that led women to leave senior roles in the finance department. To meet the research objective, a survey of 90 women was conducted which suggested that women quit due to the interplay of a cause for leaving, coupled with having a more lucrative choice. The factors included work frustrations as well as other personal triggers. It was found that though these triggers led women to want to leave yet having the ability to leave seemed to be as important as actually leaving. The quantitative analysis supported the findings of a qualitative study which suggested that the way work was structured in the industry, sought change and having choice were the main factors in a woman's decision to leave. It was also found that senior women in finance had many options outside their job which probably led women to leave senior roles simply because they could.

Okafor, Fagbemi, & Hassan (2011b) in their study focused on analysing the barriers which women managers have to face while moving to top-level management jobs in public and private organisations. Data for the empirical analysis is derived from 397 female managers of Nigeria and 50 male top-level managers of the public and private organisation via interviewees and questionnaire regarding the perception of people on the barriers faced by women managers. The analysis reveals that there exists a significant relationship between stereotypes (social factors_ and career aspirations of women. Despite having all the required capabilities and skills, females are not able to attain the top-level management jobs due to individual,

family, and organisational barriers. To create the opportunity of growth for women leaders it is required to have the availability of training and development programmes for women, mentoring, gender-sensitivity, and creation of more educational facilities for women and the girl child. This would help in enhancing the skills of women and thus creating a way towards successful female leadership. Similarly, Glass, Cook, & Ingersoll, (2015) investigated the impact of women leaders on the corporate environmental strategies of companies. To meet this objective, a dataset of all Fortune 500 CEOs and boards of directors for ten years were created to examine several aspects of gender in leadership on environmental strategy. Particularly, the impact of women CEOs was measured using the percentage of women on the BOD, the number of interlinks women board members held, and the interactive and collective impacts of women CEOs and gender-diverse boards. The findings of the research showed that companies with gender-diverse leadership teams were more effective than other companies in pursuing environmentally friendly strategies. This study contributes to research on corporate governance and environmental performance by showing how the gender composition of leaders affects corporate practice.

In a more recent study, Qian, (2016) examined the impact of gender diversity in corporate boardrooms in Asia and the Pacific on the financial and non-financial performance of those companies. It was found that boardroom gender diversity was low in Asia with 7.5% female leaders in 2012 but showed a 1.8% improvement in 2013. The appointment of female directors and a gender-diverse boardroom were found to be positively related to the performance of companies with huge cross-country and cross-measurement differences. It was found that the performance of companies was the highest when there were two females on the board.

Two-stage analyses were performed to meet the research objective and it was found that (i) a firm's past performance did not estimate its choice to add female directors; (ii) cross-country differences in female corporate leadership responded to its economic demand and supply which was measured by gender equality in college education, labour participation, wages, and infant survival; and (iii) female representation on the board, when determined by these economic factors, were significant forecasters of a firm's future value.

Further studies by DiCaprio, Yao, & Simms, (2017) sought to identify the barriers faced by women in starting and running a business. The main research objective of this paper was to intensify and modify this finding by using a unique data set to investigate the patterns of financial resource available for export firms owned by women. It was seen that two levels of exclusion were faced by women including access to basic finance and access to trade finance. Moreover, in line with existing work, it was shown that firms owned by women tended to turn to informal finance to meet their financial needs more as compared to their male counterparts. However, it was also shown that women were more likely to adopt FinTech start-ups as a financial solution as compared to men which led to the conclusion that policies aimed at incentivising banks to lend more to women might not be the correct solution to mitigate this issue.

However, correspondingly, Sahay et al., (2017) tried to measure the gap between the representation of men and women in leadership positions in banks and bank supervision agencies globally. To meet the research objective, z-scores and nonperforming loan ratios were examined. It was found using the dataset that less than 2% of bank CEOs were, and the board seats had less than 20% of women in more than 80% of the data sets across banks over time. As opposed to general perceptions, it was discovered that a majority of the low- and middle-income countries had a greater percentage of women in bank boards and banking supervision agency boards as compared to that in advanced economies.

The econometric analysis was done to control for pertinent bank and other factors specific to each country which showed that the bank which had a higher share of women on their boards exhibited greater bank stability as compared to their counterparts. A new dataset was compiled to examine the share of women on boards of banking supervision agencies which confirmed the results of the previous analysis. According to this study, further research would be required to recognise the mechanisms mandatory to achieve these stability benefits, along with understanding the positive policies for the inclusion of women in senior management roles in banks and supervision agencies. Thus, all the empirical studies stand under one roof and have a notion that, globally organisations have been more successful with high gender diversity amongst its employees and female leadership.

2.6 Research Gap

It has always been assumed that organisational structures are usually gender-neutral, and this supposition hides the power tussle between genders (Walker and Woehr, 2014). Theoretically, companies should employ committed workers who work for the advancement of organisational goals. However, to date, the image of the “ideal worker” is usually a man who is completely committed to his work, prioritising work over his personal needs and health (Reid, 2015). This image of the ideal worker leads to the marginalisation of women as explained by Reid, (2015). Similarly, previous literature on leadership has been dominated by characterising the ideal leader as a person who works within a defined work culture and is, ideally, male. Women leaders feel out of place, yet there is plenty of literature written on this topic in the media (Stead & Elliott, 2009). Still, there is a lack of critical work which focuses on women’s leadership to facilitate a better understanding of the experiences of women. Therefore, this study was conducted to identify the factors responsible for creating successful leadership among women leaders in the UK’s FinTech start-up sector. It discusses the various leadership theories related to women and identifies the various obstacles faced by women leaders and provides recommendations regarding increasing the acceptance of women in senior management roles. As such, the findings of this research are designed to close the gap between the existing knowledge base and literature by adopting a holistic approach towards the research problem.

2.7 Conclusion

This chapter provides the view of the existing literature relating to the women leadership in the context of the UK’s FinTech start-up sector. The first section of the chapter highlights the concept of leadership wherein the previous studies indicated that leadership is referred to as the influence that leaders exert upon the subordinates. Some of the studies defined leadership as a complex and time-consuming concept. The components of leadership were linked to three broad areas including the leader, situation and the followers wherein the leaders and the

managers performed the same roles. In modern times, leadership is considered as the part of social development as any form of function that explains in a manner in which the leader works for the organisation.

Following this, the next chapter links the concept of leadership with the gender that focused upon the different leadership patterns adopted by males and females. Men are considering being more autocratic and directive style leadership. On the other hand, gender differences in context to different leadership styles are vague and the style of leadership may vary. Subsequently, the next section highlighted the present state of women leadership. Some of the researchers pointed out that the advancement of women in the corporate world is not up to the mark as most of them get stuck at the middle level of management. The studies that focused upon the leadership of women in the UK stated that the hidden potential of the women has not been explored. Further, the chapter explores the importance of women leadership for better performance of the company. Some of the studies stated that women are more creative and bring a change to the organisation. Lastly, the researcher explored the factors that affect the successful female leadership including the societal – cultural factors, organisational factors, individual factors and political factors that affect the female leadership.

Chapter: 3 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.0 Introduction to the chapter

The previous chapter reviewed the available literature on the subject while this chapter aims to establish the conceptual framework or the theoretical framework of the study. The conceptual framework has been explained by Miles and Huberman (1994) cited in (Yamauchi, Ponte, Ratliffe, & Traynor, 2017) as the visual or printed description of the prominent points to be considered in a study including the definitions or concepts, the main variables and factors, as well as the assumptions about relationships between such variables. The conceptual framework is an integral part of the research because it determines the scope and quality of the research. Whilst it provides an overall structure to the research, conceptual framework aids the researcher to sort out between the relevant and irrelevant data and guides the conduct of the research by offering a systematic view of the research problem (Yamauchi et al., 2017).

Figure 3-1 below shows the conceptual framework for this study. The women leadership in FinTech start-up organisations are affected by four main factors. They are societal, organisational, individual and technological factors. In the context of this paper, the Gender-Based Role Congruence theory is chosen. Ultimately, women leadership is discussed by comparing it with the organisational performance, leading to the successful women leadership in the UK's FinTech start-up sector.

Figure 3-1: Conceptual Framework (Researcher)

3.1 Conceptual Framework

3.1.1 Explanation of the model

In the previous chapter, the researcher identified that there are many organisational, individual, technological and socio-cultural factors which affect the effectiveness of the leadership. There exist male-dominated industries and thus all these factors have more impact on female leadership. A study by Arnold, (2017) state that as females don't have technical skills as the

male employees have, hence technologies and innovations are mostly male-dominated. Based on all these factors, role and responsibilities of gender are defined. This led to considering female leader roles incongruent with their abilities. Hence, beliefs, values, attitude, and stereotypes serve as the base in categorising job roles among both genders (C. L. Hoyt & Burnette, 2013). Female leadership effectiveness is thus impacted by this role assignment and gender inequality which in turn contribute to affecting organisational performance (Qian, 2016). Further, studies (Archer, 2016; Deloitte, 2015; Qian 2016b) too suggest that effectiveness of women leadership and gender diversity affect the organisation performance as return on equity, return on investments, and return on assets are increased by having more women participation in the leadership jobs. Hence, the UK FinTech start-up sector create more opportunities to have gender disparity and encouragement of female leadership to have an improvement in performance. This would also help in the successful working of the new initiative in FinTech start-up sector thus leading towards further growth of the organisations (Ernst and Young, 2014). Hence, the model specified in Figure 3-1. completely define factors which help in having successful leadership of women leaders in FinTech start-up sector.

3.1.2 Women Leadership in the UK's FinTech start-up sector.

Workplace diversity is imperative for enticing and retaining the competent workforce along with enabling a better understanding of the customer perspective. However, this is seldom followed in real terms. On the contrary, Canada presents a better picture with nearly over 20% female representation at the top-level managerial positions of the financial institutions. This indicates the related efforts made by the industry to combat the gender inequality which prevails in the society to a significant level. There are several factors responsible for it. The political support by the government in the form of social policies like the Employment Equity Act of 1986, subsidised education, tax-funded healthcare, 12 months long maternity and paternity leave. Adding to this is the open immigration policies that add to ethnic diversity. This has compelled the country to consider various women-oriented issues and run programs like “Return to Bay Street” to encourage women to come back to their professions after taking

a break due to personal or other reasons acknowledging the efforts and accomplishment of women through awards and adulations. Also, some organisation run exclusive programs to fostering leadership amongst women to assist them to advance in their careers. Hence, it calls for cumulative efforts by cultural, governmental, industry and organisations to promote women to the professional pinnacle. Along with this, women also need support from their families in doing so (Mcintyre and Quest, 2014).

However, this is an exceptional scenario whereas, on common parlance, it is an undeniable fact that the senior-level leadership roles in both financial and technology-centric companies or the latest FinTech start-up organisations are dominated by the males and this sector experiences major gender diversity. According to the World Bank report published in 2012, “Gender Equality and Development”, stated that despite the rapid progression of the world, women are yet to remove the glass-ceiling of being homemakers with children, and family needs being top of their agendas. This socio-cultural mindset has hampered the FinTech start-up sector for a long time (Maule and Gallagher, 2015). Substantiating this further based on the study of the Chinese FinTech start-up sector, Grass-Oguma & George (2016) asserted that although the Chinese economy has witnessed unprecedented improvement, the conventional family structures are still the unperturbed aspect of the Chinese society. Despite educated women being allowed to take up employment, their top-priority remains their roles of a wife or a mother. Usually, women become mothers at a professional juncture where they could climb the organisational hierarchy to the middle or senior levels. But motherhood compels them to take a career break or quit it completely. This explains the low number of women in senior positions at Chinese financial organisations.

In 2016, only 8% of the ExCo positions were occupied by women in China as against 21% in North America and 16% in European nations. However, with changing mindset organisations felt the need for promoting gender diversity at work. The FinTech start-up organisations are warranting a demand for knowledgeable and skilled staff that possess the imperative technical, financial, operational and service competencies, particularly for the middle and senior-level positions. Hence, this may be a possibility that FinTech start-up companies start ignoring the gender aspect and family commitments of women, provided they have the desired skills and

experience (GRASS-OGUMA and GEORGE, 2016). Adding to this, Arnold (2017) stated that although the latest cohort of financial technology companies is geared up to surpass the traditional banks they are unable to do so in one domain, women on higher leadership roles. Reportedly, only 8% of the FinTech start-up directors are women against the figure of 22% at the world's thirty largest banks. It is ironical when FinTech start-up is believed to be the breakthrough in conventional banking and financial services, gender inequality is such deeply rooted in the industry (Arnold, 2017). The impact of gender inequality is multi-facet. It not only promotes group-think, herd behaviour, and excessive risk-taking but also inches the organisation towards a grave crisis based on cultural and organisational characteristics.

The industry cannot be expected to change rapidly in this regard. The mere cost-cutting advantage is not sufficient to adopt more women or gender equality favouring policies. It is persistent that women are susceptible to layoffs while most men are seen to execute such acts. Another aspect highlighted is an individual factor of career choices, wherein it is observed that since women play down in the domains of science, engineering, and technology, establishing a long-lasting and rewarding career in the FinTech start-ups is too much to ask for (Wójcik and Cojoianu, 2017).

The meticulous review of the literature undertaken in the previous chapter establishes that there certainly are impediments in the way of women career advancement to leadership positions in an organisational context. The same is considered to be the fact for the UK's FinTech start-ups sector in this research. The review of the literature provided that socio-cultural, organisational, individual, political, physical and infrastructural factors, all have a bearing on the women participation in the workforce.

- 1. Socio-cultural factors:** From times immemorial, the gender-based roles are prevalent in the society which establishes different behavioural expectations for both men and women. While men have conventionally been associated with the roles of breadwinner, the women are expected to take care of the family and do household chores. Such mindset also leads to the assumption that men and women possess different skills and aptitude and accordingly their societal roles should be decided (Eagly, Wood and Diekmann, 2007). Moreover, many countries of the world still

follow a typical patriarchal society where women have comparatively lower status than men. The women in such societies are subjugated and often compelled to act as the subordinate to men. This has somehow acted as a prominent factor in impeding the growth of women to leadership positions in the past and it continues to do so (ABOLADE, 2014). On account of such socio-cultural factors, this has been included in the conceptual framework of the current study.

- 2. Organisational factors:** Organisational factors are also found to exert influence on the status of the women leadership in the corporate world. Organisations too are influenced by the conventional gender stereotyping which is found evident in the way different organisational roles are assigned to men and women. It is however proven by the past researches alike that women and men are biologically different thus possess different inherent skills and that organisational roles should be gender congruent. The exhaustive review of the literature also offered that organisations expect women to be more educated, smart, and competent to get noticed and achieve an equal footing with men in the workplace. The organisations typically assign women lower hierarchical positions and non-strategic job profiles (Okafor, Fagbemi and Hassan 2011); (Njiru, 2013).
- 3. Individual factors:** Although external factors do impede women growth to leadership positions, the inherent characteristics of women also obstruct their growth. Women have been found to have lower levels of self-confidence and zeal to reach to the top positions in an organisational context (Talouselämä, 2013). Glass ceiling is yet another significant individualistic barrier in the way of women leadership which is prevalent since eternally. Additionally, a lack of networking also has been found to discourage women leadership because referral hiring is often an important recruitment strategy in the corporate world (Cotter, Hersem, Ovadia, & Vanneman, 2001).
- 4. Technology and physical infrastructure factors:** The level of technology and infrastructure also influence the way women progress to leadership positions. The literature offered that the advancement and exposure of women to technology can help them in their career progression. It aids to improve their productivity by

enhancing their skills and competencies (A. Bullough, 2008); (Roomi & Parrott, 2008). However, it has been unfortunate that till date the women do not get equal technological and infrastructural support as their male counterparts. This is often the reason that male dominance is still prevalent in the technology-oriented industries (Foust-Cummings, Sabattini, & Carter, 2008).

The literature suggests that the participation of women in the workforce has an impact on organisational performance. Though there are mixed references of whether more women in the FinTech start-up sector have positive or negative organisational outcomes, the organisational performance can be assumed as one of the parameters of successful women leaders in the UK's FinTech start-up sector.

The UK's FinTech start-up sector is growing globally and creating the opportunity of growth and development of the economy through innovation, and job creation. However, to manage it, there is the requirement of gender diversity in the organisations to have proper utilisation of the talent and skills of employees (Ernst and Young, 2014). However, a report by Chinwala, (2016) state that though 23% of board directors are women only 14% of the executive committee member is female. As top positions like CEO, CFO, Head of a region, CIO, Deputy CEO, or Executive chair, are more concentrated on revenue generation and women as per beliefs does not possess these skill sets, hence mostly the employment of women are in support roles like communication, HR, compliance,, marketing, or strategy. Even the report suggests that for having women in executive committee there is a requirement of creating high profile support roles. Further, a study by Arnold, (2017) suggest that the parent sector of FinTech start-up i.e. finance and technology department is mostly male-dominated as it is believed that the female does not have the skill set required to manage finance and technology. Hence, this stereotype led to a decrease in the opportunity of growth for women and even brings inequality in pay scale, thus affecting the leadership effectiveness of women. So, in order to represent the contribution of female leaders in this diversely growing sector, it is required to analyse the factors responsible for affecting the women leadership. Thus, the conceptual framework presented in Figure 3-1 is suitable only for FinTech start-up sector of the UK.

3.2 Conclusion

From the discussion undertaken in this chapter, it is evident that leadership is an ambiguous concept and there are probably as many definitions of the term as people are attempting to propose it. Similarly, gender roles in leadership are also a contradictory subject wherein the opinions of authors differ widely. But for the current research, it can be assumed that women and men do differ in the depiction of the leadership traits. The current study shows that there is a difference in the acceptance of men and women at work in different countries of the world.

The research has identified four main levels which all have their influential factors. The four main factors are societal, organisational, individual and technological factors. The societal factors are indirect factors which have an impact on organisations as well as individual workers. Organisational factors are related to culture in the workplace and therefore, can be changed more easily. It has been seen that it is necessary to promote educational choices from an early age in addition to mentoring and networking to help organisations in reducing gender inequality. Further, organisational factors of perceiving women to be incompetent of leadership widen the gap. Inflexible work arrangements, sexual harassment, wage discrimination, lack of coaching and mentoring are some of the factors that hinder women progression to corporate positions. The fourth factor is technological factor, the factor is very important for women as technology is considered to be women's weak link. It is developed and women can be trained to become a hybrid individual. (for this study the term "hybrid" will be used synonymously to STEM-educated individual) However, the literature also evidenced the role of the individual and political factors that impede women career advancement.

Previous studies have proven that companies benefit from having more women in their managerial teams. Therefore, it is necessary to identify the factors that are responsible for creating successful leaders among women in the UK's financial technology sector to provide valuable recommendations and to promote the same. As far as the case of the UK's FinTech start-up sector is concerned, the literature offered that the situation is no different either. The representation of women at leadership positions is extremely low and most studies attribute it

to the masculine nature of financial and technological industries, the parent industries of the FinTech start-ups. A lack of STEM-based education has been highlighted as the prominent factor discouraging women from joining the FinTech start-up sector, thus it should be promoted especially among the women. Apart from this, organisational roles based on gender-based congruence are deemed to enhance women participation in the workforce.

However, in the next chapter, the study will discuss how the leadership theories concerning women are perceived by the target respondents and how they apply to the UK's FinTech start-up sector. Organisations shall be benefitted by this as women leaders tend to increase diversity, improve company performance, equality and ensure optimum use of all available resources and know-how. The research methodology is discussed in the next chapter.

Chapter: 4 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.0 Introduction to the chapter

The purpose of this chapter is to present the systematic process of identifying the problem, researching methods, collecting data, analysing the data with approaches that facilitate reaching a certain conclusion. The chapter highlights the assumptions underpinning the current research as also introduces the research strategy and empirical procedures applied in the study. It further defines the scope and limitation of the research design and highlights on the multiple alternatives undertaken in the study to highlight the factors responsible for creating successful leadership among women leaders and specifically so in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK.

The primary aim of the chapter is to present the methods of analysis employed in the current study and present a complete methodology that was used to achieve the objectives. The chapter initiates from the introduction of the research strategy to introduce the research philosophy, study design, and hypothesis. The next section highlights the sampling plan for the current study and explains the source of data. Proceeding sections elaborate on data collection methods, questionnaire structure, procedures employed in data analysis, reliability and validation analysis of the study, and the limitations of the methodology adopted.

4.1 Research Process

Detailed and systematic representation of the research process is important, hence the concept of “research onion” proposed by Saunders (2003) is used. This research onion model represented in the figure 4-1 below defines the process of analysing the elements of research to formulate the research design of the study. The entire process consists of research

philosophy, approaches, strategies, choices, time horizon, techniques and procedures used in the study.

The first layer of the model is research philosophy. It discusses the beliefs that the researcher has about the data collection, its analysis, and the interpretation of the results. The researcher's personal views about the world encountered realities, and human knowledge, limits and assumptions, affect the choice of research philosophy. These philosophies are classified as positivism, realism, interpretivism and pragmatism. A researcher who focuses on analysing the outcomes to generalise its findings uses positivism philosophy (test based scientific approach). Scientific enquiry of existing reality follows realism philosophy. Studying the social phenomenon by analysing people's perception in any environment is interpretivism philosophy. Pragmatism philosophy refers to the existence of multiple realities requiring more than one analysis. The process of research begins with choosing any one of the above-mentioned philosophies. This paper concentrates on positivism and interpretivism philosophies.

The second layer, i.e. Research Approach deals with identifying the way the entire research will take place. It acts as a base of formation of strategy that gives information about the type of research that would be done and it gives direction to the methods used in the study. Saunders divides these approaches into deductive and inductive. Deductive type of research deals with taking a theory or literature into consideration and then analysing the results based on data collection. This approach is towards validating the applicability of the theory. However, inductive approach deals with testing the collected data and then the formation of the theory based on the results derived (Al Zefeiti & Mohamad, 2015; Ohi, Thi, & Oanh, 2011; M. N. Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2013). This study will use the deductive approach.

The Third layer of the research onion identifies the strategy of the research. It helps in determining the way the analysis would be done to answer the research questions and fulfil the objectives. These strategies are classified as an experiment, action research, survey, grounded theory, case study, archival research, and ethnography. Experiment research determines the cause-effect relationship along with verifying the inferences about them. Action research is based on identifying the immediate solution to the problem. Survey study helps in identifying

the psychological and social factors of a population by analysing the sample collected. Based on the social data collected, grounded theory can be applied to test the hypothesis to derive the factors affecting which then sometimes leads to the formulation of a theory. Case study strategy analyses the real-life situation. Archival research is historical research where a review of earlier researches is performed to derive information about a study. Finally, ethnography deals with analysing the views of people by living with the population of the study. It deals with studying the behaviour, culture, language, and different views of people (Al Zefeiti & Mohamad, 2015; M. N. K. Saunders, 2009). This paper has used the grounded theory.

Research choices are the next layer of the research onion and it helps in determining the method chosen in the study for analysis. As per the objectives, and method of data collection is chosen. It helps in determining whether a qualitative or quantitative method with being used or a mix of both was used for the study. There are 3 main choices i.e. Mono, Mixed, and Multi. The Mono method states that either one of both methods was used for data collection. The Mixed-method is usage of both the methods for fulfilling different objectives of the study. The Multi-method also consists of both methods but mainly include analysis using one method and the other method is used for adding supplementary support (Melnikovas, 2018; Ohi et al., 2011; M. N. Saunders et al., 2013). Along with grounded theory this paper will use the mixed method.

Another layer of this onion model is Time Horizon. This step states the time used by the researcher for fulfilling the objective. It can be either cross-sectional or longitudinal. The Cross-section is the research based on a particular time i.e. analysing different factors at a point of time. In the case of longitudinal time horizon, data is collected for a long period (M. Saunders & Tosey, 2013).

The last layer of the onion deals with the data collection and analysis procedure. It provides information about the data collected and the way the analysis is performed to derive the results of the study (Melnikovas, 2018).

Each component of the research onion has its advantages, which makes it imperative for a researcher to integrate it into their research. This study is focused on comprehending the factors which affect the successful female leadership in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK. This

pertains to the analysis of a social phenomenon, i.e. female leadership and individuals' perception of female leaders' success. Moreover, the findings of the study will be generalised to all start-ups operating in the FinTech sector. Therefore, positivism and interpretivism philosophies are followed. The deductive approach is used in this study. Further grounded theory is the strategy used in the study along with using a mixed-method. This complete research process will be discussed in detail in the subsequent sections.

Figure 4-1: Research Onion (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2008)
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4.2 Research Philosophy

4.2.1 Research Philosophies

The research philosophy highlights the belief of the researcher on the method to be employed in data gathering, analysis, and its usage in the study. The current study was based on an epistemology that is establishing the study on ‘what is known to be true’ rather than doxology or what is believed to be true by the researcher (M. Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2009). Galliers, (1991) further explains that the purpose of knowledge is to change things from what is ‘believed’ to what is ‘known’.

4.2.1.1 Positivism

Positivism as a research philosophy relies on the concept that reality is stable and observable by the researcher from the viewpoint of the objectives of the study. In this philosophy, the phenomena under study are not disturbed. The parameter under study is isolated and the observations on factors affecting them are repeated to form a relationship between the independent variables. The process involves manipulation of reality for the single independent variable to ascertain regularities in the pattern. Predictions of the study are employed in studies of quantitative orientation, and the observation in the study is based on the experimental and explained inter-relationships and realities (DiVanna, 2010).

4.2.1.2 Interpretivism

The interpretivist approach of research philosophy is based on the subjective interpretation of reality. The philosophy suggests interventions to the reality to comprehend the objectives of the study while integrating human interest. Interpretivism requires studying occurrences based on their natural environment to acknowledge their effects on the independent variable. In interpretivism, the researcher has to assume the phenomenon through its social construct and shared meanings. Additionally, the philosophical approach in interpretivism is based on

employing multiple methods that assure reflection of the difference that exists between the people under study (Matta, 2015).

4.2.1.3 Realism

The realism approach of research is similar to positivism, as it advocates the usage of a scientific approach for the development of knowledge on the research subject. Realism is of two types; direct and critical. Direct realism philosophy is based on naive practicality with the attitude of what the researcher sees and experiences through his sense, is the true representation of the problem statement. The second type of realism is critical realism, which, is based on the analysis of deceptiveness of the researcher's experience. Contemporary critical realism is seen as alternative to both, the positivist and interpretivist paradigms. It uses elements from both the theories to form a new approach for developing knowledge (Sobh & Perry, 2006).

4.2.1.4 Pragmatism

The pragmatist philosophy of research is based on a thorough analysis of the concepts before accepting them. Such that the researcher applying pragmatist approaches accepts only those concepts in the study that are supported by actions to be relevant. The pragmatics identifies that there are several ways of interpreting a research phenomenon and a single point of view cannot reveal the entire picture of the study. The pragmatic philosophy identifies multiple realities and bases the analysis of the research problem on the modified philosophical assumption that requires continuous analysis of new positions in research (Hookway, 2013).

The review of literature in this research helped in determining that the FinTech sector was male-dominated and there are very fewer opportunities available for women to work at top-level as leaders. However, with the technological development of the economies, the importance of women leader was realised. Today they possess good communication skills, decision-making skills, vision and creativity. Further, many policies like encouraging gender

diversity and gender equality have been implemented by organisations which have led to an increase in female leaders. However, the effectiveness of these leaders is affected by socio-cultural factors like stereotypes or family, organisational factors like values or leadership style, personal factors like competence or personality, and technological factors like transportation facilities or training opportunities.

The belief of the researcher is that identification of these factors will lead to better opportunities for women in profession, as it will identify the shortcomings with respect to the factors and suggest ways in which they can be addressed. Thus, although the researcher was able to obtain information regarding the factors responsible for successful leadership, there lacked empirical evidence connecting these factors to the success of female leaders, particularly in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK. This was the main gap identified in this study. Therefore epistemology was found to be the suitable choice of philosophy for this research. Furthermore, success of an organisation is not just dependent on the leaders, instead there are many employees who together function to enhance the performance of the organisation. Thus, stakeholders of this study are the employees from each department i.e. sales, management, finance or IT. Hence, employees of each gender i.e. engineers, CEO, Tech support, personal assistant, product manager, work as a stakeholder for the organisation hence contributing in affecting the effectiveness and success of stakeholder.

4.3 Research Design

There are three major research paradigms that can be employed in the research process. These are qualitative, quantitative, and mixed research.

4.3.1 Qualitative Research

Qualitative research offers a subjective view of the phenomenon under study. It offers insight into the emotional, experimental, and social aspects of the phenomena. The qualitative research

process aims to draw out the overall comprehensibility and perception entailing the linkage between successful leadership and women leaders. Additionally, qualitative research processes are directed towards the exploration of human experience to ensure understanding of the underlying behaviour and reason behind the phenomena.

In qualitative research, every stage should be clearly defined as there is no codification of responses gathered from respondents. Also this approach aids researcher in conducting the research based on theories identified by the researcher in consideration of the issue at hand. Qualitative research strategy aids in determining the 'how' and 'why' of the proposed research questions (Cohen et al., 2002).

This approach encompasses qualitative data gathered via verbal expressions i.e. not numeric. Besides, the study of Saunders et al., (2009), qualitative data analysis assists in cross-checking of the results derived under quantitative analysis. This, in turn, strengthens its results and establishes significance concerning the issue at hand (J. McMillan & Schumacher, 2001). Also, the qualitative approach considers the non-numerical interpretation of the content that results in better perceptive of the social phenomena of multiple realities. Moreover, the study of Reeves et al., (2008) acknowledges that reliability and validity are most appropriate and applicable to qualitative researchers since it includes non-codified responses from the respondents. Following this, the study of Dr Jane Wambui, (1998) discussed feminist perceptions on preferring qualitative analysis approach.

This study acknowledged the fact that traditional quantitative research confined respondents completely to the purview of the researcher about an agenda. Moreover, such researcher approaches silence the voices of participants with that of the researcher. In consideration of this scenario, the feminist researcher majorly considers qualitative research to be an appropriate approach that can reveal and understand the experiences of women in contemporary society. Also this approach aids in addressing their needs to the subject of the agenda. Moreover, there are similar widespread views attained via other women and thus reflects a strong voice that can bring solutions to the issues of broader social change and social justice especially regarding the changing condition of women. Further interviews are the best

mechanism underlying qualitative research approach to gather data. There are three ways: Structured interviews, semi-structured interviews, and unstructured interviews.

Within a structured interview, the interviewer prepares a set of predetermined questions to be asked from the respondents in a specific order (Langkos, 2014). These questions are about the theme of the research. Following this, the respondents mark down the relevant answer to the question put forward. This type of research method is mainly used in surveys. Next is semi-structured interviews. Within this method, there are also predetermined questions but the respondents can answer the same in their own words (Rajasekar, Philominathan, and Chinnathambi, 2006). However few interviewers use a topic guide including a checklist about the information on the theme of the topic. Additionally, the interviewer can even investigate other areas concerning the respondent's answers in addition to other supplementary questions for clarification. This method aids in gaining in-depth information in an organised way from the given set of respondents. Lastly within the unstructured interviews, the interviewer follows no particular paradigm, restrictions or any predetermined questions including any checklist or options. The interviewer addresses the response of the broad question from the participant thereby creating an open, informal, and spontaneous discussion (Kumar, 2009). Also, the interviewer undertakes several other questions to detect inconsistencies for viewing details of the issue at hand. It's mainly used to examine the background of any experience of the participant in consideration of little information about a topic. However, this research approach doesn't aid in quantifying predictions of future events, has lower credibility, longer time in the analysis of data may contain biased answers, etc. (Benbasat, Goldstein, & Mead, 1987). This may make it more difficult to get the results published.

In the current study, the qualitative research process will facilitate in highlighting the experience of the women leaders in the Fin-Tech start-up segment via interviews using an open-ended questionnaire (Campbell & Scott, 2011).

4.3.2 Quantitative Research

The quantitative research method is an objective and formal review of the systematic process under study. The quantitative research utilises numerical data to obtain quantifiable information and focus on narrow questions on the study. According to Bryman and Bell, (2011), quantitative research portrays one particular reality that is achieved employing the use of statistical measures and other techniques. This particular approach analyses relationships and causality among variables that in turn results in gaining a much more succinct result. Additionally, this research strategy systematically arranges the data and derives statistical results depicting the significance of the relationships accounted in the study. It also aids in determining similarities as well as any differences among the variables of the dataset.

Another major feature underlying quantitative research approach indicates that the sample chosen for the study must represent the features of the population. To this, this approach requires testing the reliability and validity of the instruments to attain reliable results. A Cronbach's statistic can be used to identify the interrelatedness of the variables within the dataset (Kothari, Kumar and Uusitalo, 2014). The results of the Cronbach's Alpha test are shown in table 47 in appendix V. The values for the five parameters including the effective leadership behaviour, factors impacting the women leadership, the effectiveness of women leader, shortcomings of women leader and the impact of leadership on the organisation performance are greater than 0.6 indicating high reliability of the data. Besides, it is also crucial that the entire data collected through different methods and instruments should describe the variables concerning the theme of the study completely.

Furthermore, a quantitative approach should represent suitable attributes of particular individuals, situations, or groups participating in the survey. Figure 4-2 below shows the major

steps to be followed while conducting a quantitative research analysis (Bryman and Bell, 2011) (Rajasekar, Philominathan, and Chinnathambi, 2006).

**Figure 4-2: Main stages in Quantitative research approach (Bryman & Bell, 2011)
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- Elaborate theory:** At the first stage, the researcher identifies the main variables of the theory for the theme of the study. To this, the researcher explores vast data across existing journals, magazines, newspaper reports, etc. the researcher tries to identify what all elements are important for their decided research theme.
- Devise hypothesis:** After acknowledging the main variables in the study, the researcher next formulates the research problem of the study in form of a possible hypothesis that in turn will be either rejected or accepted based on results diagnosed after the data analysis. A hypothesis statement reflects as to what variables will affect the other identified variable(s).
- Select research design:** Next, the researcher decides to execute the study in the form of selecting a research design for the hypothesis constructed. A research design is kind of a theoretical framework that encompasses research methods, approach, techniques, etc.

this aids the researcher towards the aim of the study thereby gaining answer for the hypothesis formulated.

- iv. Devise measure of concepts: For the next step, the researcher identifies the most suitable method to measure the concepts of the research theme undertaken. Additionally, the hypothesis framed in consideration to the aim of the study is tested with the most appropriate test to derive authenticity of the same.
- v. Select research site(s): For the collection of data, the researcher now decides as to where it can execute the study that is the location of the research and its participants. There can be more than one location as per the theme of the study. Data is gathered from these locations from the selected respondents.
- vi. Select research respondents: Also, the researcher identifies the target respondents of the research study. There can be a set of respondents at a research site but the theme of the study decides the respondents of the most suitable answers that the study intends to answer. Also, the researcher needs to decide the number of sufficient responses which, will be acceptable in gaining the insight of the research topic.
- vii. Administer research instruments/ collect data: The researcher then focuses on the medium to gather the data from the respondents selected for the study. As discussed above, there can be three ways to gather data from the respondents: Structured interviews (mostly used for survey analysis), semi-structured interview and unstructured interviews.
- viii. Process data: After the collection of data, the researcher processes or compiles the data in a codified format to attain its output via software using an appropriate test. The data is then addressed with the required measure thereby previewing its results.
- ix. Analyse data: The data results obtained via software testing are then analysed with the given criteria. Finally, the hypothesis formulated at the beginning of the quantitative research hypothesis is analysed via the results attained.
- x. Develop findings/conclusions: As per the analysis of data, the hypothesis is rejected or accepted thereby developing the conclusion of the study. This supports in screening the research question's outcome of the data collected.

However, there are certain disadvantages to conducting a quantitative research approach. To gain access to a large sample size is a time consuming and costly procedure (Kothari, 2004). Further, there is no in-depth knowledge of the subject theme chosen as there are a limited set of questions put forward (M. Saunders et al., 2009). The researcher faces a lack of funds in tracking their targeted demographic that includes spending money on travel, food, and transportation.

In the current study, the quantifiable data was used to conduct an unbiased enquiry to understand the factors contributing to women leaders in the Fin-Tech segment (Creswell, 2013).

4.3.3 Mixed Research

The mixed research combines the processes of qualitative and quantitative methods to develop a complete framework on the subject under study. The mixed-method focuses on the collection, analysis of both qualitative and quantitative data in a single study. The approaches combined provide a better understanding of the overall research problem than either of the approaches in segregation (Nicholas, 2010).

In mixed methods, two main arguments support its prevalence in executing a research study: Embedded method and paradigm method (Bryman and Bell, 2011). The embedded method involves the convergence of two datasets by bringing them together, one builds on the other or building one dataset within the other. This helps one of the datasets supported by the other dataset. Overall the mixing of datasets presents a complete picture of the issue at hand. Thus it is just not enough to simply collect and analyse quantitative and qualitative data.

The quantitative data is well facilitated with qualitative data to gain in-depth knowledge of the issue (Klenke, 2008). Moreover, a quantitative study is addressed as weak in comprehending the context (Ghauri, Kjell, and Ivar, 1995). Also, the voices of the respondents are not directly assessed and reached to the researcher in quantitative research. In comparison, qualitative research examines personal interpretations of the respondents on the subject and derives more

than required information. However, there can be a bias that in turn cannot be generalised to a large group since there is less number of participants in an interview conducted (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017).

Mixed methods thus provide a researcher with all tools of data collection to attain more comprehensive evidence for studying a research problem. These methods provide solutions to the problems that cannot be served in separation with quantitative or qualitative data. These methods involve the use of multiple worldviews based on the existence of a problem as per the worldviews. Mixed methods include the researcher to decide on the use of combining inductive and deductive thinking to derive a result from theory or theory from the results derived. However, it is not easy to conduct mixed-methods effortlessly since it takes much time and resources in gathering data for both quantitative and qualitative data analysis. It complicates the procedures of research and requires clear presentation if the reader is going to be able to sort out the different procedures. The figure 4-3 below describes the process of embedding different datasets.

Figure 4-3: Embedding datasets (Researcher)

Another argument in conducting a mixed research approach involves the paradigm approach. There were different views of different researchers regarding the involvement of quantitative and qualitative data together for the theme of the study. The researcher established that research paradigm is a philosophical way of thinking with which the researcher continues the research theme of the study (Given, 2008). These methods are either in terms of the crossing of paradigm emphasis or the time taken for conducting quantitative and qualitative phases. There is another way of carrying out mixed methods that are in terms of the degree of mixture. This means that there is a combination of methods of data collection, research methods, during data analysis and data interpretation (Glogowska, 2010). Lastly, the researcher must critically examine the ideological approach to a study. Also these methods aid in forming many potential classification dimensions.

For data collection, the researcher should view as to what are the values of each quantitative and qualitative paradigm independently in addition to the time taken for its fulfilment. Further for the analysis of data stage, the researcher should decide as to what statistical techniques can be used for quantitative data and what descriptive or analytical methods can be used for qualitative data collected (Kristianslund, Gronhaug, and Ghauri, 1995). Following this, the triangulation method confirms the validity of results attained from research data analysis thereby making a final report (Qu and Dumay, 2011). Thus the nature and use of the triangle is established with that of the results derived in the final report prepared. If it is convergent this means that the qualitative and quantitative outcomes are quite similar. If the results are complementary, this indicated that the quantitative and qualitative outcomes can be used to supplement each other. Lastly, if the results are contradictory then the results indicate different outcomes. Thus the logic of triangulation helps in the use of more than one method in consideration top the issue at hand following with interpretable robust results (Creswell, 2013).

The current study will utilise a mixed approach to highlight the factors that contribute to the successful leadership of working women in the sector of Financial Technology in the UK (Creswell, 2007).

4.3.4 Types of data

4.3.4.1 Primary data

The primary data is collected intensively for the current study. Qualitative and quantitative methods of primary study have been employed. For qualitative methods, first-hand data is collected by interviewing one top-level manager of the selected 5 companies in the study i.e. Truelayer, Transferwise, Monzo, Nutmeg, and Starling. These 5 companies are the FinTech start-ups in London where women are in the profile of leadership. The leaders interviewed have at least 15 subordinates working under them and have an experience of at least 8 years. As these companies were promoting the female leadership and were among the top 10 FinTech start-ups of UK in 2019, thus they were considered for the study. The interview technique helps in understanding the underlying reasons and motivation for the attitude of the respondents towards women leadership in the industry. As the interview has been collected on a one-to-one basis, it allows the collection of responses at a good rate. Further interviewing the managers permits the chances of collecting in-depth information and investigates on the correct motives and feelings of the respondent (Qu & Dumay, 2011).

Additionally, the study is based on a close-ended questionnaire thus using the Cochran's formula sample size is computed

Formula, $N = \frac{Z^2 p(1-p)}{e^2}$

N = Sample size

Z = confidence interval (0.95% = 1.96)

p = significance level at 95% (0.05)

e = margin of error (50% or 0.05)

Thus, the sample size is 100 for the study.

The questionnaires for quantitative evaluation have been employed in the current study. The advantages of the questionnaire include that it is a cost-effective method of gathering large scale data. It allows anonymity of the respondent and no prior engagement is required in the process. However, the primary data collection method faces the problem of being a design constraint. The questions are framed by the researcher's understanding of the industry. For interviews, the process is time-consuming and has geographic limitation. Further to the questionnaire, the response is spontaneous or independent of each other (Yin, 2013).

4.3.4.2 Secondary Data

The secondary data collection methods are employed in the current study using the quantitative data that has been previously collected by other researchers for different purposes. The secondary data employed in the current study comprised of publications on factors affecting women leadership across segments in the UK. Other sources include journal articles, reports, news articles, and books that have earlier reported on the role of female leadership in the FinTech industry. Secondary data help in guiding the present study and identification of the data set required for conducting the primary research. While using the secondary data care should be taken on the purpose of the study, the credibility of the information, and the timeline of the data collected (W. L. (William L. Neuman, 2013).

4.4 Research approach

Additionally, as a mixed approach in research design is adopted for the current paper, the current section will highlight the suitable approach for the study and will compare deductive versus inductive methods. In the study by Ketokivi and Mantere (2010), the authors have described a deductive approach to be derived from a set of properties or theory. The hypothesis is assumed based on all premises in the theory being true. On the other hand, inductive reasoning does not link the premises and its end. Rather, it starts with the hypothesis about the

organisation, or a business problem and investigates the hypothesis through various methods. The result is then used to generalise the theory on the subject (Hayes, Heit, & Swendsen, 2010). Thus, the deductive approach helps in validating the applicability of a theory i.e. after considering the theories which are already given, data is collected to test whether the theory is applicable.

The hypothesis is formulated as per the theory and using different tests, the empirical evidence is provided about the validity of the theory in reality. However, inductive approach deals with the realistic collection of data and after testing the data, theories are formulated based on the results. It is not based on existing theories. Hence, the results of inductive approach lead to the formulation of new generalised theories. Thus, for the current exploratory study of determining the factors responsible for creating successful leadership among women leaders in the UK's FinTech Sector, an inductive approach was adopted. The study will start with the developmental roles of women leader in the FinTech sector and then present a broader generalisation and theory on the drivers that can lead to a more successful direction in the studied sector. Inductive research in the current study was based on reasoning, with an exploratory and more open-ended approach. Inductive reasoning is also a preferred method for the current study as its methodology of investigation begins with an acknowledgement of trends and patterns in a set of data. This trend subsequently can be articulated to form a hypothesis that is finally developed into a general conclusion (Zalaghi and Khazaei, 2016). Furthermore, the current study is based on building a theory of determining the factors that influence women leadership roles in the FinTech start-ups. The study will begin by examining the meaning of women leadership and take into account the data that will lead to an incremental analysis of trends in start-up businesses (Anderson, 2011).

Sampling plan

The current study will focus on the level of female representation in higher management roles in the FinTech start-ups. Additionally, the current study will employ a questionnaire and secondary research to identify the dependent and independent variable that affects the progress of the career of women leaders in the sector. For the analysis of the role of influencing factor

that adds to the leadership behaviour among the women, leaders supervising at least 15 direct subordinates for 8 years have been selected for the study.

London is selected as the preferred site to study the factors leading to increased female leadership as London is among the top financial centres. It is the fertile site for the analysis of female leadership in the FinTech Sector (Finch, 2017). Additionally, Langley (2017) highlighted that the FinTech sector in the UK has been showing the progress that points towards the available superior financial infrastructure in the country. Further, the author also highlights that the site is endowed richly with the appropriate capital and technological knowledge of the consumers.

For comprehending the factors contributing to the development of women in the leadership role in the FinTech start-ups, five leaders of the start-ups in the UK were asked to respond to surveys. The survey has been developed to comprehend the present developmental practices in women leaders in their respective companies. The surveys were conducted across five organisations to study the effectiveness of the woman leader of their organisation. The final sample of 100 respondents was analysed to highlight the shortcomings and future outlook under their leadership. The respondents were chosen from start-ups ranging widely in the business size and units among the start-ups. Further 5 managers were interviewed from these 5 companies to gain insight on the subject.-

4.4.1 Sample size

To comprehend the factors affecting the women leaders, the study should be of adequate sample size. The size should be adequate to estimate with precision the prevalence of the population. The study by Naing, Winn, and Rusli (2006) highlighted that the decision on the appropriate value of the sample size is not always dependent on the largest sample size. The authors highlight that the aim should be to get an adequate sample size that is cost-effective and precise in the statistical sense. 100 respondents have been chosen as the preferred sample size for the study. The study will encompass respondents from 5 organisations that are 20

respondents from each firm. The study will collect the opinion of respondents from across start-up companies operating in the Finance and Technical companies operating in the UK.

4.4.1.1 Companies' profile

The FinTech start-up companies (no more than 10 years old) located in London, and having female leaders with a minimum of 8 years' experience who are at least responsible for 15 subordinates are selected for the study. 5 such start-up organisations are included in the study. They are Truelayer, Transferwise, Monzo Bank, Nutmeg Savings and Investments, and Starling Bank

4.4.1.2 Respondent profile (survey)

The respondents covered in the study are both male and female employees working at higher or middle-level positions in the FinTech start-ups of the UK. The respondents included in the study were from various departments i.e. finance, IT, Management, Customer support, production, and sales. They had profiles like CEO, Engineer, Product Manager, Client Care, Product Manager, Design Engineer, Talent acquisition partner, Legal counsel, UI Designer, Product operation, and COO. However, one condition was there for a selection of employees i.e. they should have at least 1-year experience in that organisation.

4.4.1.3 Respondent profile (interview)

The scope of this research is limited to female leadership only, with the primary aim being to identify the factors responsible for their leadership success. Therefore, only female leaders were considered for the interview. Their perspective was considered to be instrumental in answering this aim. 1 leader from each company was selected for this purpose. They have worked for more than 8 years in the sector. They hold senior positions such as COO, Marketing

Executive, Head of Product Management, People Operations Manager, and Managing Director.

4.4.2 Sampling type

For the quantitative study, a systematic sampling method has been used in the current study combining the benefits of both random and non-random sampling methods. Through the random sampling technique, each employee or member of the firm is provided with the equal opportunity of being selected for the survey. As the sample needs to represent the opinion of all segments of employees in the FinTech sector, stratified sampling technique was used. Stratified segment classifies the population-based on strata. The characteristic of the strata is identifiable for that segment of the population and helps in determining the factors that they perceive contribute to the rise in female leadership within the industry (Lynch, 2008). The systematic approach combines the technique of both random and stratified sampling techniques.

4.4.3 Stakeholder analysis

While conducting the literature review, the researcher observed the most of the findings were summarised by a particular stakeholder group, i.e. males (Paustuan-Underdahl, Walker, & Woehr, 2014; Cook and Glass, 2014). Therefore, a stakeholder analysis is important and it has been conducted to determine the main participants of this primary research. A stakeholder can be defined as “any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organisation's objective” (Freeman, 2015, p. 84). Identifying stakeholders is a necessary first step in creating a research methodology since it establishes the criteria for selection of participants. Stakeholder analysis helps identify the stakeholders of the study and what influence they have on the outcomes of this research.

For this purpose, the following four steps are identified as important:

- Defining the stakeholders
- Analysing stakeholders by the influence
- Report communications with stakeholders
- Engaging with them

The process is explained below.

4.4.3.1 Defining the stakeholders

The key stakeholders of this study are female leaders and the FinTech start-ups they lead.

Following is the detailed list:

- Female leaders
- Employees
- Educational institutions
- Government institutions (taxation, funding, etc.)
- Families

4.4.3.2 Analysing them by the influence

The second step included analysing the influence of these stakeholders in this study. The principal stakeholder includes female leaders because the aim of this study was centred around leadership success of females in the FinTech start-ups operating in the UK. Of the other relevant stakeholders, the employees were the second most important as they deal with the leaders daily, and influence the success of the leaders and vice-versa. Moreover, the opinions of males, as well as female employees, are equally important in determining their perspectives regarding the success of their female leaders. Therefore it was decided that the primary research would include a survey of employees (being larger in number) and interviews of the female leaders.

4.4.3.3 Communication with the stakeholders

The female leaders of the organisations were contacted via email first. Following this, telephone calls were conducted with them for interviews. For the survey, the employees were contacted via emails obtained from the leaders. Employees were then requested to fill the questionnaire in email. This process is explained in detail in the below sections.

4.4.3.4 Engaging with stakeholder

After prior permission from the university and the leaders, necessary access to the employees was gained and a plan of action was charted out with the organisations for collection of survey responses. Finally, the interested employees responded to the emails within the stipulated time frame.

4.5 Data collection procedure

4.5.1 Questionnaires

The purpose of the questionnaire is to collect unbiased, accurate, and relevant data for the study. Additionally, the questionnaire in a study provides structure to the process of the interview. The systematic response to the questionnaire allows the researcher to process data applicable following the study. The structure of the data additionally facilitates the analysis of the result as well. The questionnaires have been designed based on the objective of the study to understand factors that have led to women leaders in the FinTech sector.

As suggested by (Acharya, 2010) while developing the questionnaire, the focus is kept on the information needed to ensure that the respondents do not view any lack of clarity. Further, the questions were developed based on the analysis plan for the study. As the authors suggest that questionnaire without an orientation toward clear analytical outputs would lead to overlooking of the factors that have led to the success of women leadership. Additionally, Willimack,

(2013) suggests that the questionnaire should be developed keeping the end-user of the study in mind. As the research design chosen for the current research is exploratory, the structure of the questionnaire will focus on facilitating the respondents in providing the correct information as per their capacity.

For both interview and open-ended questionnaire, the structured technique is employed in the current study. The questionnaire was designed using the funnel technique to ensure the easy flow of questions. Acharya (2010) in a study described the flow of questions using the funnel technique. Encouragingly, the current questionnaire will also start with broad general questions to ensure that the respondents are at ease to answer the questions. Further, after the warm-up questions and getting the respondents involved in the study, the questions based on the role played by the factors in influencing women in leadership roles were incorporated. At the end of the questionnaire, general questions on the profile of the respondents were included to indicate on the demography and other classification parameters of the respondents (Bowen, Martin, and Hunt, 2002).

The structured quantitative and close-ended questionnaire to be answered by the 100 respondents will employ multiple choices, Likert scale, and importance scale. For the interview, open-ended questions were used. Additionally, to ensure valid and reliable results, the measurement of error has to be minimised. To limit the errors, unambiguous questions with clear instructions were included. In the questionnaire designing, the flow of the questionnaire and the wordings were developed through field testing of the pilot questionnaire. Furthermore, while designing and administering the questionnaires in the current study, ethical considerations also have been kept in mind. The respondent's consent was obtained by providing information on the nature of the study. Additionally, the respondents were informed of the use of collected data and precaution were taken to ensure that the information provided by the respondents will not jeopardise their security and safety (Krosnick & Presser, 2010).

The data collection process involved several steps. Firstly, the researcher identified the companies that fitted the sampling criteria, i.e. FinTech start-ups that have been operating for

less than 10 years in the UK. Initially, the researcher identified 35 such companies. This was then narrowed down to 8 companies, which had females in the leadership position.

After identification, the researcher sent a personalised email to each company, explaining the intent of this study, the aim, the hypothesis, its significance and the lack of existing literature. The researcher requested their participation in the study via the survey of employees as well as interviews. The questionnaires, as well as the necessary university approval documents, were attached in the email.

Then, the researcher conducted several rounds of follow-up with the companies via phones and emails. Finally, only 5 companies expressed an interest in participating in the survey. To those that expressed interest, the researcher sent a detailed email assuring them of the ethics followed, i.e. that the data collected from were used for this study only. This enhanced their confidence in further participation.

Thereafter, the researcher sought a suitable time and medium for conducting the interviews with the leaders, as well as the survey with the employees. On the stipulated time, the researcher called these leaders and asked them the interview questions on the phone. All the responses were recorded and later transcribed. For the survey, the researcher circulated the questionnaire via email. Initially, all the employees in each of these 5 firms were targeted for the survey, thus bringing the initial sample size to 254 respondents. However, after the first follow-up, only 48 sent their responses. The researcher then conducted two more rounds of follow-ups, until the desired sample size was reached, i.e. 100.

After data collection, the analysis procedure will depend on the nature of the data collected for the current study. For the secondary data collected from the literature that have already established the factors leading to the success of women leaders, was analysed through meta-analytical review method. Additionally, for the data collected by questionnaire method, due to their quantitative nature was analysed using the statistical software packages.

The survey responses were analysed for obtaining descriptive and inferential results using SPSS v21.

4.6 Data Analysis procedure

After the collection of primary data through the interviews and the survey, the researcher followed a systematic procedure for analysing the data. In case of interviews, the responses were recorded and transcribed verbatim, after which they were analysed using thematic analysis format.

In case of surveys, the data was analysed using SPSS software. The SPSS analysis for the primary research allows a thorough analysis of the data collected using a spreadsheet program. The data entered, however, is unlike the nature of spreadsheet. The column data defines the variables that are central to the study and the data is then worked upon to present the result of the study through graphs, statistics, and tables. The SPSS statistical v 21 is chosen as the software to conduct quantitative analysis in the current study. Following tests will be conducted.

- Descriptive Statistics: Descriptive statistics method is used to study the categorical data in the first section of the survey and a few nominal types of data in the second section of the survey. A frequency analysis was done to understand the demographic and professional profile of the respondents. Further, the analysed data has been plotted in graphs for better visualisation of the analysis.
- Inferential Statistics: Inferential statistics helps one to draw insights from the data collected from the respondents and put up a strong conclusion, supporting the objective of the research. Inferential statistics were performed on the different factors related to the women leadership. Inferential analysis tools used in the present research study are correlation test and regression analysis.
- Correlation Test: Correlation test checks if there is an association between the different independent variables (factors), which have been articulated for the study. For better results, those independent variables should be highly significant.

- Regression Analysis: Regression analysis helps to establish an association between the dependent variable (Objective of the study) and independent variables (different factors that could be affected by the objective of the study). This analysis helps to build a model to understand the pattern of factors influencing the teaching anxiety of student teachers.
- Cross Tab Analysis: Crosstab analysis has been conducted to analyse the difference in the perception of male and female employees towards women leadership in organisational performance. Furthermore, for the current study, the cross-tabulation will break down the data of women leaders to concentrate only on the FinTech sector and female leaders holding managerial posts in the respective companies. The specific data needs pose a limitation to the study as the results of the study cannot be interpolated to other regions owing to the difference in the technical knowledge, financial infrastructure, policy incentives, and capital structure in other areas.

4.7 Hypothesis Development

In the current study, several hypotheses will be developed to establish the significance of some factors in successful women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK. Following is the list of that hypotheses that will be tested:

4.7.1 Hypothesis 1

***H01:** Social factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK*

***HAI:** Social factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK*

The literature review identified certain social factors like inferiority of female concerning male employees, glass ceiling, gender stereotypes, patriarchy system, and family-related issues, perception of people is analysed on the contribution of these factors in affecting the success of female leaders. Thus the first hypothesis framed is regarding the impact of these social factors on the success of female leaders in the FinTech start-ups in the UK.

4.7.2 Hypothesis 2

***H02:** Organisational factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK*

***HA2:** Organisational factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK*

In the literature review, it was identified that there exists a difference in the culture of organisations like priorities of company, policies, beliefs, values, and structure of the organisation. Organisational factors like working environment, values of the organisation, policies to manage organisational resources, organisational setting, and leadership styles followed affecting the working of female leaders and their appointment in the organisation were identified in the literature review. Thus, the second hypothesis framed is to test the impact of these organisational factors on the success of female leaders in the FinTech start-ups in the UK.

4.7.3 Hypothesis 3

***H03:** Personal factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK*

***HA3:** Personal factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK*

From the literature review, the researcher further identified that the personality of an individual plays an important role in their work performance. This includes individual factors like competence, personal needs, personality, confidence, courage, creativity, and initiative ability of a person, do have any relationship with the success of the leadership. Therefore, hypothesis 3 was formulated to test the impact of personal factors on the successful leadership of females in the UK's FinTech start-ups.

4.7.4 Hypothesis 4

H04: Technological factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

HA4: Technological factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

With globalisation and technological advancement of economies, there are various changes taking place in the business environment thus it was required to determine the influence of these factors on the working of female leaders. This includes factors like innovation, technical expertise, competence, education and technical training opportunities, and physical infrastructural development through transportation capabilities change in roads, railways, electric supply and improving telephonic lines. Thus, the next hypothesis was to test the relationship between technological factors and female leadership success in Fintech start-ups in the UK.

4.7.5 Hypothesis 5

H05: There is no significant difference in women leadership behaviour with respect to gender working in the FinTech sector of the UK

***HA5:** There is a significant difference in women leadership behaviour with respect to gender working in the FinTech sector of the UK*

To determine the influence of female leadership in the FinTech sector, hypothesis 5 was formulated. This hypothesis helps in determining whether the presence of female leaders in the organisation has influence different from gender working, i.e. the presence of male and female employees. Considering the factors of women effectiveness and shortcomings based on vision, competence, interpersonal skills, optimism, accountability and perspective, this hypothesis is imperative.

4.7.6 Hypothesis 6

***H06:** There is no significant impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK*

***HA6:** There is a significant impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK*

Hypothesis 6 studies the relationship between female leadership effectiveness and organisation performance of the UK's FinTech start-ups. Through the literature review, indicators of effectiveness were identified i.e. working environment and values, coordination and control, values, motivation, external orientation, accountability, capability, motivation, innovation, and inspiration. The results of this hypothesis help in determining whether these features of leadership improve the performance of an organisation or not.

4.8 Description of Variables and response format

4.8.1 The dependent variable

The dependent variables for the current study are the work-related values that are based on the leadership behaviour of female leaders and locus of control that they exercise within the organisation. The dependent variable chosen for the current study includes intrinsic work-

related aspects such as job involvement, pride in work, attitude towards organisational growth, and social status of the job. Other dependent variables include the responsibility to work, internality, domestic responsibility and leadership style (Aycan, 2004, Frederiksen and Halliday, 2015).

4.8.2 The independent variables

Among the independent variable considered in the study includes the gender of the leader. Only female leaders are chosen to highlight the factors that contribute to their leadership in the organisation. The second independent variable considered in the study is age. The leadership behaviour is formed through forces of development of the management ability, and age influence the value and organisational culture. The third independent variable is the level of management. At lower management levels, the female leaders will not be able to influence the job or work environment. Among the primary independent variable in the current study is years of work experience. Years of experience influence the leadership style and frame the working relations between the team and their leader that can be used to influence the working conditions at work (Lathi, 2013, Maule et al., 2015, AAUW, 2016a).

4.9 Justification of the methodology

The rationale described by the philosophies of interpretivism and positivism entails different aspects of the methodology employed in the research. Benbasat, Goldstein, and Mead (1987) in a study on research methodology highlighted that a single approach is not innately better than the other in studying all the parameters under research. The combination of the philosophies helps in absorbing the complexity and richness of all components of research and helps in improving the quality as well. The current study is based on comprehending all factors that are responsible for the creation of successful leadership among the women leader in the

FinTech segment of the UK, and the mix of positivism and interpretivism is best suited for the subject under consideration.

The positivist philosophy in the research suggests taking a structural and controlled approach towards identifying a clear approach for the construction of appropriate hypotheses. The positivism philosophy would also ensure that the researcher remains detached from the observations of the participants. The researcher needs to remain neutral to differentiate between the factors that contribute to the success of women leaders in the UK's FinTech sector and the factors that the researcher perceives is important (Malhotra, 2010).

Further, interpretivism philosophy explains the multiple realities that depend on factors contributing to success. In the current study, the role played by the factors in influencing female leadership and the connection between drivers of successful governance and female front-runners in the industry are the multiple and relative factors that the study has to analyse. Interpretivism philosophy helps in broadening the understanding that each driver depends on multiple realities for their meaning, and each driver is analysed from the view of the social construct in which the study is to take place (Iacobucci, 2014).

4.10 Validity and reliability

The primary aim of the current study is to highlight the valid and accurate representation of factors that are leading to the leadership roles of women in the FinTech sector. Reliability of the study as defined by Bhattacharyya (2010) is the measure of trustworthiness or dependability of the assessments made in the study. The reliability of the study is about the consistency and repeatability of the perspective obtained through the study. Further, (Neuman, 2011) in a study highlighted that the use of analytical programs leads to an accurate analysis of the data. Hence, the current study has used SPSS v21 and meta-analysis v3.0 to assist the precise results of the study.

Additionally, the instruments used in the current study that are, questionnaire, interview, and assessment tool have been chosen precisely. This is to ensure that the results of the study are

uniform in spite of repeated assessment. Provided, that the measures and factors in the study are not altered while repeating the tests. However, a study by Posner (2016) highlighted 100% consistency is not achieved while re-analysing the same study, as there is the possibility of random error or noise that leads to a difference in the results.

Further, for the validity of the current study, the study by Bhattacharyya (2010) highlight that the validity refers to the covenant between the true value and the measurements employed in the study. To maintain the validity of the secondary literature, precautions have been taken to ensure the multiple sources that are used in the study to gather information are up-to-date. The studies used for secondary data collection were taken from studies pointing at women leadership situations in the present times. Further, primary research methods of questionnaire and interview have been employed in the study to obtain first-hand information about women in the FinTech sector of the UK. To validate the results, the results of the primary comparison of the views of respondents to similar previous literature are made.

Further, for maintaining the validity of the questionnaire in the current study, pre-tests have been undertaken. The questionnaire for the study was pilot tested by handing over ten questionnaires. The pilot testing on a small scale was conducted to ensure the feasibility of the study and reduce the errors in the survey and improve on the quality of data obtained by the study (Grim, 2010). Furthermore, the respondents chosen for the current study have been chosen through random sampling methods. By employing random sampling method, the researcher bias is constrained and ways of promoting women leadership are highlighted.

Further, the data obtained for the current study is based on the parameters that are central to women leadership in FinTech segment of the UK. The results of the study cannot be interpolated across the industries without prior testing of the parameters leading to female leadership roles. Finally, throughout the process of the study, the reliability and validity of the data will be maintained thorough evaluation of the data collected in the processes of sampling, a collection of responses, evaluation of missing responses, and minimising the researcher bias.

4.11 Limitations

4.11.1 Limitations in Using qualitative methodology

The current study has employed a qualitative research method for analysis via an interview with managers of the companies. However, Silverman (2010) argued that qualitative methodology occasionally excludes the sensitiveness of the context and focuses more on the experiences and meaning of the study. Further other authors including Tuohy *et al.*, (2013) and Wilson (2014) highlight that the phenomenological approach of the qualitative methodology attempts to interpret and understand the experience of the participants only. Similarly, in a study Cumming (2001) also argued that the experience of the respondents in the qualitative study takes priority over other imperative issues. Further, in the interpretation and analysis of the qualitative data, Darlington and Scott (2003) highlight that refining the results in the qualitative research may pose a limitation as developing theories from the existing literature is difficult.

4.11.2 Limitations in Using quantitative methodology

The quantitative approach presents a limitation to the study as suggested by Bouwer et al. (2015) the quantitative methodology fails to ascertain the explanations behind the responses of the participants. The authors highlighted that the quantitative analysis of the response is suggestive of the variance that exists in the phenomenon under study. However, the quantitative method does not point out the context of the variance observed in the study. Further, a study by Blaikie (2007) highlights that the quantitative method does not suggest how the respondent interprets reality through their actions. In the current study, the quantitative method will highlight the factors that contribute to women leadership roles. However, the quantitative methods do not provide the clarification of the conditions that lead the factors to contribute to the women leadership. The lack of deeper information poses a limitation to the quantitative methodology of the study. Further, the limitation of the quantitative study has been

pointed out by Hammersley (2007) in a study. The study states that the quantitative approach takes into account the problem in a specific period. It does not point out to the unresolved problems that can arise before or after the particular period of study.

4.12 Conclusion

The research methodology has been designed in the progression of adaptability of concepts central to study using a variety of context. Research design along with qualitative and quantitative methods using both the primary and secondary data has been described in the section to ensure the formulation of an effective methodology. Additionally, the research approaches and various philosophies are used to explore the research objectives of the current study.

Chapter: 5 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

5.0 Introduction to the chapter

In the present chapter, the researcher conducted data analysis to evaluate the growth phenomenon of female leadership within FinTech companies in the UK's financial sector. Besides, the researcher also had to identify the factors that lead to successful female leaders among women who work in the Financial Technology sector of the UK and to determine the role played by each influencing factors in achieving successful leadership behaviour among women leaders in the UK's FinTech sector. For this, the researcher has presented a detailed analysis of the primary data collected from the questionnaire survey and the interview, and secondary data collected from other previous research studies. The secondary studies are used to support the analysis of the primary data and helped the researcher in answering the research questions of the current study.

In addition to this, the researcher used both qualitative and quantitative approach under the primary study. Under the quantitative approach, the researcher surveyed 100 respondents (20 employees each from FinTech Company based in London) through a close close-ended questionnaire. Under descriptive analysis technique, the data collected from sections A and B pertained to the demographic profile of the employees who participated in the research and their background knowledge about the women's leadership role in the industry. Under inferential analysis, the data collected from the remaining sections of the quantitative questionnaire was used to understand the effectiveness, shortcomings and future outlook of women leaders. Further, the data was also used to analyse the behaviour required for the effective leadership role by the women leaders of FinTech companies in the UK. Additionally, to find out the critical factors that could affect the leadership performance of the future women leaders of FinTech companies.

The first section of the analysis will include correlation and regression analysis of the survey data. To determine the critical factors required for successful women leadership in FinTech companies in the UK, the factors under three categories such as social factors, organisational factors, and personal factors, were considered. The independent variables and effectiveness parameters required for leadership role were considered as the dependent variable. These variables were subjected to a correlation test to check the association between the variable, and regression analysis this was to understand the relationship between the variables.

To determine the factors impacting the leadership role and the performance of the organisation two parameters are required. They are effective and shortcomings of the women leaders. The same two factors were used for correlation and regression tests. In the conceptual framework, the relationship between social, individual, organisational and technical factors, and leadership success of females were identified. The main problem formulated based on the conceptual framework was to identify the extent to which these factors affect the success of female leadership. According to many researchers correlation and regression tests are the most efficient way to identify the impact of the independent variable (s) on the dependent variable (Cho, 1972; Mistry & Bora, 2019; Setyaningsih, 2017). In the case of the present research, the main independent variables identified are the social, individual, organisational and technological factors, whereas the dependent variable is female leadership success in FinTech start-ups. Therefore, the correlation and regression tests were found most apt for this research.

Further, to discover the leadership behaviour required for the effective leadership role, the factors under the behaviour section were analysed using the cross-tabulation method concerning gender.

In the last stage, for the qualitative approach, data were gathered through interviews from one manager of each selected 5 companies in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK. The researcher presented the qualitative study that captured the responses of the managers, along with the supporting secondary findings from other research studies. A set of open open-ended questions was posed to the interviewees to determine the factors that led to the success of women leaders in the industry. Lastly, the summary was presented describing the data analysis process in brief

and key findings from the insights of both, the quantitative, and the qualitative research approach.

5.1 Descriptive Statistics

5.1.1 Qualitative analysis

The study aims to understand the influence of different factors on female leadership, in the UK's FinTech sector. For this purpose, the researcher used a qualitative research approach to draw the overall comprehensibility and perception entailing the linkage between successful leadership and women leaders. The researcher also conducted interviews with 5 managers in the FinTech sector of the UK (London area). The interviews were conducted through an open-ended questionnaire consisting of four sections. The first section captured the demographic profile of the respondents. The next section captured insights about the interviewees' perception of the leadership strategies, subsequent sections captured the factors that lead to success in the FinTech sector. Finally, the questionnaire highlighted the challenges faced in the leadership position.

5.1.1.1 Department and location

This section presents a demographic and thematic analysis for the interviews conducted with managers from five companies in the FinTech sector of the UK (London area). The thematic analysis included three themes which involved a) a discussion about the managers' opinion on perception of leadership strategies, b) factors leading to success in industry and c) challenges faced in the leadership position. The purpose of the qualitative study is to understand 1) the perception of women in the leadership position about the organisation, and 2) their strategies to carry out their core responsibilities. The details of the interviewees are presented below in table 5-1:-

Table 5-1: Interviewee profile (Researcher)

Sr. No.	Manager Code	Department of the Manager	Place
1	A	R &D	Greenwich, London
2	E	Accounting	Ealing, Hammersmith and Fulham, London
3	C	Banking	Islington, London
4	B	R & D	Wandsworth, London
5	D	Accounting	Southwark, London

5.1.1.2 Marital status

Following table 5-2 and figure 5-1 shows the marital status of all five target respondents.

Table 5-2: Marital status of interviewees (Researcher)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Marital Status	Married	2	40.0	40.0	40.0
	Single	2	40.0	40.0	80.0
	Widow	1	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	5	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5-1: Marital status of interviewees (Researcher)

The table 5-2 and the figure 5-1 above represent the information of 5 managers that were interviewed as per the objective of the study. The interviewees were asked about their marital status. In this context, the table and the figure clearly indicates that 40% interviewees were married, 40% were single and 20% were widowed. Therefore, most of the interviewees were either single or married.

5.1.1.3 Stay with family

Following table 5-3 and figure 5-2 show if the target interviewees stay with their family or not.

Table 5-3: Stay with family (Researcher)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Do you stay with your family?	Yes	3	60.0	60.0	60.0
	No	2	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	5	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5-2: Stay with Family (Researcher)

The interviewees were asked whether they stay with their family. In this regard, the above figure 5-2 and table 5-3 clearly indicate that 60% of interviewees were staying with their families whereas 40% of interviewees were staying unaccompanied. Therefore, most of the respondents were staying with their family.

5.1.1.4 No. of dependents in the family

Following table 5-4 and figure 5-3 shows the number dependents the family of target respondents.

Table 5-4: No. of dependents in the family (Researcher)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Dependents in the family	Less than 3	3	60.0	60.0	60.0
	Greater than 3	2	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	5	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5-3: No. of dependents in the family (Researcher)

Subsequently, the interviewees were asked about the number of dependents in the family. In this regard, 60% stated that there are less than three dependents in the family whereas about 40% stated that there are greater than three dependents in their family. Therefore, most of the interviewees had less than three dependents in their family.

5.1.2 Quantitative analysis

To understand the demographic details of the respondents (employees), who are working at different FinTech companies based in London, and to check their understanding about the status of women's leadership in those organisations, the categorical data collected from the respondents are presented using descriptive analysis. Further, these categorical values are plotted in a pie chart for a better understanding. In addition to that through this descriptive analysis of 100 profiles, the researcher establishes how these profiles are qualified for the present study.

Demographics in research are characteristics of a population involved in the research study, such as age, gender, profession, income level, education, etc., are expressed statistically. The study of demographics is important as it provides insights into the nature of the population and how it reacts to the other parameters in the study.

5.1.2.1 Gender

Following table 5-5 and figure 5-4 show the gender of the target respondents

Table 5-5: Gender composition of survey respondents (Researcher)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	54	54.0	54.0	54.0
	Female	46	46.0	46.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5-4: Gender composition of survey respondents (Researcher)

From the above table 5-5 and pie-chart 5-4, the statistics clearly indicate that out of 100 respondents, 54% are males and the rest of them are females. Therefore, it can be said that the sample was biased towards males.

5.1.2.2 Age

Following table 5-6 and figure 5-5 show the age of the target respondents

Table 5-6: Age of survey respondents (Researcher)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Age	21-30 Years	37	37.0	37.0	37.0
	31-40 years	40	40.0	40.0	77.0
	41-50 years	19	19.0	19.0	96.0
	Above 50 years	4	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5-5: Age Distribution of survey respondents (Researcher)

From the above table 5-6 and pie chart 5-5, it is evident that about 40% of respondents were from the age group of 31-40 years. This was followed by 37% of respondents who were from the age group of 21-30 years. That means the age of 77% of the respondents comes in the category of 20 to 40 years and they could be the future leaders in the industry. So, this category of the population is expected to provide the relevant data, which is required to determine the study objective.

5.1.2.3 Association with the present company

Following table 5-7 and figure 5-6 show association of the target respondents with the current companies, i.e.: the number of years worked for the FinTech organisation

Table 5-7: Association with present company (Researcher)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Association with the company	Less than 5 years	12	12.0	12.0	12.0
	5-10 years	38	38.0	38.0	50.0
	10-15 years	26	26.0	26.0	76.0
	15-20 years	14	14.0	14.0	90.0
	More than 20 years	10	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5-6: Association with the company (Researcher)

The statistics in figure 5-6 above indicates that 38% of the employees were associated with the current organisation since 5-10 years. In addition to this, about 26% of the employees were associated with the current organisation since 10-15 years. Therefore, the majority of the young talents are associated with their present organisation for a while and so they could be well aware of the culture and value of the organisation. Since these attributes could be the influencing factors and deciding factors for the behaviour required for the successful leadership, the researcher could conclude that the relevant information is being collected due to a strong association with the organisation.

From the demographic analysis, it is evident that there was not much difference in the number of male and female respondents. Also, most of the respondents were from the age group of 21-40 years and were associated with the organisation since 5-15 years. Overall, it's evident that respondents are middle-aged and well associated with the working organisation. The following section will test the knowledge of the employees, with respect to different attributes required for the women leadership in an organisation.

5.1.3 Qualitative analysis

5.1.4 Perception of Leadership Strategies

The interviewees were asked about the different leadership strategies adopted by men and women. In this regard, the interviewees were questioned about the management, gender neutrality in the organisations, leadership role played by women, and gender-specific leadership benefits. In addition to this, the interviewees were asked about the obstacles they faced and their perspective on the qualities of a good leader.

5.1.4.1 Management of FinTech Company

On being asked about the differentiating traits of leadership in FinTech companies as compared to other sectors, Interviewee 'E' was of the view that the financial sector is driven by the agenda of innovation. Therefore, the main objective of the leaders is to navigate to a new and competitive environment. In addition to this, the leaders should be able to build a strong and competitive team who can align with the growth of new business strategies. To this interviewee, 'A' added that technological development has experienced growth of big data analytics, artificial intelligence and cloud computing that has delivered increasing speed in business operations. Big data, cloud technology, and artificial intelligence are evolving with seemingly ever-increasing speed. Financial services companies must adapt and transform their business models to take advantage of the opportunities they bring. The leaders should play a significant role in adapting and transforming the business models that can offer advantages of the opportunities.

Further, interviewee 'D' articulated that the leadership role should invite transparency in the new business models. In addition to this, interviewee 'D' reported that 'FinTech is a specialised banking segment and along with new ideas there is risk associated with the choices as well. Leading a FinTech company requires keeping oneself updated of various changes in the technological and financial sphere, it requires survival quality'. Interviewee 'C' was of the

view that FinTech Company needs to add value for its existing customers as they depend on different needs on which FinTech encompasses all the products of banking.

Interviewee 'B' stated that the FinTech sector is formed by combining the features of banking and IT industry. The leaders have to manage the ethical and legal risks involved in banking transactions. In addition to this, they have a fast-paced environment demanded by the IT industry. Further, the interviewee 'A' has reported that *'such a competitive industry demands bureaucratic leaders who are strongly committed to achieving the organisational goals and can clearly understand the priorities attached to the different task.'*

5.1.5 Gender neutrality in leadership

There were mixed reviews regarding the issue of gender neutrality in leadership in the FinTech sector. Gender neutrality is the concept of not discriminating in the roles of an employee based on their gender or sex (Anthony, 2008). It is similar to the concept of gender equality, which in the context of this study, in the literature review, gender equality had been identified as a critical component of organisational success. The primary difference between gender neutrality and equality is that the former is majorly used to refer to people in general, and not society male and female gender in any context (Doyle, 1998). Therefore, it was important to understand the leaders' perspective on the presence of gender equality and how FinTech organisations convey gender neutrality in their workplace. Interviewee 'A' was of the view that there is significant drop regarding leadership being considered as a gender issue in the organisations as there is a different kind of leadership behaviours that apply to men and women. The interviewee also reported a sharp rise in the number of women holding a leadership position in their organisation. The organisations have started being viewed as gender-neutral. Further, on being asked about the opportunities that have helped women leaders to reach to the top, Interviewee 'A' reported that having a gender-neutral organisation is helpful for leaders, they also added that "it is good to share the vision that gender and leadership skill are exclusive characteristics". It has also helped them set trends and open doors for female managers to advance into leadership roles. It ensures to set industry trends and set a benchmark in diversity

in the leadership of different sections of the economy. Gender-neutral organisations build more confidence and trust among the employees.

Interviewee 'B' thought that women have proved that they have an equal ability to achieve the success goals for the organisation. The leadership role assigned to the women has fetched long term impact to enact them to perform as leaders. She reported that her organisation promotes equality in terms of appointing women as leaders in their organisation. Further on being asked about the opportunities that have helped the leaders to rise to the top, interviewee 'B' thought that developing a gender-neutral organisation is exemplary which is essential for FinTech sector to observe the change and evolution. Maintaining gender neutrality in firms leads to encouragement of responsibilities at the workplace since it conveys to the employees that the leaders do not discriminate between male and female employees when referring to any task. Thus, the organisations who share the vision of gender equality focus upon the core skill and personality development to lead ahead. The gender neutrality vision helps the leaders to build new opportunities and enable the organisation to undertake greater risk that is capable of entrusting new leadership positions.

However, Interviewee 'C's response was somewhat different. She was of the view that leadership positions in their organisation are more biased towards males. Few females are appointed at the leadership position. But, the interviewee agreed with that gender diversity is more in FinTech than in the other sectors. For this purpose, the women employment trends from the base level should be high enough to promote more women at leadership positions.

In this regard, the interviewee 'D' believed that businesses which are led by women have enabled long term economic gains for the firms. To pave the path for female leadership, inequality should be addressed at the very beginning at the executive level in the firms. For this purpose, the gender parity needs to be addressed to the root level to ensure FinTech as well as other sectors to get more female leaders.

Interviewee 'E' strongly disagreed with the view that leadership is neutral in their organisation. The interviewee revealed that even though the representation of female leaders is more in the

FinTech sector, there is still gender inequality when it comes to holding the leadership position. Female leadership can provide the firms with long-time growth but it is still limited by unequal pay standard. The opportunities that exist in the form of gender-neutral hiring and exclusion of the female employees can help in addressing the gender gap.

5.1.6 Women's Success in Leadership Roles

On being asked about the shift in women's characteristics in the leadership role, interviewee 'A' believed that there is a requirement for a shift in women's outlook towards the leadership, to able to stand with men they need to develop FinTech specific skills. Traditional characteristics that have enabled them to succeed as leaders have started changing in the UK. As the FinTech sector needs new talent, software development skills, coding as well as financial management. In a nutshell, Women need to develop analytical and strategic skills.

Interviewee 'E' believed that women are still underrepresented in terms of handling leadership responsibilities as compared to their male counterparts. The interviewee also reported that there exist incongruity between male and female leadership behaviour that acts as a hurdle in leadership and result in negative performance appraisals and different standards as compared to male. This, according to the interviewee, mainly occurs due to their lack of participation in STEM education which is essential to gain technical skills. The interviewee also opined that possessing a background of STEM education and technical skills specific to the FinTech sector increases the chances of the organisation's confidence that she is also capable of rational decision-making necessary for the firm's success, as the necessary knowledge related to technical aspects is not missing.

Further, interviewee 'E' believed that the way to lead an organisation depends on the individual's characteristics rather than the gender being considered as the function of leadership. Many a time, men and women possess different leadership characteristics which are associated with gender. The leaders are influenced by the social construction of leadership styles.

Interviewee 'D' had a different perspective in this regard; that the women bring in more diverse strength and innovation into leadership roles. The women's roles have transformed the traditional leadership styles to display improved leadership by building large alignment and strategic vision and mission. Women have displayed optimistic behaviour by building strong effective teams towards a growth path of a successful future.

Interviewee 'B' was of the view that collaboration of personal characteristic with leadership has to start from very early stage of education like A levels. Although there are more female students opting for STEM (science, technology, engineering, and maths) subjects, the inclusion of strategic studies can ensure that female leadership is a movement and not a gesture.

Interviewee 'C' holds a different perspective in the context of the change of women characteristics that succeed in the leadership roles. The interviewee stated that, *"I think that there is no requirement to change personal characteristic of women to ensure that they succeed in leadership roles. They are as capable as their male counterparts to do so if they are provided with the same opportunities. The environment that we inhabit, shapes who we are, if we can ensure gender inclusion in the talent base, especially at the very early stage of A levels, we would see more women leaders."*

5.1.7 Benefits of women leadership

On being asked about the benefits in the context of women leadership, Interviewee 'A' was of the view that there are no such gender-specific benefits. The leadership style is dependent on one's attitude and behaviour. Many of the people often point out that the male and female possess different leadership styles. The women leadership is more concentrated towards coaching and being compassionate.

Interviewee 'B' was of the view that more gender-specific benefits are perceived than usual. The responses of male and female leaders have different effects on subordinate outcomes. The leadership has been dependent on context.

Interviewee 'D' believed that female leaders are more compassionate towards employees and organisations which helps them to lead them in a much better way.

Interviewee 'C' thought that women can perform in a better way as leaders because women can balance work and life in a better way. This enables them to manage innovative skills in handling various situations at a particular point in time.

Interviewee 'E' also thought that apart from being more compassionate, female leaders are more inclined towards innovation which is very beneficial for industries like FinTech.

5.1.8 Tools to increase Women Leadership

Following this, the respondents were also asked about the best tools that can increase the number of women holding leadership positions. In this regard, interviewee 'A' and 'B' strongly agreed that mentoring can help in improving the number of women in leadership positions. Interviewee 'A' stated that *“effective mentoring can help women compete in their career path. Mentoring can assist women in setting their career goals and can help them in achieving those goals”*. The interviewee believed that mentoring can help women in developing a more collaborative and creative approach towards decision making, in turn, boosting their self-confidence. Effective mentoring can help women in generating new perspectives on the given set of problems.

Interviewee 'C' strongly disagreed with the opinion that quotas act as a good tool to increase women in leadership. She believed that allocating quotas for leadership position undervalues the skills and abilities of the female leader. This can even reduce the confidence of women. She stated that *“Instead of allocating quotas, women should be trained through discussions about gender neutrality. Rather, women should be motivated to work hard, be participative and collaborative. This will boost leadership skills among women and will help them in making themselves self-reliant.”* She also added that quotas were meant for the part of the society who were discriminated due to their caste, colour, and creed. Today, the times have changed and

society thinks above a person's colour or background, it is more about what you can bring on the table to move the organisation further.

Interviewees 'D' and 'E' believed that both mentoring and general discussions can act as the best tools to increase the women at the leadership position. Interviewee 'D' was of the view that frequent debates and discussions within the organisations can encourage women to enhance their skills and knowledge. General discussions not only build transparency but, also develop community involvement which can assist women to take part in the organisation. Moreover, the organisations must also undertake regular interactive sessions to educate and impart technical skills in women employees, particularly those lacking STEM background. This according to them gives the employees the necessary exposure to understand every aspect of the FinTech business as they climb up the hierarchical ladder.

Further, both interviewee 'B' and 'C' did not favour quotas. They were of the view that quotas are not necessary to increase the number of women engagement. Interviewee 'C' stated, *"I don't think allocating quotas is the solution for the problem, rather the organisations should aim at achieving a balance between men and women"*. The women should be positioned at those spheres where men dominate the industry. But, this should be achieved through their capabilities and abilities. However, interviewee 'E' had a different opinion in this context. The interviewee was of the view that quotas are allocated for those individuals who are placed backwards since centuries. This is done to ensure the balance among the positions. Gender quotas also ensure a certain number of positions for women. Gender quotas have many advantages as positive discrimination can only bring equality in society. Therefore, organisations must employ some women in their management team.

Interviewee 'D' was neutral towards the view of allocating quotas for women. Interviewee 'D' reported that *"Quotas can act as a tool to improve the current situation existing in society. However, the quotas are not a cure to the problem. Quotas should not be seen as a threat to society, instead, it should be seen as a mode to provide equal opportunities for women. Women are equally skilled and can be placed at the board of directors in the companies."*

Following this, the interviewees were asked about the aspects that have advanced their career. In this regard, interviewee 'B' explained that she focuses on the mistakes committed by her and examines the failures. Following this, she tries to meet her targets and standards. Further, she stated that women need to participate in every event, debates, and discussions that take place in the organisation. Without the active participation of women and the incorporation of women's perspective at all three levels of decision-making, the goals of equality, development, and peace cannot be achieved.

Interviewee 'A' was of the view that the most important aspect that helped him in the advancement of the career is how he understood the importance of achieving the corporate objectives. The interviewee was of the view that the objectives of the organisation can only be met by building up a dedicated workforce who are committed to achieving the goal of the organisation.

Further, the interviewees were also asked about the obstacles faced by the interviewees in their career. In this regard, interviewee 'B' was of the view that being women, she has always faced a struggle of maintaining a work-life balance. However, one of the major obstacles faced by her is a lack of family support. She stated *"my family always preferred teaching job for me. They thought that being a woman, I should focus on my family responsibilities"*.

To this, interviewee 'E' added that *"there are some minor obstacles such as a bad superior that I face in everyday work-life. There is a lack of coordination between us and that, in turn, creates a huge communication gap"*. In addition to this, interviewee 'E' thought that the speed bump in his career was a switch from the IT industry to the FinTech sector that offered multiple opportunities for growth.

For Interviewee 'D', there were no obstacles and the interviewee attached no value to it. However, many speed bumps were experienced in the form of building up of good networking. The interviewee was of the view that there is strong coordination between the team members and the superiors. In addition to this, the team constantly supports the interviewee and play a major role in influencing her career success.

However, interviewee 'A' revealed that the most powerful aspect in their career was her family who had constantly supported her at every stage of the career. The interviewee stated that *“My Family has always been my strongest support, they always motivated me to work hard. They boosted my confidence and encouraged me to focus on my career.”*

Interviewee 'C' thought that the most effective speed bumps in my career are my skills and talent. She was of the view that she possesses all the qualities of a leader, stating that *“My effective communication and power to make effective decisions in any situation have helped me to reach till this position.”*

5.1.9 Qualities and characteristics of a good leader

Following this, the interviewees were asked about the most important qualities and characteristics of a good leader. In this regard, interviewee 'B' believed that the most important quality of leaders is to have impact and influence on the workforce. The leader should have commanding authority and must possess the power to influence the team members. In addition to this, the leader should be able to guide the team in the right direction.

Interviewee 'D' thought that leaders in an organisation should possess the goal of achieving long term objectives of the organisation. The leader should develop a vision for the organisation. In addition to this, the leader should set targets and goals for their team members.

Interviewee 'C' was of the view that the leader should be able to motivate the employees to work hard and help them in framing long term vision for the organisation. In addition to this, the leader should give priority to the organisational goals rather than personal goals. The leader should be confident to ensure that the directions are followed by all the team members.

Innovation is the main instrument which can distinguish between a leader and the follower, especially in the FinTech sector. This was the view of interviewee 'D' who thought that innovation, creativity, and honesty can create better leaders for the future. In addition to this,

the interviewee stated that leaders can succeed only if they stick to their core values and beliefs of the organisation.

Interviewee 'A' reported that *“good leaders have the vision and have the ability to show the right direction to their team. They guide their team to the path of achieving success. For this purpose, the leader should possess good communication skills and should act reasonably with all the employees, in turn, ensuring transparency in the organisation. They take the responsibility of displaying a big picture of future expectations.”*

Following this, the respondents were asked about their experience of gender bias in their way to the career development of the organisation. To this interviewee, 'A', 'B' and 'E' stated that they had never faced any kind of gender bias in their way to career development. However, Interviewee 'C' stated that they have often observed that female employees are given more flexibility than males. To this, interviewee 'D' was of the view that it is often perceived that women are not talented to handle the leadership position. They lack confidence and are unable to participate in the team. Further, the interviewee stated that this type of mindset has been developed and this is the main reason behind the fact that few women are placed at leadership positions as compared to males.

5.1.10 Factors leading to Success in the Industry

Following this, the interviewees were asked about the factors that influence women's rise to the leadership position. In this regard, interviewee 'A' believed that talent concerning the prevailing technology can influence women's rise to the leadership position. Contextual knowledge is the key to succeed in any industry and female employees with a high knowledge base of industry and talent will surely rise to the leadership position.

On the other hand, Interviewee 'B' was of the view that the rise of women to leadership roles has acted as a glass ceiling in a particular organisation. Multiple restrictions faced by women employee while disposing of her duties enhance the individualistic struggle that she undergoes

and help her in developing better leadership development. In addition to this, the interviewee was of the view that his organisation is among those few that do not align with the existing glass ceiling. The presence of such a phenomenon has always ensured to take extra bits of effort to ensure that the leadership is inclusive. Interviewee 'A' agreed that societal standards, expectations, and customs towards the organisations and individuals can help women in achieving success at the workplace.

The respondents were also asked about the situations in which the success generating factors have helped them in achieving success. Interviewee 'A' was of the view that there are several situations where contextual knowledge and know-how of the prevailing technology has helped in the success. The technological era that exists in the current world ought to know about the users of AI that can assist in predicting the behaviour of the consumer and big data in a way that they can design more relatable FinTech products. These technological developments have helped the interviewee in growing the customer base and choosing the customers.

Following this, the respondents were asked whether gender is a relevant factor to impart professional skills when considering the leadership of the managers. To this, interviewee 'D' thought that although professional skills impact the leadership, the reason behind choosing a leader rests upon the culture of the organisation. According to the interviewee, 'D' gender becomes relevant when it is thought that emotional intelligence, and ability to view the things in broader terms are considered important for leadership. However, interviewee E believed that element of skills is the most relevant factor to be considered while choosing a leader for an organisation. According to him, the organisations must give more importance to the skills and competencies within an individual while looking for an innovative leader. This will ensure high performance and efficiency of the organisation soon.

In this regard, Interviewee 'A' was of the view that gender is an irrelevant factor in deciding about leadership. The changes come in the form of equal opportunity and professional skills that are enough to guide more female leaders to success. While interviewee 'B' believed that the presence of huge gender disparity between male and female in leadership is a reality. In addition to this, the interviewee was of the view that women face obstacles other than

professional skills that have long stood in the path of women leadership success. *“There is a deep social and cultural change that is required to provide women with equal opportunity in the first place. I think those women who reach the top position in spite of such difficulties are liable for some preferential treatment”*.

Further, the respondents were asked about the common leadership styles adopted by the women. In this regard, Interviewee ‘C’ was of the view that women in the leadership position in several institutions especially in the FinTech sector are now recognising women’s growing influence and prosperity in leadership, it is becoming a trend. The organisations are aligned to use diversity in leadership in the future as well. In addition to this, the interviewee was of the view that it is the time for women leaders to become a phenomenon across different industries.

Regarding the leadership style, interviewee ‘B’ thought women have started taking up subjects such as mathematics, computer science, and analytics, this is an indication that the future of women leaders is brighter. In addition to this, women recognise their promotional and leadership roles, this would facilitate the organisations to be informed of their priorities and goals. There is healthy talent in the pipeline that is looking for opportunity. Equality is a boost that female leadership needs to continue growing in the future.

5.1.11 Challenges faced in a leadership position

Following this, the respondents were asked about the challenges faced by the women leaders in the FinTech companies in the UK, and the reasons for their under- representation. In this regard, Interviewee ‘D’ thought that the corporate world has been built on the culture of long working hours that are self-imposed on employees as a result of peer pressure. *“Flexible working arrangements are also not welcome, and I am talking about this factor for either gender. With the social mindset and need for women to play larger roles in family life as well women often get lesser chance to succeed and this lead to their underrepresentation in higher management”*.

Interviewee 'E' thought that women are under-represented in the senior management in FinTech companies of the UK. The interviewee had never noticed any women being registered to coordinate for seminars and meetings for different firms in FinTech. Thus, was of the view that women are fewer in comparison to men in the industry.

Interviewee 'B' also thought that women have not been given an equal position in the senior management of FinTech companies in the UK as there are more male senior partners in the industry. Interviewee 'C' strongly agreed with the view that women are under-represented in the higher leadership role. Most of the women are in administrative jobs and not at senior level due to limited opportunities are given to them at the executive role. There exists disparity in gender balance in an organisation that translates to the under-representation of women in higher management.

Interviewee 'A' also rationalised that women are under-represented in senior management as women are seldom given opportunities and their full potential is rarely utilised.

5.1.12 Suggestions to improve leadership

Interviewee 'D' believed that to improve the position of women leadership, it is necessary to remove society and structural barriers. In addition to this, the policies that prevent sexual discrimination in workplaces and career path of women need to be addressed. Female leadership should not intimidate their colleagues and only an open organisation can enable women to achieve leadership positions. Furthermore, the interviewee also opined that educational institutions should do more to encourage women's participation in STEM education, as it enhances their chances of gaining more technical skills that are necessary to attain the leadership position. According to him, this starts at the grassroots level, i.e. home and education.

Interviewee 'E' thought that the most influential way to increase women representation in a leadership role is in ensuring their inclination towards information technology and new-age

developments, such as usage of AI and big data. In addition to this, the interviewee thought that women are much more capable of balancing their work and life. They only need opportunity which can motivate them to achieve more and be successful in FinTech leadership. Gender stereotypes often hurt the career development for both men and women. To make women rise to leadership, organisations need to address stereotypes and prejudice. The organisational policies should be developed to address the traditional gender roles and to cater to the expectation of women seeking a higher management role.

Interviewee 'B' was of the view that female students should take up extensive STEM studies like their male counterparts. The female employees should be able to take up the required motivation that can enable them to take new challenges.

Interviewee 'C' thought that males and females should be given equal opportunities at the workplace and there should be no discrimination in pay scale. There should be an industry-standard irrespective of gender. In addition to this women should also be provided with the training and assistance to acquire the technological and infrastructural skills that can help them to reach a leadership position.

Interviewee 'A' felt that the female population need a more infrastructural support system that is inclined to provide technological proficiency. Such opportunities are required to mould the female leadership. In addition to this, there is a necessity to recognise gender imposed restrictions and design gender gender-sensitive policy in the industry

5.1.13 Preference for Male Leadership

Interviewee 'E' disagreed with the opinion that male leaders are preferred over female leadership as the team members had never expressed any opinion to be led by the male leaders. There is no gender disparity contextualised in leadership.

Interviewee 'B' believed that men are aggressive and dominant, this instance of preferential male leadership occurred in a team conflict-handling process. The male leaders should ensure that gender norm stereotypes do not come in the way of leadership positions. The organisations should adopt several measures to make leadership position conducive to women's rise in an organisation. Addressing gender equality in both payment and promotion are contributions that the industry can provide to promote female leadership. If the organisations align their internal culture to reduce social and cultural barricade, it will have a positive impact on the acceptance of more women in the industry in leadership roles.

Interviewee 'D' accepted that males domination exists in technical skills related job. According to the interviewee, it is common knowledge that more males pursue STEM education than females. This ultimately affects females' chance of climbing up the corporate ladder, as they lack the same level of technical expertise as males. However, according to the interviewee, the trend was slowly changing as an increasing number of women are pursuing technical studies and globalisation is bringing about an influx of technically competent women in the FinTech sector from different countries.

Interviewee 'C' stated that organisational settings in which women perform do not present any obstruction to the leadership process. A distribution of opportunity alongside power in the industry is required. Women often do not reach their possible success due to prejudiced organisational policies.

Interviewee 'A' was unable to decide about the team members preference for working under a male or female leader. However, no such instances have been observed by the team members in which they have preferred to work under male leadership.

Thus, it can be asserted that the major words asserted by respondents include leadership, women, gender, agree and strongly. These words indicate that the major relation was identified in leadership with that of women. Thus the study surrounds to identify factors underlying effectiveness and challenges to this theme. Table 5-8 shows the most used words in the interviews.

Table 5-8: Most frequently used words in the interview (Researcher)

Word	Length	Count	Weighted Percentage (%)
Leadership	10	201	3.98
Women	5	149	2.95
Agree	5	109	2.16
Think	5	98	1.94
Strongly	8	93	1.84
Disagree	8	88	1.74
Gender	6	74	1.47
Female	6	68	1.35
Leader	6	56	1.11
Leaders	7	53	1.05
FinTech	7	51	1.01
Position	8	48	0.95
Undecided	9	35	0.69
Male	4	34	0.67
Team	4	29	0.57
Career	6	28	0.55
Factors	7	28	0.55
Organisation	12	26	0.52
Question	8	26	0.52

Organisations	13	25	0.5
Success	7	25	0.5
Well	4	25	0.5
Yes	3	25	0.5
Rise	4	24	0.48
Roles	5	23	0.46
Opportunities	13	22	0.44
Industry	8	21	0.42
Helped	6	20	0.4
Positions	9	20	0.4

5.1.14 Summary

The growth of the FinTech sector in the UK has delivered benefits to a pool of trained professionals. Apart from effective business operations and technological innovation, this growth is supported by achieving expertise in leadership. The FinTech sector has also transformed in terms of gender diversity thereby increasing the role of women. The sector has offered a fair representation of female talent, in turn, promoting gender equality in the industry. The government has also adopted several measures to promote equal representation of social and political spheres. However, women are often underrepresented in the leadership roles, with only 12% representation in the executive roles. Thus, it is important to understand the factors that help in successful leadership amongst women. In this regard, the present study aims to evaluate the growing phenomenon of female leadership within FinTech companies in the UK's financial sector. For this, the researcher collected primary data using qualitative and quantitative approach. Under the quantitative approach, the researcher surveyed 100

respondents (20 employees each from FinTech companies based in London) through a close-ended questionnaire.

The data collected were entered into MS Excel and imported into SPSS for further analysis. This data was analysed using frequency distribution, crosstab analysis, correlation, and regression. From the qualitative analysis, the finding of the study indicates that there are factors that lead to successful female leaders among women working in the Financial Technology sector of the UK. Though there were other factors, the '**Social Factor**' concerning to its impact in achieving successful leadership by women leaders in the FinTech sector is positive with '*Existence of phenomenon like a glass ceiling*'. That means the social barrier created by the organisations, especially for women employees, could be a blockade for the efficient female employees.

The 'Organisational Factor' that could impact in achieving successful leadership by women leaders in the FinTech sector is positive with 'Organisations have their particular work environment with its values, which is a legacy of past leaders, as well as current leadership'. The women leader, who can follow up and adapt easily with the organisational culture and values, could easily exhibit effective and efficient leadership in the organisation.

The 'Personal Factor' that could impact in achieving successful leadership by women leaders in the FinTech sector is positive with 'Creativity and initiative ability of a leader'. The women leader, who can take up initiatives and responsibilities and who have a creative mindset to resolve problems, could end up in management role for a successful career in their life.

Further, from crosstab analysis, it was evident that there is a significance between the effective leadership behaviour and the gender for the women leaders of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK. Among all the leadership behaviour, 'Individualistic Decision Making' is the most significant behaviour required for effective leadership role concerning gender.

Lastly, the finding of the study indicates that there is a significant impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK. The effectiveness parameters that could result in a significant impact on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector is positive with 'She exhibits frequent absence and lack of involvement during critical

junctures'. The shortcomings of women leaders that could result in a significant impact on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector is positive with 'She has limiting abilities to influence, adapt to the culture, and "fit in" organisationally and impersonally'.

The qualitative analysis captured insights from 5 managers working in the FinTech sector in the UK (London). The survey captured insights from the interviewees in the context of the leadership strategies and factors that can lead to success in the FinTech sector. Further, the survey also analysed the challenges faced by women in the FinTech sector. The findings highlight that the FinTech sector is driven by innovation and technological development.

In the context of gender neutrality, most of the interviewees said that the FinTech sector has experienced a sharp rise in the number of women holding leadership positions. In addition to this, the interviewees reported that their organisation was gender-neutral. Further, some interviewees were of the view that women are better leaders as they are capable of handling multiple tasks at the same point of time. They thought that business led by women can fetch long term economic gains to the firms.

In the context of women's success in leadership roles, most of the interviewees thought that leadership depends on individual's characteristics whereas some of them thought that there still exist incongruity between male and female leadership behaviour that acts as a hurdle in leadership.

In terms of the benefits of women leadership, most of the interviewees thought that women are more compassionate and inclined towards achieving organisational goals. Further, the interviewees highlighted that effective mentorship and general discussions can boost confidence among women, in turn, helping them to act as better leaders. They were of the view that allocating quotas harm competitive behaviour will discourage women to enhance their capabilities. Therefore, organisations should promote healthy competition among males and females.

Lastly, the interviewees highlighted the challenges faced by women in the leadership position. In this regard, most of the interviewees were of the view that women are supported by their families to achieve their career goals. To improve women leadership, it is necessary to remove society and structural barriers. The women should be encouraged to participate in all matters of the organisation.

5.2 Quantitative Analysis

The quantitative research approach is a technique that emphasises the objective statement, and aim of the research study through statistical or numerical analysis of data collected from surveys or interview through questionnaires. The researcher's aim to determine the relationship between the dependent variable and independent variable, concerning the research objective, could be done by drawing a logical conclusion based on the facts and data with the help of quantitative research technique. Quantitative research techniques are either descriptive in nature or inferential in nature.

5.2.1 General background

In this section of the analysis, the researcher would try to check the knowledge of employees, involved in the research study, concerning different parameters required for the women leadership in an organisation. The respondents were asked about the presence of women leaders, their effectiveness, leadership functions and leadership competencies possessed by their leaders. These data values would be presented in a pie chart for better visualisation and understanding.

5.2.1.1 Presence of Women leaders in the Organisation

Following table 5-9 and figure 5-8 below show the presence of the women leaders in the chosen FinTech organisations of the UK.

Table 5-9: Presence of female leaders (Researcher)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Does your organisation have women leaders?	Yes	64	64.0	64.0	64.0
	No	28	28.0	28.0	92.0
	Can't say	8	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5-7: Presence of Women Leaders (Researcher)

From the above table 5-9 and figure 5-7, it is evident that about 64% of the employees agreed that women leaders are working in their organisation. On the other hand, 28% of the employees stated that their organisation doesn't have any women leaders. Also, about 8% of respondents did not have any knowledge of the presence of women leaders in their organisation. So, therefore, the researcher could conclude that organisations are supporting and encouraging women leaders for the effective balance in the companies.

5.2.1.2 Effectiveness of Women leaders with respect to Male leaders

Following table 5-10 and 5-8 figure show the effectiveness of women leaders vs. male leaders

Table 5-10: Effectiveness of female leaders with respect to male leaders (Researcher)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Do you think that women leaders are more effective than male leaders?	Yes	66	66.0	66.0	66.0
	No	19	19.0	19.0	85.0
	Can't say	15	15.0	15.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5-8: Effectiveness of women leaders with respect to the male leaders (Researcher)

From the above table and figure, it is evident that about 66% of the respondents were of the view that women leaders are better than or as effective as male leaders. 19% of the employees stated that male leaders are more effective than female leaders. Therefore, it can be said most of the respondents believed that women leaders are equally effective as their male counterpart.

5.2.1.3 Leadership function performed by the leader

Following table 5-11 and figure 5-9 show the leadership function performed by the leader.

Table 5-11: Leadership function performed by the female leader (Researcher)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Which of the following leadership function is performed by your leader?	Developing the vision	24	24.0	24.0	24.0
	Sharing the goals	21	21.0	21.0	45.0
	Gaining support	13	13.0	13.0	58.0
	Delivering success	38	38.0	38.0	96.0
	Others	4	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5-9: Leadership functions performed by the leader (Researcher)

From the above table 5-11 and figure 5-9, it can be inferred that 38% of the respondents mentioned that leaders in their organisation play a major role in delivering success for the organisation. Another 24% of them responded that developing the vision, also, play a major

role in their leaders, and 21% of them mentioned sharing team or organisation goal with the colleagues are the leadership functions adopted by their leaders. Therefore, the researcher can conclude that leaders can play a major role in their organisation by developing a vision and sharing their organisational goals with their colleagues or peers.

5.2.1.4 Leadership Competencies

Following table 5-12 and figure 5-10 shows the leadership competencies of the female leaders as perceived by the employees.

Table 5-12: Leadership competencies (Researcher)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Which of the following leadership competencies is being possessed by your leader?	Persuading and Influencing	12	12.0	12.0	12.0
	Communicating	14	14.0	14.0	26.0
	Meeting Customer needs	14	14.0	14.0	40.0
	Relating and Networking	27	27.0	27.0	67.0
	Taking Risk	15	15.0	15.0	82.0
	Creating and Innovating	18	18.0	18.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5-10: Leadership Competency (Researcher)

Respondents were asked about the leadership competencies of their leaders in the organisation. In this regard, the data highlights that 27% of the employees responded that leaders in their organisation are competent in relating and networking. Besides, the employees also stated that the leaders in their organisation possess other competencies such as communication, meeting customer needs, relating, and networking, risk-taking, creativity, and innovativeness. Therefore, it could be concluded that there are several leadership competencies possessed by the leaders in respondents' organisation.

Regarding the data collected above, the study was conducted by (Trequattrini, Russo and Lombardi, 2012) they highlighted that business relationships are managed by the people who play different social roles. The leaders should play an important role in building social bonds within the employees, establish personal networks, and frame stronger business networks.

From the background study of the respondents involved in the research, it could be stated that most of the organisations support and encourage women to become leaders in different roles. Further, majority of the respondents believed that women leaders are more effective as compared to male leaders. Besides, leaders play a major role in delivering success and relating

and networking with the members of the organisation, though the leaders possess other leadership competencies.

5.2.2 Inferential Analysis

In this section of the analysis, the researcher aims to understand the contribution and influence of factors in achieving successful leadership qualities among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK. Also, the researcher aims to understand the significance of the impact of women leaders on organisational performance. For that, the researcher has used the quantitative data collected using a Likert scale from the respondents and the same had been subjected to take correlation and regression analysis. Finally, to check the significance of women leadership behaviour concerning gender working in the FinTech sector of the UK, the researcher performed cross-tabulation analysis.

5.2.2.1 Factors responsible for Successful Women Leadership

In this section of the analysis, the aim is to explain the factors responsible for successful leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK. These factors are segregated into three categories; social, organisational and personal. For the analysis, to understand the impact of these factors, correlation test and regression analysis were performed. The proposed hypotheses are:

Hypothesis 1:

H₀₁: Social factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

H_{A1}: Social factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

For the analysis of the above-mentioned hypothesis, “effectiveness parameters for women leadership (Mean 1)” is response variable or dependent variable and social factors impacting the women leaders are independent variables.

Hypothesis 2

H₀2: Organisational factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

H_A2: Organisational factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

For the analysis of the above-mentioned hypothesis, “effectiveness parameters for women leadership (Mean 1)” is response variable or dependent variable and organisational factors impacting the women leaders are independent variables.

Hypothesis 3

H₀3: Personal factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

H_A3: Personal factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

For the analysis of the above-mentioned hypothesis, “effectiveness parameters for women leadership (Mean 1)” is response variable or dependent variable and personal factors impacting the women leaders are independent variables.

Hypothesis 4

H₀4: Technological factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

H_A4: Technological factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

For the analysis of the above-mentioned hypothesis, “effectiveness parameters for women leadership (Mean 1)” is response variable or dependent variable and technological factors impacting the women leaders are independent variables.

5.2.2.1.1 Social Factors impacting women leaders

Correlation test

H₀1: Social factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

H_A1: Social factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

Following table 5-13 shows the correlation for social factors for developing successful leadership among women leaders in the FinTech organisations.

Table 5-13: Correlation for hypothesis 1 (social factors) by Researcher

		The women are considered to be inferior to the male counterparts	Existence of phenomenon's like glass ceiling	Gender stereotyping	Family-related barriers	Orthodox and believing in the patriarchy system
Social Factors	Pearson Correlation	0.699**	0.828**	0.587**	0.613**	0.631**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	100	100	100	100	100

The Pearson correlation is used to understand the relationship between the effectiveness parameters for women leadership in FinTech sector (dependent variable) and the social factors contributing to the success of women leaders in the FinTech sector (independent variables) is quite high and positive, being significant at $p < 0.05$. Out of all the independent variables representing the organisational factors for the success of women leadership, ***‘Existence of phenomenon like a glass ceiling’*** (0.828**) depicts the highest correlation with the dependent variable. This means that the glass ceiling for women leaders in the organisations could be a significant and deciding social factor for their successful leadership.

Glass ceiling is an old concept that exists to date in almost every industry, it could be a hindrance to the career development of the women leaders. Glass ceiling is an invisible or unseen barrier that keeps the minority group and women away from vertical advancement to the higher and responsible corporate roles, regardless of their qualifications or achievements.

In this context, a similar study by (Ranaa, 2017) mentioned that societal factors have an indirect effect as underlying factors on women' career possibilities. While organisational factors have

a more direct effect. There are many ways to promote female leadership. However, there always exists a glass ceiling in terms of allocating equal opportunities for women to emerge as leaders.

If societal factors are considered, attention should be paid on the raising of children by giving boys and girls more possibilities to get to know different fields and professions to balance the gender division. Networking, sponsoring and mentoring are all good ways to promote female leadership as well. Thus, the researcher could conclude that there is a strong association between the effectiveness parameters for women leadership in the FinTech sector of the UK and the contribution of social factors towards their successful leadership role in the FinTech sector.

Further, the results indicate that the variable *'the women are considered to be inferior to the male counterparts'* is correlated with the social factors with the correlation coefficient 0.699. In this regard, the study conducted by (Petersen, Snartland and Milgrom, 2007) has highlighted that the jobs that are being defined in terms of gender are very common in society. Socialisation in society is indulged in society since childhood. The leadership is presumed to be dominated by men rather than women. The society has developed thinking that managerial functions are similar to masculine rather than feminine. The gender stereotyping is concerned with the belief that teaching characteristics are associated more with men than with the women. Therefore, gender stereotyping plays an important role in deciding that the leadership positions in the organisations will be dominated by men. Following part of the chapter covers the regression analysis conducted for the study.

Regression Analysis

Table 5-14: ANOVA test for hypothesis 1 (social factors) by Researcher

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	54.921	5	10.984	57.317	0.000
	Residual	18.014	94	0.192		
Total		72.935	99			

The ANOVA table 5-14 shows that null hypothesis, i.e. there are no social factors that contributes to the successful leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector in the UK, is rejected since the F value is significant at $p < 0.05$. Also, the F- value is high (57.317) and so the probability for accepting alternative hypothesis results is quite high and hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Further, the test results depict that the variables considered for the analysis show significant concerning the dependent variable.

Table 5-15: Model summary for hypothesis 1 (social factors) by Researcher

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.868	0.753	0.740	0.43777

Further, R square (0.753) and adjusted R square (0.740) values are higher than the standardised value of 0.5. So, this indicates that more than 70% of the variation is contributed by the independent variables in the dependent variable.

Table 5-16: Regression table for hypothesis 1 (social factors) by Researcher

Coefficients:				
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Sig
(Intercept)	1.187	0.176	6.757	0.000
The women are considered to be inferior to the male counterparts	0.063	0.061	1.025	0.308
Existence of phenomenon's like glass ceiling	0.422	0.069	6.125	0.000
Gender stereotyping	0.039	0.062	0.625	0.533
Family related barriers	0.145	0.057	2.552	0.012
Orthodox and believing in patriarchy system	0.046	0.062	0.754	0.453

The coefficient regression table above shows that among all the significant variables, ***‘Existence of phenomenon’s like glass ceiling’*** is the most significant factor among all social factors that contribute to the positive impact for successful leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK (0.422), significant at $p < 0.05$. This means that the vertical limits created by the organisational people, especially for women employees, could be an obstacle for attaining successful leadership by the women leaders in the FinTech sector.

(Bang and Shin, 2013) in their study mentioned that broad societal forces and policies perpetuate assumptions and stereotypes, which present challenges to women in leadership

roles. Legislation and policies related to employment equity, human rights, access to affordable day-care and reproductive rights have a profound impact on the ability of women to advance in the workplace. Thus the social factor does have a contribution in achieving successful leadership among women leaders, especially in the FinTech sector in the UK.

Further, family barriers are also a significant variable that impacts the successful leadership of women in organisations. In this regard, the study conducted by (Elmuti, 2009) family support has a direct relation with the family work, job satisfaction, and organisational commitment. The challenges in the form of childbearing act as a significant barrier. The women always face a dilemma in handling their career and family responsibilities. Therefore, women are often at a disadvantage in terms of family responsibilities and commitment towards organisations.

Table 5-17: Result of hypothesis 1 (social factors) by Researcher

Hypothesis	Results
H ₀₁ : Social factors do not contribute to developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK.	Rejected

From the inferential analysis, it is understood that their social factors contribute to achieving successful leadership among women leaders, especially in the FinTech sector of the UK. Therefore, the null hypothesis considered for quantitative analysis is rejected.

5.2.2.1.2 Organisational Factors impacting the women leaders

Correlation Test

H₀₂: Organisational factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

H_{A2}: Organisational factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

Following table 5-18 shows the correlation of organisational factors for the study.

Table 5-18: Correlation table for hypothesis 2 (Organisational factors) by Researcher

		Organisations have their own particular work environment with its own values, which is a legacy of past leaders, as well as the current leadership	Leaders are dependent on organisational resources, such as staff, technology, finances and physical resources to achieve their goals	Organisation culture that establishes rites, such as rituals, routines and a set way of doing things impacts company norms, such as how a worker can be in good standing and how a worker can respond appropriately for various circumstances which then impacts the leader	Organisational setting	Types of management style (change management, managing conflict, performance indicators, and management) followed in organisation effect leaders
Organisational Factors	Pearson Correlation	0.586**	0.575**	0.549**	0.588**	0.653**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
	N	100	100	100	100	100

The Pearson correlation used to understand the relationship between the effectiveness parameters for women leadership in the FinTech sector and the organisational factors contributing to the success of women leadership is quite high and positive, being significant at $p < 0.05$. Out of all the independent variables representing the organisational factors for the

success of women leadership, '*Types of management style followed in an organisation*' (0.653**) depicts the highest correlation with the dependent variable. This means that the proper and efficient management style followed by the women leaders in their respective organisations could help in achieving effective leadership quality for them in the industry. It's the responsibility of each leader to identify the most suitable leadership style for their organisation, to meet the organisation's vision and mission.

Likewise (Ana and Steve, 2017) in their previous research suggested that female leaders need to be on a journey of working through their leadership patterns and growth areas, so they can break free from male-dominated constructs and harness feminine qualities. They need to take deep dives to integrate themselves and lead from their higher purpose. In this way, they can strengthen the chain of women needed to bring more balance to the corporate world. Hence, it is understood that there is a strong association between the effectiveness parameters for women leadership in the FinTech sector of the UK and the contribution of organisational factors towards their successful leadership role in the FinTech sector.

In addition to this, '*organisational setting*' displays a high correlation with the dependent variable indicating that efficient organisational setting helps in promoting effective women leadership in the organisation. In this regard, the study conducted by (Subramanian, 2016) indicated that organisational culture clearly states the qualitative differences that exist between men and women in an organisation. A favourable political and social culture that exists in the organisation can act as a major instrument to promote female leadership. The organisations that create a self-motivated environment and provide equal opportunities to men and women promote successful leadership among women. The organisations should promote leadership development efforts which integrate the unique experiences that women have due to their gender identity. In addition to this, it should discourage any type of business bias that exists in the workplace.

Regression Analysis

Table 5-19: ANOVA table for hypothesis 2 (organisational factors) by Researcher

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	36.305	5	7.261	18.633	.000
	Residual	36.630	94	.390		
Total		72.935	99			

The ANOVA table 5-19 shows that null hypothesis, i.e. there are no organisational factors that contribute to the successful leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector in the UK, is rejected since the F value is significant at $p < 0.05$. Also, the F- value is high (18.633) and so the probability for accepting alternative hypothesis results is quite high and hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Further, the test results depict that the variables considered for the analysis show significant concerning the dependent variable.

Table 5-20: Model summary for hypothesis 2 (Researcher)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.706	.498	.471	.62425

Further, R square (0.498) and adjusted R square (0.471) values are close to the standardised value of 0.5. So, this indicates that around 50% of the variation is contributed by the independent variables in the dependent variable.

Table 5-21: Regression table for hypothesis 2 (Researcher)

Coefficients:				
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Sig
(Intercept)	1.753	0.235	7.473	0.000
Organisations have their own particular work environment with its own values, which is a legacy of past leaders, as well as the current leadership	0.208	0.077	2.705	0.008
Leaders are dependent on organisational resources, such as staff, technology, finances and physical resources to achieve their goals.	0.099	0.087	1.146	0.255
Organisation culture that establishes rites, such as rituals, routines and a set way of doing things impacts company norms, such as how a worker can be in good standing and how a worker can respond appropriately	-0.009	0.091	-0.096	0.924

ately for various circumstances which then impacts the leader				
Organisational setting	0.005	0.104	0.048	0.962
Types of management style (change management, managing conflict, performance indicators, and management) followed in organisation effect leaders	0.262	0.123	2.136	0.035

The coefficient regression table above shows that among all the significant variables, ***‘Organisations have their particular work environment with its values, which is a legacy of past leaders, as well as current leadership’*** is the most significant factor among all organisational factors that contributes to the positive impact for successful leadership of women leaders in FinTech sector in the UK (0.208), significant at $p < 0.05$. This means that the values inculcated and the eternal work environment established by the company’s ancestors and its present generation for efficient and effective business operations would have contributed to the success of leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector.

‘Organisation culture that establishes rites, such as rituals, routines and a set way of doing things impacts company norms, such as how a worker can be in good standing and how a worker can respond appropriately for various circumstances which then impacts the leader’ is the most significant factor among all organisational factors that contributes to the negative impact for successful leadership of women leaders in FinTech sector of the UK (0.208), significant at $p < 0.05$.

In a similar study by (Kattan et al., 2016), leadership success was found to have a positive impact on the success of organisations, where successful leaders could achieve organisational goals more efficiently and effectively. The cultural obstacles faced by the women leaders to get successful leadership achievement could be greatly reduced through knowledge attainment. Thus the organisational factors do have a contribution in achieving successful leadership among women leaders, especially in the FinTech sector in the UK and that could bring significant changes in their career development.

Table 5-22: Results of hypothesis 2 (Researcher)

Hypothesis	Results
H ₀ 2: Organisational factors do not contribute to developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of The UK.	Rejected

From the inferential analysis, it's understood that their organisational factors contribute to achieving successful leadership among women leaders, especially in the FinTech sector of the UK. Therefore, the null hypothesis considered for quantitative analysis is rejected.

5.2.2.1.3 Personal Factors impacting women leaders

Correlation Test

H₀3: Personal factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

H_A3: Personal factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

Table 5-23: Correlation table for hypothesis 3 (personal factors) by Researcher

		The personality of a leader	Individual needs of a leader	Competence of the leader	Confidence and courage of the leader	Creativity and initiative ability of a leader
Personal Factors	Pearson Correlation	0.638 **	0.679 **	0.585 **	0.573 **	0.704 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	100	100	100	100	100

The Pearson correlation is used in table above to understand the relationship between the effectiveness parameters for women leadership in the FinTech sector and the personal factors contributing to the success of women leadership, which, is quite high and positive, being significant at $p < 0.05$. Out of all the independent variables representing the organisational factors for the success of women leadership, '*Creativity and initiative ability of a leader*' (0.704**) depicts the highest correlation with the dependent variable. This means that the women leader, who takes great initiatives in their work and put forward a more creative and practical idea, could achieve success in their leadership role. The organisation support in case of people, who take such initiatives in their work, is very evident in the industry.

(Kendall, 2018) in his recent research study mentioned the similar opinion of increasing one's capacity for leadership. This is especially beneficial for women who participate in systems that lack equal gender representation. Despite differences in organisational culture, certain patterns of experience have been negatively related to female leadership presence, and depend on the theoretical lens of leadership for development. Examination of demand-side and supply-side factors inhibiting female a career progression shows significant effect of environmental and

individual impositions which ultimately impact women leadership development. Female leadership presence is a mechanism for change, as well as a means of building the most effective team possible.

The representation of stakeholders in leadership is a value that should be fostered within organisational dynamics and human relations, as these operate effectively only when clientele, employees, community, and leadership are integrated and supported. Hence, it is understood that there is a strong association between the effectiveness parameters for women leadership in the FinTech sector of the UK and contributing personal factors in achieving their successful leadership role in the FinTech sector.

In addition to this, the *'Individual needs of the leader'* are highly correlated with the dependent variable. This means that women who possess characteristics of the leader can create successful leaders for the organisations. In this regard, the study conducted by (Morgeson, DeRue, and Karam, 2010) highlighted that leadership rest on the type of leadership style. In addition to this, it depends upon the leadership behaviour shown by the individual. The leader should be an inspirational person who is confident, self-motivated and has had authoritative control over its team. Further, the leader should be able to communicate and coordinate with their team by understanding their needs. If these set of characteristics are possessed by women, they can emerge as a great leader.

Regression Analysis

H₀₃: Personal factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

H_{A3}: Personal factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

Table 5-24: ANOVA table for hypothesis 3 (personal factors) by Researcher

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	44.853	5	8.971	30.027	0.000
	Residual	28.082	94	.299		
Total		72.935	99			

The ANOVA table shows that null hypothesis, i.e. there are no personal factors contributing to the successful leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK, is rejected since the F value is significant at $p < 0.05$. Also, the F-value is high (30.027) and so the probability for accepting alternative hypothesis results is quite high and hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Further, the test results depict that the variables considered for the analysis show significant concerning the dependent variable.

Table 5-25: Model summary for hypothesis 3 (personal factors) by Researcher

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.784	.615	.594	.54658

Further, as shown in table above, R square (0.615) and adjusted R square (0.594) values are higher than the standardised value of 0.5. So, this indicates that around 60% of the variation is contributed by the independent variables in the dependent variable.

Table 5-26: Regression table for hypothesis 3 (personal factors) by Researcher

Coefficients:				
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Sig
(Intercept)	1.210	.230	5.263	.000
Personality of leader	-.035	.079	-.437	.663
Individual needs of a leader	.159	.086	1.842	.069
Competence of leader	.318	.134	2.375	.020
Confidence and courage of the leader	-.054	.135	-.400	.690
Creativity and initiative ability of a leader	.301	.095	3.158	.002

The coefficient regression table above shows that among all the significant variables, **‘Creativity and initiative ability of a leader’** is the most significant factor among all personal factors that contribute to the positive impact for successful leadership of women leaders in the FinTech sector in the UK (0.301), significant at $p < 0.05$. This means that the women leaders showing great initiatives in their responsibilities could get good support from the organisations and that would have contributed to the success of leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector.

In this context, a study by (Mberia and Mberia, 2017) has mentioned that leadership is important in guiding human actions to conform to certain ideals. Where proper leadership is exercised, societies experience development in many spheres. Many studies have shown that women and men are one of the important criteria that determine the employee's position in the workplace. Therefore, society, in general, should accept and value diverse roles played by men and women in society. However, Women leadership is still faced with many challenges, some of which lie in fundamental personal factors that need to be addressed. Thus the organisational

factors do contribute to achieving successful leadership among women leaders, especially in the FinTech sector in the UK and that could bring significant changes in their career development.

Also, '*Competence of a leader*' is the significant personal factor that contributes to the successful women leaders in the organisations. In this regard, the study conducted by (Pentti Sydanmaanlakka, 2003) highlights that functional competencies that promote competition between male and female create an environment that promotes growth in the organisation. There must be a healthy competition among male and female leaders. The male and female leaders often compete in terms of managerial ability, interpersonal skills, communality, and assessment. These functional competencies must be acquired through formal qualification and skills provided through the required training. These competencies are acquired through problem-solving and include the set of communication as well as technological skills. The body of knowledge thus establishes HR capability as a functional competency that is required by top top-level managers for the effective execution of strategic functions.

Table 5-27: Result of hypothesis 3 (personal factors) by Researcher

Hypothesis	Results
H03: Personal factors do not contribute to developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of The UK.	Rejected

From the inferential analysis, it can be inferred that the personal factors contribute to achieving successful leadership among women leaders, especially in the FinTech sector of the UK. Therefore, the null hypothesis considered for quantitative analysis is rejected.

5.2.2.1.4 Technological Factors impacting women leaders

Correlation Analysis

H₀₄: Technological factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

H_{A4}: Technological factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

Below table shows the correlation between the effectiveness of female leaders and the technological factors which affect the female leaders.

Table 5-28: Correlation table for hypothesis 4 (technological factors) by Researcher

		Functionality and Transportation Capabilities like Railways, Paved roads, electric power, and telephone lines	Innovation	IT education and Training Opportunities like workshops, technical information based programs	Technical Competence	Technical Expertise
Technological Factors	Pearson Correlation	.475**	.536**	.572**	.530**	.635**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	100	100	100	100	100

The correlation analysis revealed that all parameters under the technological factors are positively correlated with female leadership success in the UK's FinTech start-ups. Although, all the factors have significant relationship because p-value is less than 0.05, the magnitude of correlation depicted by Pearson correlation value varies. For "**Technical Expertise**", the correlation value is 0.635 thus depicting that there exists high positive correlation between the expertise in technical field and the effectiveness of a leader. This shows that an employee possessing technical skills tends to perform more effectively and has more chances of growth in the organisation.

A study by (Ashcraft, Mclain, & Eger, 2016) stated that women have less expertise in the field of technology. For creative and innovative roles, their contribution is less. This is one of the main reasons for the lack of women leaders in the tech sector as compared to men. Core and innovative roles in a firm need possession of technical skillset, as it yields more innovation and growth of an organisation. Hence, the effectiveness of an employee increases which further leads to her becoming a successful leader. Thus, this study proves the existence of a high correlation between the effectiveness of leadership and technical expertise.

Further, the Pearson correlation value is also high for “IT Education and Training Opportunities”, i.e. 0.572. In order to have a more effective performance by an employee, it is required that regular training opportunities should be available. As these training and education opportunities tend to develop new skills among the employee, the productivity of employees increases.

World Economic Forum (2013) report also stated that mentorship by managers and training opportunities create more efficient employees. Lack of support from the managers discourage the employees and thus affect their performance. Training of employees and even informal or formal support from managers by tends to boost employees’ confidence. Further, the study showed that support via education and training even tend to create more innovation possibilities which created the opportunity of having effective leadership and led to the growth of the organisation (Ashcraft et al., 2016).

For “Innovation”, “Technical Competence” and “Functionality and Transportation Capabilities” also Pearson correlation shows a positive correlation with women leadership effectiveness, however, the magnitude of the correlation is less thus depicting the existence of the moderate positive relationship. It shows the awareness of and availability of good infrastructure enables women leaders to perform better at the workplace. Women leaders fulfilling technical roles and innovating new techniques lead to improvement of efficiency. This was also supported by Bullough, (2008) study who examined the impact of infrastructure and technical factors on leadership effectiveness. Hence, technological and infrastructural

factors contribute to influencing the effectiveness of female leaders and even the existence of positive factors tend to provide a way towards successful leadership for women.

Regression Analysis

H₀4: Technological factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

H_A4: Technological factors contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

Table 5-29: ANOVA table for hypothesis 4 (technological factors) by Researcher

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	36.805	5	7.361	19.142	.000 ^b
	Residual	36.148	94	.385		
	Total	72.953	99			

Table 5-29 above shows that the null hypothesis of not having any significant impact of technological factors on the successful leadership of women in FinTech sector of UK is rejected as the p value is less than 0.05. As the above table has p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$, thus there is possibility of rejecting null hypothesis and showing existence of significant relationship between technological factors and successful leadership. F-statistic value is 19.142 which is quite high thus the probability of existence of relationship is also high. However, the relationship is tested via t-statistic.

Table 5-30: Model summary of hypothesis 4 (personal factors)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.710 ^a	.505	.478	.62012

Table 5-30 above shows that the model framed to test the impact of technological factors on the effective of female leaders is effective. As R square value is 0.505 and adjusted R square value is 0.478, thus the value are close to the standardised value of R i.e. 0.05. Hence about 50% variation in the female leadership effectiveness is explained by the technological factors.

Table 5-31: Regression table for hypothesis 4 (technological factors) by researcher

Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.203	.288		4.176	.000
	Functionality and Transportation Capabilities like Railways, Paved roads, electric power, and telephone lines	.054	.072	.071	.757	.451
	Innovation	.129	.068	.182	1.883	.063
	IT education and Training Opportunities like workshops, technical information based programs	.106	.087	.136	1.223	.224

Technical Competence	.135	.072	.174	1.865	.065
Technical Expertise	.237	.082	.321	2.892	.005

Table 5-31 represents the regression analysis which via p-value testing helps in determining the relationship between technological factors and effectiveness of women leaders in the UK's Fintech sector. As the p-value for technical expertise only is less than 5% level of significance i.e. $0.005 < 0.05$, thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, the coefficient value of the factor depicts that there exists a positive relationship between "Technical expertise" and "Successful Female Leadership". With an increase in technical knowledge of women employee (0.237), there is a possibility of having the effective working of women as a leader. Thus, as women gain more technical knowledge and acquire new skills, their productivity and contribution in the organisation increase. Further, it creates the opportunity of effective and efficient performance of women along with job advancement. Hence, women move toward becoming a successful leader. This viewpoint was supported by (Colwill & Townsend, 1999; Dahlvig & Longman, 2010) as they stated that with the advancement in technology, the skills of women employees improved. Thus more leadership roles were available for women due to the expertise that they have derived after attaining new skills. Further, (Ashcraft et al., 2016) study added that with the achievement of expertise in the technological sector, core and innovative roles were available for women. Hence, attainment of skills not only helps existing women leaders in growing professionally but also opens opportunities for other females of learning new skills and getting employment in the technological sector.

Though there are various other technological factors like "Innovation" and "Technical Competence" but they are significant at 7% level of significance because their p-values are 0.063 and 0.065. Though studies (World Economic Forum, 2013; Bullough, 2008) support that these two factors to have the effect of successful and effective female leadership as these factors help in creating recognition opportunity for women and also contributing in developing something, this study fails to provide empirical evidence of a significant relationship. Further technological factors like "Functionality and Transportation

Capabilities”, and “IT Education and Training Opportunities” also do not have any significant relationship with female leadership effectiveness in UK’s FinTech sector.

Table 5-32: Result of hypothesis 4 (Researcher)

Hypothesis	Results
H04: Technological factors do not contribute to developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK.	Rejected

From the inferential analysis, it can be inferred that the technological factors contribute to achieving successful leadership among women leaders, especially in the FinTech sector of the UK. Therefore, the null hypothesis considered for quantitative analysis is rejected.

5.2.2.2 Significance between leadership behaviour and gender

To check the significant difference between the effective leadership behaviour and the gender for the women leaders of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK, the researcher adopted crosstab analysis. Crosstab construction and analysis is widely used in research survey results to find out relationships and interactions between the variables.

Therefore the proposed hypothesis is:

H05: There is no significant difference in women leadership behaviour with respect to gender working in the FinTech sector of the UK.

HA5: There is a significant difference in women leadership behaviour with respect to gender working in the FinTech sector of the UK.

5.2.2.2.1 Participative Decision Making

Table 5-33: Cross tabulation for participative decision making (Researcher)

			Participative Decision Making					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Gender	Male	Count	7	13	10	14	10	54
		% within Gender	13.0%	24.1%	18.5%	25.9%	18.5%	100.0%
	Female	Count	4	4	8	16	14	46
		% within Gender	8.7%	8.7%	17.4%	34.8%	30.4%	100.0%
Total		Count	11	17	18	30	24	100
		% within Gender	11.0%	17.0%	18.0%	30.0%	24.0%	100.0%

The cross cross-tabulation table above shows that about 31% female respondents and 18% male respondents strongly agreed with the fact that *'Participative Decision Making'* is one of the most effective leadership behaviour possessed by the women leaders of their organisation. Hence, the researcher could conclude that there is a significant difference between *'Participative Decision Making'* behaviour concerning gender working in the FinTech sector of the UK. Few male respondents agreed with the fact that women leaders possess effective leadership in their organisation. The study by (Danish et al., 2013) has mentioned that employees' participation in the decision-making process can also help the organisation to improve its performance in terms of meeting goals efficiently. In addition to that, the previous study shows that there is a strong association for participative decision making concerning the performance of the organisation.

5.2.2.2.2 Role Model

Table 5-34: Cross tabulation of role model (Researcher)

			Role Model					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Gender	Male	Count	7	13	4	15	15	54
		% within Gender	13.0%	24.1%	7.4%	27.8%	27.8%	100.0%
	Female	Count	3	1	4	20	18	46
		% within Gender	6.5%	2.2%	8.7%	43.5%	39.1%	100.0%
Total		Count	10	14	8	35	33	100
		% within Gender	10.0%	14.0%	8.0%	35.0%	33.0%	100.0%

The cross cross-tabulation table indicates that about 44% of female respondents agreed to the view that the women leaders in their organisation act as a role model for others. On the other hand, only about 28% of male respondents supported the same view. Hence, the researcher could conclude that there is a significant difference between *'Role Model'* concerning gender working in the FinTech sector of the UK. The results highlight the only few male respondents support the view that the women leaders in their organisation act as a role model for others.

5.2.2.2.3 Inspiration

Table 5-35: Cross tabulation for inspiration (Researcher)

			Inspiration					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Gender	Male	Count	5	11	11	13	14	54
		% within Gender	9.3%	20.4%	20.4%	24.1%	25.9%	100.0%
	Female	Count	1	2	6	22	15	46
		% within Gender	2.2%	4.3%	13.0%	47.8%	32.6%	100.0%
Total		Count	6	13	17	35	29	100
		% within Gender	6.0%	13.0%	17.0%	35.0%	29.0%	100.0%

The cross-tabulation table 5-35 shown above indicates that a majority of 48% female respondents and about 24% of the male respondents agreed to the opinion that women act as an inspiration when displaying effective leadership. Thus, there is a significant difference in the perception of male and female respondents. It can be concluded that effective leadership behaviour displayed by the women leaders act as a source of motivation for other women working in the FinTech sector of the UK. In this context, in journal published by (Dan Nielsen, 2017), he has mentioned that inspirational leaders are intentional in using their position to inspire, change lives, and leave excellent and lasting legacies. It is amazing to witness the ripple effect of a great inspirational leader, the author has also shared many first-hand accounts of people who have had the opportunity to work under these wonderful leaders.

5.2.2.2.4 Expectation and Rewards

Table 5-36: Cross tabulation of expectations and rewards (Researcher)

			Expectations and Rewards					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Gender	Male	Count	6	5	5	20	18	54
		% within Gender	11.1%	9.3%	9.3%	37.0%	33.3%	100.0%
	Female	Count	0	4	3	18	21	46
		% within Gender	0.0%	8.7%	6.5%	39.1%	45.7%	100.0%
Total		Count	6	9	8	38	39	100
		% within Gender	6.0%	9.0%	8.0%	38.0%	39.0%	100.0%

The above cross-tabulation in table 5-36 above shows that in terms of expectations and rewards, about 33% male respondents and about 46% female respondents strongly agree to the view that women leaders in their organisation are rewarded for their hard work. Hence, it can be concluded that there is hardly a difference in context to the *‘Expectations and Rewards’* between the males and females working in the FinTech sector of the UK. In the similar context, the journal of (Iqbal, Sha, and Haider, 2015) mentioned that most effective strategy is reward system and leader’s ability to engage the employees in the organisational goals and to manage their performance. The best way for leaders to do so is to show them their worth and appreciate their efforts. They further mentioned that the appreciation can be in the form of a raise, it could be a small raise or recognition among others. Rewards can have a great impact on engaging

employees within the organisation. It is observed that engaging employees within an organisation is a very complex process but management must take time to fully develop it.

5.2.2.2.5 People Development

Table 5-37: Cross tabulation of people development (Researcher)

			People Development					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Gender	Male	Count	7	8	8	17	14	54
		% within Gender	13.0%	14.8%	14.8%	31.5%	25.9%	100.0%
	Female	Count	1	4	9	18	14	46
		% within Gender	2.2%	8.7%	19.6%	39.1%	30.4%	100.0%
Total		Count	8	12	17	35	28	100
		% within Gender	8.0%	12.0%	17.0%	35.0%	28.0%	100.0%

In the context of *'People development'*, about 32% male respondents and 39% female respondents think that women leaders act for people's development. Hence, there is less difference in the perception of male and females in context to people's development in the organisation. In this framework, the study of (Zing Collaborative, 2018) has mentioned that people are put into leadership roles because they're good at their jobs, but they don't necessarily have the competence to be effective. But that dearth could be compensated by providing proper training and giving proper guidelines to the future leaders of the organisation.

5.2.2.2.6 Intellectual Stimulation

Table 5-38: Cross tabulation of intellectual stimulation (Researcher)

			Intellectual Stimulation					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Gender	Male	Count	5	3	20	15	11	54
		% within Gender	9.3%	5.6%	37.0%	27.8%	20.4%	100.0%
	Female	Count	0	4	3	18	21	46
		% within Gender	0.0%	8.7%	6.5%	39.1%	45.7%	100.0%
Total		Count	5	7	23	33	32	100
		% within Gender	5.0%	7.0%	23.0%	33.0%	32.0%	100.0%

The results of the cross-tabulation shown in the above table 5-38 indicate that 46% of female respondents strongly agreed with the opinion that intellectual stimulation is an effective leadership behaviour displayed by the women in their organisation. On the other hand, only about 20% of male respondents strongly agreed with the same opinion. Thus, a significant difference between the perception of the male and female respondents can be observed. Only a few male respondents think that *'Intellectual stimulation'* is one of the effective leadership behaviour displayed by the women leaders working in the FinTech sector of the UK. With regards to this, (Breux, 2010) has defined the intellectual stimulation as having a leader who encourages innovation and creativity, as well as critical thinking and problem-solving. Intellectual stimulation involves arousing followers' thoughts and imagination, as well as stimulating their ability to identify and solve problems creatively.

5.2.2.2.7 Efficient Communication

Table 5-39: Cross tabulation of efficient communication (Researcher)

			Efficient Communication					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Gender	Male	Count	4	5	7	23	15	54
		% within Gender	7.4%	9.3%	13.0%	42.6%	27.8%	100.0%
	Female	Count	3	2	6	18	17	46
		% within Gender	6.5%	4.3%	13.0%	39.1%	37.0%	100.0%
Total		Count	7	7	13	41	32	100
		% within Gender	7.0%	7.0%	13.0%	41.0%	32.0%	100.0%

The results of the cross-tabulation table 5-39 shown above indicate that about 43% male respondents and 39% female respondents agreed with the opinion that effective communication is one of the effective leadership behaviour shown by the women leaders in their organisation. Thus, it can be concluded that both male and female respondents thought that effective communications skills are possessed by the women leaders working in the FinTech sector of the UK. In this context, the article published by (Anthony, 2018) has stated that effective leadership in business requires knowing how to communicate with all elements of the organisation, including employees, managers, customers, and investors. Each group may require a different communication style and leadership style. Leaders must be able to adapt based on the group they are communicating with at the time. Effective communication skills are an important aspect of any leader’s portfolio of skills and experience.

5.2.2.2.8 Individualistic Decision Making

Table 5-40: Cross tabulation of individualistic decision making (Researcher)

			Individualistic Decision Making					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Gender	Male	Count	18	9	9	11	7	54
		% within Gender	33.3%	16.7%	16.7%	20.4%	13.0%	100.0%
	Female	Count	1	2	6	22	15	46
		% within Gender	2.2%	4.3%	13.0%	47.8%	32.6%	100.0%
Total		Count	19	11	15	33	22	100
		% within Gender	19.0%	11.0%	15.0%	33.0%	22.0%	100.0%

The cross-tabulation table 5-40 above shows that majorly about 48% of female respondents agreed with the opinion that women leaders in their organisation possess the quality of individualistic decision making. On the other hand, only about 20% of male respondents agreed to the view. Hence, there is a significant difference in the opinion of male and female respondents in context to ***‘Individualistic Decision Making’*** by the women leaders. Most of the male respondents do not support the view that the women leaders in the FinTech sector are capable to take effective decisions individually.

5.2.2.2.9 Control and Corrective Action

Table 5-41: Cross tabulation of control and corrective action (Researcher)

			Control and Corrective Action					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Gender	Male	Count	10	13	1	15	15	54
		% within Gender	18.5%	24.1%	1.9%	27.8%	27.8%	100.0%
	Female	Count	3	3	4	18	18	46
		% within Gender	6.5%	6.5%	8.7%	39.1%	39.1%	100.0%
Total		Count	13	16	5	33	33	100
		% within Gender	13.0%	16.0%	5.0%	33.0%	33.0%	100.0%

The cross cross-tabulation table 5-41 above shows that about 39% female respondents and 28% male respondents strongly agree with the opinion that the female leaders in their organisation can control the present situation and take the corrective action. The results indicate that there is not much difference in the opinion of male and female respondents. Thus, both male and female respondents think that they can control the problems faced by the organisation and can take the necessary action in the FinTech sector of the UK.

Table 5-42: Result of hypothesis 5 (Researcher)

Hypothesis	Results
H ₀ 5: There is no significant difference in women leadership behaviour with respect to gender working in the FinTech sector of the UK.	Rejected

From the inferential analysis, it is understood that there is a significant difference in women leadership behaviour concerning gender working in the FinTech sector of the UK. Therefore, the null hypothesis considered for quantitative analysis is rejected.

5.2.2.3 Leadership and Performance of the organisation

To analyse the impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK, “*organisational performance (Mean 2)*” is response variable or dependent variable and factors consisting of effectiveness parameters and shortcomings of women leadership are independent variables. Therefore the proposed hypothesis is:

H₀₆: There is no significant impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK

H_{A6}: There is a significant impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK

5.2.2.3.1 Effectiveness Parameters

Correlation Test

Table 5-43: Correlation table for hypothesis 6 (Researcher)

	Effectiveness Parameters		
	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	N
She is a visionary who challenges the old order and way of doing things.	.739**	.000	100
She is competent in managing change and planning and organising	.690**	.000	100
She is able to develop a specific vision for and a plan for implementing change.	.618**	.000	100
She has the interpersonal skills to inspire employees to embrace and deliver the vision and strategy	.759**	.000	100

She is an effective change agent because she is creative, empathetic and able to deal with the concerns of colleagues and employees who may be resistant to change.	.809**	.000	100
She understands the importance of achieving corporate objectives in order to advance the organisation	.695**	.000	100
She demonstrates qualities that motivate respect and pride from association with him or her	.766**	.000	100
She communicates values, purpose, and importance of organisation's mission	.706**	.000	100
She exhibits optimism and excitement about goals and future states	.752**	.000	100
She examines new perspectives for solving problems and completing tasks	.378**	.000	100
She focuses on the development and mentoring of followers and attends to their individual needs	.685**	.000	100
She provides rewards for satisfactory performance by followers	.635**	.000	100
She attends to followers' mistakes and failures to meet standards	.592**	.000	100
She waits until problems become severe before attending to them and intervening	.686**	.000	100
She exhibits frequent absence and lack of involvement during critical junctures	.620**	.000	100

The Pearson correlation used to understand the relationship between the effectiveness parameters for women leadership in FinTech sector (dependent variable) and the impact of the leadership on a team or organisational performance in FinTech sector (independent variables) is quite high and positive, being significant at $p < 0.05$. Out of all the independent variables

representing the effectiveness parameters for women leadership, ***'She is an effective change agent because she is creative, empathetic and able to deal with the concerns of colleagues and employees who may be resistant to change'*** (0.809**) depicts the highest correlation with the dependent variable. This means that the women leader, who has a creative and empathetic mindset to deal with the concerns of their colleagues, could generate a significant impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation.

According to leadership's researchers published by (Madanchian et al., 2017), effective leadership is a key analyst of organisational success or failure while examining the factors that lead to organisational success. Effective leaders have power over specific traits and show specific behaviours or styles of leadership. The most common outcome measure to evaluate an effective leader is examining the consequences of a leader's actions. For instance, if a leader can influence his subordinates or organisation in such a way that positive outcomes are realised, this constitutes an effective leader. Another similar study by (Cordeiro and Stites-Doe, 1997) indicates that a firm's strategic positioning concerning the hiring and promotion of women to managerial positions has a direct effect on both, its cost and productivity levels. As such, firms that discriminate against women in hiring and promotion decisions suffer lower performance, as they incur added costs and/ or lower productivity. Hence, one could conclude that there is a strong association between the effectiveness parameters for successful women leadership in the FinTech sector and the impact of leadership on organisational performance.

Further, another variable ***'She demonstrates qualities that motivate respect and pride from association with him or her'*** (0.766**) also depicts a high correlation with the dependent variable. This means that the women leaders who possess qualities that motivate, and respect employees and generate pride from the association with their employees have a significant impact on the performance of the organisation.

In this regard, the study conducted by (Aarum Andersen and Hansson, 2011) highlighted that women leaders that act as motivators for their team can lead their organisations towards long term growth and success. They do not just act as a role model for their team but an inspiration for all women employees in the organisation.

Regression Analysis

Table 5-44: ANOVA table for hypothesis 6 (Researcher)

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	49.737	15	3.316	29.658	.000 ^b
	Residual	9.391	84	.112		
	Total	59.128	99			

The ANOVA table 5-44 above shows that null hypothesis, i.e. there is no significant impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK, is rejected since the F value is significant at $p < 0.05$. Also, the F- value is high (29.658) and so the probability for accepting alternative hypothesis results is quite high and hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Further, the test results depict that the variables considered for the analysis show significant concerning the dependent variable.

Table 5-45: Model summary for hypothesis 6 (Researcher)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.917 ^a	.841	.813	.33437

Further, R square (0.841) and adjusted R square (0.813) which, indicates that about 81% of the variation is contributed by the independent variables in the dependent variable. This means that the model is good enough to explain the variation in the dependent variable.

Table 5-46: Regression of hypothesis 6 (Researcher)

Model		Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.875	.181		4.826	.000
	She is a visionary who challenges the old order and way of doing things.	.084	.385	.126	.219	.827
	She is competent in managing change and planning and organising	-.342	.467	-.487	-.732	.466
	She is able to develop a specific vision and a plan for implementing change.	.106	.053	.159	2.012	.047
	She has the interpersonal skills to inspire employees to embrace and deliver the vision and strategy	.107	.066	.168	1.616	.110
	She is an effective change agent because she is creative, empathetic and able to deal with the concerns of colleagues and employees who may be resistant to change.	.140	.096	.215	1.459	.148
	She understands the importance of achieving corporate objectives in order to advance the organisation	.096	.053	.131	1.802	.075
	She demonstrates qualities that motivate respect and pride from association with him or her	.129	.078	.192	1.663	.100
	She communicates values, purpose, and importance of organisation's mission	.028	.072	.040	.387	.700

She exhibits optimism and excitement about goals and future states	-.018	.068	-.027	-.261	.795
She examines new perspectives for solving problems and completing tasks	.011	.044	.015	.240	.811
She focuses on the development and mentoring of followers and attends to their individual needs	.106	.342	.157	.309	.758
She provides rewards for satisfactory performance by followers	.328	.450	.466	.728	.468
She attends to followers' mistakes and failures to meet standards	-.202	.238	-.284	-.849	.398
She waits until problems become severe before attending to them and intervening	.027	.170	.040	.159	.874
She exhibits frequent absence and lack of involvement during critical junctures	.186	.226	.271	.820	.414

The coefficient regression table 5-46 above shows that among all the significant variables, '*She is able to develop a specific vision and a plan for implementing change*' (2.012) is the most significant factor among all effectiveness parameters that has a positive impact on the organisation performance in FinTech sector in the UK, significant at $p < 0.05$. This means that the women leaders who develop a specific vision or plan for achieving the organisational goals would improve the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK.

In this context, a similar research study by (K, 2013) tends to view gender issues based on the premise that women are marginalised and a glass ceiling effect is still the major impediment to women's participation in leadership, other current yet authentic issues may go unnoticed or misunderstood. Without the active participation of women and the incorporation of women's perspective at all three levels of decision-making, the goals of equality, development, and

peace cannot be achieved. Further, the research study by others shows that good policies which promote non-discriminatory practices in a company can boost the performance of employees that includes women. Another similar study by (Alam and Ahmed, 2015) indicates that the leadership function is very important for any organisation seeking to achieve financial success and competitive advantage. The study also revealed that although other external factors, such as government regulations, globalisation and the current economic climate of a country may be responsible for the performance of an organisation, with effective leadership an organisation can overcome these challenges. Thus, there is a significant impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK.

5.2.2.3.2 Shortcomings for Women Leaders

H₀₇: There is no significant impact of shortcomings of female leaders on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of The UK

H_{A6}: There is a significant impact of shortcomings of female leaders on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of The UK

Correlation Test

Table 5-47: Correlation test for hypothesis 7 (Researcher)

	Shortcomings		
	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	N
She is not intellectually inspiring	.590**	.000	100
She does not possess the individualistic decision-making competency	.506**	.000	100

She is not able to control the difficult scenarios and situations that arise.	.620**	.000	100
She does not take corrective actions for mistakes	.461**	.000	100
She Distances herself and behaves arrogantly to those she leads	.572**	.000	100
She lacks accountability and courage while handling her or the team's performance	.542**	.000	100
she rarely works collaboratively with her team members and lacks trust over her team	.545**	.000	100
There is rarely any scope of diversity of thoughts and actions and delegation of responsibilities under my leader	.514**	.000	100
She is more result-oriented than being considerate on accountability, tasks, processes, people, and outcomes	.781**	.000	100
She lacks emotional intelligence	.528**	.000	100
She has limiting abilities to influence, adapt to the culture, and "fit-in" organisationally and impersonally	.561**	.000	100

The Pearson correlation table 5-47 is used to understand the relationship between the shortcomings of women leaders in FinTech sector (dependent variable) and the impact of the leadership on a team or organisational performance in FinTech sector (independent variables) is quite high and positive, being significant at $p < 0.05$. Out of all the independent variables representing the shortcomings of women leaders in the FinTech sector, ***'She is more result-oriented than being considerate on accountability, tasks, processes, people, and outcomes'*** (0.781**) depicts the highest correlation with the dependent variable. This means that the women leaders who are more result-oriented, generate better economic gains for the organisation.

A similar study by (Gipson, 2017) stated that women in senior decision-making positions as well as lower-ranking positions within traditional and non-traditional sectors of employment, as well as lower-ranking positions of employment, take risks, which could even make them lose their positions. Previous studies, also, indicate that having more women in positions of power does not necessarily result in women-friendly social, economic and political systems that are responsive to women's concerns.

Other studies show that extending education and training to women for becoming more active in the paid and productive workforce has enhanced economic development efforts further.

The barriers that prevent women from making effective decisions are resistance and acceptance from their counterparts, stigma attached to women as emotional beings and not logical thinkers, protecting them from getting exposed to decision-making situations. Decision-making is a skill, which can be perfected by practicing the skill. Women need to be encouraged and provided the required opportunity to make decisions for themselves and others. Hence, one could conclude that there is a strong association between the shortcomings of women leaders in the FinTech sector and the impact of leadership on organisational performance.

Regression Analysis

Table 5-48: ANOVA table for hypothesis 7 (Researcher)

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	42.182	11	3.835	19.912	.000
	Residual	16.947	88	.193		
	Total	59.128	99			

The ANOVA table 5-48 shows null hypothesis, i.e. there is no significant impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK, is rejected since the F value is significant at $p < 0.05$. In addition, the F- value is high (19.912) and so the probability for accepting alternative hypothesis results is quite high and hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Further, the test results depict that the variables considered for the analysis show significant in nature with respect to the dependent variable.

Table 5-49: Model summary for hypothesis 7 (Researcher)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.837 ^a	.701	.664	.44814

Further, R square (0.701) and adjusted R square (0.664) values are higher than the standardised value of 0.5. So, this indicates that more than 66% of the variation is contributed by the independent variables in the dependent variable.

Table 5-50: Regression table for hypothesis 7 (Researcher)

Model		Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.044	.223		4.685	.000
	She is not intellectually inspiring	.208	.114	.265	1.829	.071
	She does not possess the individualistic decision making competency	.096	.098	.123	.980	.330
	She is not able to control the difficult scenarios and situations that arise.	.024	.112	.028	.210	.834
	She does not take corrective actions for mistakes	.023	.076	.033	.299	.766
	She Distances herself and behaves arrogantly to those She leads	.243	.208	.306	1.167	.246
	She lacks accountability and courage while handling her or the team's performance	-.362	.195	-.450	-1.852	.067
	she rarely works collaboratively with her team members and lacks trust over her team	-.448	.167	-.557	-2.682	.009
	there is rarely any scope of diversity of thoughts and actions and delegation of responsibilities under my leader	-.119	.122	-.162	-.977	.331

she is more result-oriented than being considerate on accountability, tasks, processes, people, and outcomes	.624	.073	.776	8.534	.000
She lacks emotional intelligence	-.027	.176	-.035	-.156	.877
She has limiting abilities to influence, adapt to the culture, and “fit in” organisationally and impersonally	-.454	.175	.567	2.592	.011

The coefficient regression table 5-50 above shows that among all the significant variables, *‘She is more result-oriented than being considerate on accountability, tasks, processes, people, and outcomes’* is the most significant factor that has a positive impact on the performance of the organisations operating in FinTech sector of the UK (0.624, significant at $p < 0.05$). This means that the women leaders who are more result-oriented have a positive impact on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector. Apart from this, another variable *‘She rarely works collaboratively with her team members’* hurts the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK (-.448, significant at $p < 0.05$). This indicates that the women leaders who don’t coordinate with the other team members and rarely works in collaboration of the team members negatively affect the organisation’s performance in the FinTech sector of the UK.

In this context, the study of (Pentti Sydanmaanlakka, 2003) highlighted that the women leaders must possess the quality of developing coordination with the employees, the women must focus upon the effective team building and community involvement by coordinating with the team members and the employees. This motivates the employees and inspires them to deliver greater efficiency.

In context to the result result-oriented behaviour shown by the women leaders of the organisation, the study conducted by (Asha N. Gipson et al., 2017) stated that the women who are in the position of leadership are often more result-oriented. They are concerned with the

outcomes of profits and the value-added in the organisation. In this manner, they act as more effective and competent leaders as compared to males.

Results

Table 5-51: Results of hypothesis 7 (Researcher)

Hypothesis	Results
H ₀ 6: There is no significant impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of The UK.	Rejected

From the inferential analysis, it is understood that there is a significant impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK. Therefore, the null hypothesis considered for quantitative analysis is rejected.

5.3 Conclusion

This chapter examines the results of the data analysis to evaluate the growing phenomenon of female leadership within the FinTech companies of the UK. For this purpose, the researcher conducted both quantitative and qualitative analysis. Under the quantitative analysis, the researcher approached 100 male and female employees of the five companies. On the other hand, the qualitative analysis, the researcher interviewed 5 female managers working in five selected companies in the FinTech industry. Under the qualitative analysis, the interviewees were inquired about the leadership strategies adopted. In this context, most managers were of the view that the organisations are driven by innovation. Thus, the leaders must be able to build a competitive team that can align with the business strategies.

Leadership in the FinTech industry must perform in a manner such that they can adopt the advanced technology that is continuously changing the phase of the financial sector. In addition

to this, the managers thought that organisations have started becoming gender-neutral due to which there is a rise in the number of women who are at the leadership positions in the organisations. This is because women have proved that they are equally competent in comparison to the men. Some of them also thought that women have different leadership characteristics and have greater strength and creativity in comparison to men.

About the tools that must be adopted to boost women leadership, the managers were of the view that women must be provided with an adequate level of training. In the context of the factors that lead women leaders to be successful within the industry, the managers thought that women have more conceptual knowledge. Concerning the challenges, the interviewees were of the view that women have a larger role to play in family responsibilities due to which they get a fewer chance to succeed and are underrepresented.

Under the quantitative analysis, the researcher examined the social, organisational, personal, and technological factors that lead to successful women leaders in the organisations. The results indicated that women face many barriers due to family obligations. In addition to this, the culture of the organisation plays an important role in developing circumstances that can impact the leader of the organisation.

Further in context to the personal factors, the creativity and the initiative ability of the leader is one of the major factors that can develop successful women leadership among the women leaders. However, in the case of technological factors, attaining technical expertise contribute to having successful female leadership.

In context to the success of the organisations, the results indicated that leaders who can develop a specific plan for implementing the change can improve the performance of the organisation.

Chapter: 6 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.0 Introduction to the chapter

The previous chapter presented an analysis of the factors that affect the growth phenomenon of female leadership within the FinTech companies in the UK. This chapter explains the results obtained by the researcher through primary and secondary analysis. The introduction of the chapter explains the role and importance of female leadership in the FinTech sector. Following this, the researcher describes the key findings of the results that were obtained through secondary and primary research. Lastly, the researcher presents the summary of the chapter.

The present decade is witnessing the increasing role of women in the FinTech start-up sector. However, the leadership roles in the FinTech start-up sector are still skewed towards males. The high rate of growth experienced by the FinTech start-up sector has created a strong demand for the staff with the required financial technical and operational capabilities. The FinTech sector has opened up a vast number of opportunities at both the middle and the senior level of management. This has, in turn, increased the demand for qualified professionals.

Along with this growth, the era of modernisation has encouraged women to take up roles in the corporate sector. This has increased the need for getting educated among females. The present decade is also encouraging women to take up responsibilities for their career growth. However, the traditional family structures continue to play an important role in the present society due to which even the well-educated women face multiple social barriers for acting as future leaders. Apart from this, multiple organisational and political factors affect the growth of women leaders in the industry.

6.1 Findings

This research aims to evaluate the growth of female leadership within FinTech companies in the UK's start-up sector. For this purpose, the researcher examined the factors that create successful leaders amongst females in the UK's FinTech start-up sector. In addition to this, the researcher examined the role played by these factors in influencing female leadership. By examining the factors and the role played by these factors, the researcher proposes a framework that explains the connection between drivers and successful female leadership within the FinTech sector of the UK.

The study used both primary and secondary sources of information. The primary data was collected through the administration of the survey questionnaire to the current female leaders in the FinTech sector. The secondary studies were used to support the results of the primary analysis. This research aims to evaluate the growing phenomenon of female leadership within FinTech companies in the UK's start-up sector. Under the inferential analysis, the data collected was used to understand the effectiveness, shortcomings and the future outlook of the women leaders.

6.1.1 Findings from the primary study

In the present study, the researcher employed the quantitative and qualitative research approach. Under the qualitative approach, the researcher collected the first-hand information by interviewing the top-level female managers of the five selected companies. For this purpose, the researcher used an open-ended and semi-structured questionnaire. The interviewees were probed about their perception on leadership strategies, management of FinTech companies, gender neutrality in leadership, the success of women in leadership roles, benefits of women leadership, tools to improve women leadership, factors leading to success in the industry and the challenges faced in leadership positions.

In terms of management of FinTech companies, most interviewees were of the view that this sector is driven by the agenda of innovation. To derive innovation in the sector, they require

the leaders who can navigate into a new and competitive environment. These leaders must possess the passion to take up new challenges as they need to adapt to technological challenges.

In terms of gender neutrality in leadership, the interviewees were of the view that leadership is no longer considered as a male-dominated job. In the modern era, organisations invite equal participation and believe in granting equal opportunities to females. This has opened up new opportunities for them to enter into leadership roles. Moreover, they expressed that women have equal capabilities to act as future leaders. They can act as key players who can generate long term gains for the economy.

Further, in the context of women's success in leadership roles, the interviewees reported that there exist certain hurdles. One of the most common hurdles is the incongruity that exists between male and female leadership behaviour that generate a different set of standards for male and female leadership. On the other hand, some of the interviewees believed that women set up a different set of standards to strengthen and innovate into leadership roles. They build a strategic and long term vision for the organisation that can lead it to a path of a successful future. About the benefits of women leadership, some of the interviewees thought that every individual possesses a different style of leadership according to their behaviour and attitude, while some of them believed that women can manage the organisation in a better manner because they can balance the work and life in a better manner. In addition to this, they are more compassionate which helps them to generate long term gains for the organisation.

The interviewees were also questioned about the tools that must be used to increase women leadership in organisations in the FinTech sector. In this context, the interviewee's thought that women need better mentoring and guidance which can help them to compete in their career path. They have a more creative approach to decision making.

Most of the interviewees believed that allocating quotas for women is not the correct solution for the problems that women are facing in the present era. Rather than the allocation of the quotas, the women must be motivated by providing them with the chance of equal participation. In addition to this, another most important factor that can generate success among

the women is the family support as women always face a barrier in maintaining the work-life balance.

Further, concerning the factors that lead to the success of women in the industry, the interviewees shared two different sets of view. Some interviewees thought that women possess greater knowledge base and professional skills that have given them the ability to manage a leadership position with a high degree of efficiency. On the other hand, some of them believed that the glass ceiling that exists in women's lives have helped them in emerging as great leaders. The individual struggle that the women undergo has helped her in emerging as better leaders. Further, the emotional intelligence and the ability to view the things in broader terms have assisted the women.

The interviewees were also asked about the challenges faced by them at the leadership positions. In this context, the interviewees were of the view that the most significant challenge faced by the women is the inflexible working arrangements that make it difficult for women to handle their family and job responsibilities due to which they often get lesser chance to succeed. This often leads to under-representation of women in higher management. On the other hand, some of the interviewees supported the view that women are under-represented in leadership roles. Lastly, the interviewees suggested some changes to improve the leadership position. To this, most of the interviewees believed that it is necessary to remove society and structural barriers. The organisational policies must be framed in a manner that can address the traditional gender roles and can cater to the expectation of women seeking a higher management role.

Under the quantitative approach, the researcher gathered the responses of 100 male and female respondents working in the industry. For this purpose, the researcher used a close-ended questionnaire to gather the data. The results of the frequency analysis highlighted that the women leaders are more effective as compared to their male counterparts. In addition to this, the respondents highlighted that their leaders performed the function of sharing of organisational goals, and networking.

In context to the social factors, the researcher highlighted that the existence of glass ceiling and family-related barriers can affect the development of successful female leadership among the women leaders in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK. This means that women often face barriers in terms of vertical limits created by society. Apart from this, women always face a dilemma in handling their family and job responsibilities.

Following this, the researcher analysed the impact of organisational factors that contribute to developing successful female leadership in the FinTech sector of the UK. Among the organisational factors, the most significant factor is that the organisations have their particular work with its values as a legacy of the past leaders as well current leadership and the types of management style followed by the organisations. Subsequently, the interviewees were inquired about the personal factors that contribute towards the development of successful female leadership. In this context, the results indicated that the creativity and initiative ability of the leader and the confidence as well as the courage of the leader would act as one of the major factors that affect the development of successful leaders among the women leadership in FinTech sector of the UK.

Lastly, the impact of technological factors on the success of female leaders in the UK's FinTech start-ups was analysed. Technological factors included questions related to the effect of infrastructural development, innovation, education and training opportunity, competence, and expertise impact on the effective successful working of female leaders in the FinTech start-up sector of UK. The analysis showed the possession of technical expertise is the most significant among all technological factors which contribute to influencing female leadership effectiveness. As this expertise tends to affect the productivity, efficiency, and effectiveness of female leaders, they seek opportunities for growth. Further, technical competence and innovation too significantly contribute to influencing female leaders' effectiveness. Moreover, the interviewees expressed that STEM education must be emphasised early on in females' education to encourage more participation of females in technical jobs.

Apart from this, the researcher conducted the cross tab analysis to examine the significant difference between leadership behaviour and gender. Further, the researcher analysed the leadership and performance of the organisation. The findings highlighted that the women

leaders are more creative, empathetic and able to deal with the concerns of the colleagues and employees. Further, these women demonstrate qualities that motivate other leaders. In context to the performance of the organisations, the findings indicated that women often learn from their mistakes that help enable them in meeting the desired standards. Further in context to the shortcomings of the women leadership, the results indicated that women leaders often have to limit abilities to influence and adapt to the culture of the organisation

6.1.2 Findings from secondary study

Through the primary findings, the result highlighted that the existence of a glass ceiling is one of the most significant factors that affect successful leadership. To this, the study of (Ranaa, 2017) highlighted that the societal factors that have an indirect effect on the career possibilities of the women have a direct effect on women leadership.

In addition to this, the study highlighted that the glass ceiling is the unseen barrier that women face in every industry that keeps women away from the vertical advancements in higher corporate roles. In the same context, the study of (Bang and Shin, 2013) stated that the societal forces and stereotypes pose a challenge to the women leadership in the present decade. Apart from this, the family responsibilities act as a major barrier that impacts the successful leadership of women in organisations.

In the context of the organisational factors that impact the women leadership, the findings indicated that types of management styles followed by the organisation are one of the major factors that affect the success of leadership. In this regard, the study of (Ana and Steve, 2017) found that female leaders can take up deep divines to integrate themselves for a higher purpose. Further, the organisational setting helps in promoting effective women leadership in the FinTech sector. In this context, the study of (Subramanian, 2016) stated that there exist multiple qualitative differences between men and women in the organisation. Favourable political and social culture acts as a major instrument to promote female leadership. The organisations promote leadership development which can integrate the women due to their

gender diversity. In the same context, the study of (Kattan et al., 2016) highlighted the view that cultural obstacles faced by the women leaders can be reduced through appropriate knowledge attainment.

Concerning the personal factors, the study of (Kendall, 2018) mentioned that few differences in the organisation can generate a negative impact on female leadership. If the organisation takes up steps to eliminate such differences, the value of the stakeholders would be fostered through different organisational dynamics and the human relations that are supported through the leadership.

Further, the regression analysis indicated that the *'Creativity and initiative ability of a leader'* has a positive impact on the successful women leaders in the FinTech start-up company. In this context, the study of (Mberia and Mberia, 2017) highlighted that leadership is important for guiding the human action that conforms to the cretin ideals. However, the women leadership undergoes a certain set of challenges in context to their personality that the individuals need to address. In the same context, *'Competence of a leader'* is another significant factor that contributes to successful women leaders among the organisations. The study of (Pentti Sydanmaanlakka, 2003) supported this view that the functional competencies promote competition within male and female leaders, this competition arises in the form of interpersonal skills, managerial ability, and communality.

(Colwill & Townsend, 1999; Dahlvig & Longman, 2010) suggested that "Technical Expertise" is a significant factor which tends to create promotional opportunities for female leaders. Furthermore, the availability of technical expertise leads to the appointment of more female employees in an organisation.

The researcher conducted the cross tab analysis to examine the evidence for a significant difference in the women leadership behaviour concerning gender working in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK. In this context, the study of (Danish et al., 2013) stated that there is a strong association for participative decision making concerning the performance of the organisation. Concerning the inspirational factors, the study of (Dan Nielsen, 2017) was of the

view that inspirational leaders are intentional in using their position to inspire, change lives, and leave beautiful and lasting legacies.

Further, the study of (Iqbal, Sha, and Haider, 2015) stated that the most important strategy to generate an effective reward system is through the engagement of employees in the organisational goals to manage the performance of an individual or a group. This is because rewards can have a great impact on engaging employees within the organisation.

The researcher also identified that effective communication is one of the most important instruments which can help the leaders in generating the right pathway for the success of the organisation. To this, the study of (Anthony, 2018) stated that effective leadership requires business organisations to develop community involvement among the employees, managers and the customers of the organisation.

Following this, the researcher examined the impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation. In this regard, the study highlighted that though the female leaders meet the required standards by learning from their mistakes they don't display active participation in the organisational matters. Further, in terms of the shortcomings of the women leaders, the study of (Pentti Sydanmaanlakka, 2003) supported the fact that women leaders have limiting abilities to influence and adapt to the culture. The companies must have positive and empowering company policies that can play an important role in motivating women leaders.

6.1.3 Hypothesis Findings

H₀₁: Social factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

Through the first hypothesis, the researcher examined how social factors contribute to developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK. The dependent variable is the effectiveness parameters for women leadership and the independent variables include all the social factors contributing to the success of women

leaders in the FinTech start-up sector. The researcher identified various independent variables including the women leaders are considered to be inferior to the male counterparts existence of phenomena like the glass ceiling, gender stereotyping, family-related barriers, orthodox and believing in patriarchy system. The findings indicated that among all the social factors 'Existence of phenomena like a glass ceiling' is the most significant factor that contributes to positive impact for successful leadership among the women leaders. This means that the vertical limits created by the organisational people especially the women employees could be an obstacle from attaining successful leadership by women leader in the FinTech sector. Apart from this, family barriers also have had a direct relationship with the level of job satisfaction. This is because women face a lot of difficulties in handling both the family and job-related responsibilities.

H02: Organisational factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

Through the second hypothesis, the researcher examined the impact of organisational factors on developing successful female leadership among the women leaders in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK. Organisational factors could include the types of management style, organisational setting, and organisation culture that establishes the rites and rituals routines and the set of doing the things. In this regard, the findings highlighted that '***Organisations have their particular work environment with its values, which is a legacy of past leaders, as well as current leadership***' contributes to the positive impact from successful leaders in the FinTech start-up sector. This means that the organisations have their values and policies which are governed by the legacy of the past leaders. These policies often grant an equal set of opportunities for all the employees which, can have a positive impact and help the organisations in achieving the desired goals.

H03: Personal factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

Through the third hypothesis, the researcher examined the impact of personal factors on the successful women leaders among the women leaders in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK. The set of independent variables includes the set of personal factors including the Personality of leader, Individual needs of a leader, confidence, and courage of the leader and the creativity and initiative ability of a leader. In this regard, the findings highlighted that the ***‘Creativity and initiative ability of a leader’*** is one of the most significant factors among all the personal factors that contribute to the positive impact on successful leadership. This means that the women leaders who are committed towards their organisation take up the responsibilities and guide the human actions in the right direction. Another personal factor that contributes to successful business leadership is the competence of the leader as functional competencies often promote healthy competition among the male and female leaders in the organisation.

H04: Technological factors do not contribute towards developing successful female leadership among women leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK

Through this hypothesis, the contribution of technological factors in influencing the effectiveness of female leaders was analysed in FinTech start-ups in the UK. For this, the technological aspects such as infrastructure support, innovation, IT training and education opportunity, technical competence, and technical education were taken as independent factors while women leaders effectiveness was taken as the dependent variable. The analysis suggests that there is a high correlation between female leaders effectiveness, and competence and IT education and training opportunities but the regression suggests that “Technical Expertise” has been the biggest impact on successful leadership of females. Increase in technical knowledge and skills of female leaders tend to generate opportunities for promotion and recognition of females, improving their efficiency and productivity. This leads to better performance of the organisation as a whole. Further, the interview analysis of female leaders to shows that technical competence and innovation has a positive influence on female leaders’ effectiveness.

H05: There is no significant difference in women leadership behaviour with respect to gender working in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK.

Following this, the researcher assessed the difference in women leadership behaviour concerning gender working in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK. In this context, the researcher examined the different factors that generate effective leadership behaviour. These decisions include the participative decision making, role model, inspiration, expectation and rewards, people development, intellectual stimulation, efficient communication, individualistic decision making, control, and corrective action.

About participative decision making, few male respondents strongly agreed with the view that ***'Participative Decision Making'*** is the quality possessed by the women leaders in their organisation. In the same context, only a few male respondents supported the view that the women leaders in their organisation act as ***'Role Models'*** for the others. Women leaders often act as a source of motivation for other women in the organisation. In this context, the findings highlighted that the women leaders act as a source of motivation as well as ***'Inspiration'*** for other women leaders in the organisation. Further, both male and female respondents think that there is not much difference in the view of the male and female respondents concerning the ***'expectation, rewards and people's development'***. Similarly, the male respondents thought that women can act as effective communicators in the organisation. However, the male respondents thought women leaders working in their organisations lack certain leadership qualities like intellectual stimulation, control, and corrective action and effective decision making.

H06: There is no significant impact of leadership on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK

Through this hypothesis, the researcher examined the impact of effective parameters of leadership and shortcomings of the women leaders on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK. In the context of the effective parameters that are possessed by the women leaders, the regression results indicate that women leaders can develop a specific vision and plan for implementing the change in the organisations. This means that the women

leaders who can develop a long term vision for achieving the organisational goals would positively influence the organisation's performance. In addition to this, women leaders often focus on implementing a new set of strategies and policies for improving the performance of the organisation. Vis-à-vis the shortcomings possessed by the women leaders, the results of the regression analysis indicated that the women leaders are more result-oriented than the male leaders of the society. However, one of the major shortcomings among women leaders is that they rarely work in collaboration with the other team players that negatively impacts the performance of the organisation.

6.2 Discussion

Women have continued to face greater barriers than men to participate in the economy. The traditional society provides clear evidence of the fact that there are greater incongruences among men and women in terms of pay gaps, uneven opportunities for advancement and unbalanced representation in the decision-making process. The only way to overcome the preconceptions of the traditional society is to uplift the women by encouraging them to take up positions of leadership and providing the support to act as the role models.

In the new age culture, the images of women leadership always act as the source of motivation accomplishment and achievement for other women. However, women upliftment has set up a major benchmark for the overall society to develop their mindset in a manner that can provide equal treatment to both men and women. A similar situation is evident from the FinTech start-up sector of the UK. The sector has displayed a high level of holistic development and progress. Though this sector has continuous development, gender diversity is still an issue of concern that has to be focused upon. An optimal level of development of the sector requires the need for the presence of diversity. The organisations that have fair gender diversity produce greater financial returns and higher profit as compared to the other firms. In the present era, the leadership position is no longer configured to be taken by the male members of society. The organisations are concerned by the long term economic gains which can only be achieved through the qualities of the leader who can guide their team in the right direction.

In addition, it is important that society must adopt a certain set of measures to eliminate the barriers faced by women leaders. For this purpose, it is important to identify the factors that influence female leaders in executing successful leadership skills. In this context, the present study evaluated the growth phenomenon of female leadership within FinTech companies in the UK's financial sector. By examining the factors that create the successful women leaders in the UK financial technology start-up sector, the researcher proposed a framework that explains the connection between the drivers and the successful female leadership within the FinTech sector of the UK. The present study highlighted that there are social barriers in the form of the glass ceiling, organisational factors in the form of the work environment, personal factors in the form of family barriers, and technological barriers in terms of technical skills expertise that impacts the successful leadership among the women leaders. Apart from this, the culture of the organisation plans plays an important role in affecting the successful leadership among the organisations.

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6.3 Conclusion

Traditionally, women have been unrepresented in senior leadership positions in the corporate sector across the globe. In addition to this, the leadership positions in the political, organisational and military spheres were dominated by the male members of the society. This trend is reversed in the modern era where women have developed their own social identity by acquiring leadership positions in every sector. The FinTech sector has also witnessed a growth in the number of women leaders. However, these women leaders continue to face multiple social, organisational personal, and technological barriers due to which they are unable to emerge as successful leaders. To eradicate the barriers that are hindering the growth and development process among the women leaders, it is important to examine the factors that are impacting the success of women leadership.

In this regard, the present study examined the growing phenomenon of female leadership within the FinTech companies in the UK's start-up sector. For this purpose, the researcher used both primary and secondary sources of information. The researcher adopted a mixed methodology under which the researcher followed both a quantitative and qualitative approach. Under the quantitative approach, the researcher examined the responses of 100 employees working in 5 companies in the FinTech sector in London, the UK. To collect the data, the researcher used a structured and close close-ended questionnaire. Through this questionnaire, the researcher examined the factors that have led to the success of female leadership in the FinTech sector. Under the qualitative approach, the researcher interviewed 5 managers of each of the 5 companies selected for the study. In this context, the researcher used an open-ended questionnaire.

The researcher used correlation, regression, and cross tab analysis to understand the effectiveness of women leaders in their organisation, the shortcomings and the future outlook under that leader. The results indicated that among the social factors, the existence of the glass ceiling is one of the significant factors that have a positive impact on successful leadership among the women leaders. In addition to this, women leaders often face family family-related barriers as they face multiple difficulties in handling their responsibilities. Regarding the organisational factors, the organisation's values which direct the employees in the right

direction have a positive impact on successful leadership. Further, among the personal factors, the creativity and initiative ability of the leader has a positive impact on the leadership and for technological factors, technical expertise has a positive influence on female leadership effectiveness. The women leaders who are committed towards their organisation take up the responsibilities and guide the human actions in the right direction.

Cross-tab analysis was used by the researcher to examine the women leadership behaviour concerning gender working in the FinTech sector of the UK. The findings highlighted that there is no difference in the perception of the male and female leaders concerning the expectation, rewards and the people's development. However, the female leaders act as an inspiring force and role model for the female employees in the organisation.

Lastly, the researcher examined the effect parameters and the shortcomings of the women leaders on the performance of the organisation in the FinTech sector of the UK. The findings of the regression analysis that the women leaders who can develop a long term vision for achieving the organisational goals would influence the organisation's performance. Concerning the shortcomings possessed by the women leaders, the results indicated that women leaders are more result-oriented which have a positive impact on the performance of the organisation.

Chapter: 7 CONCLUSION, CONTRIBUTION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.0 Introduction to the chapter

This chapter highlights the conclusions, contributions, and recommendations following the analysis done in the study. After giving a brief introduction to this chapter, the next part will entail the conclusions based on the objectives as listed in the first chapter of the study. Further, the second part highlights recommendations which would improve the women leadership in the FinTech industry. Lastly, this chapter highlights the limitations and the future scope of the study.

The expansion of digital platforms which are being adopted for availing other financial services has widened the scope of the FinTech industry. The banking industry is also undergoing an innovation wherein they are adopting alternative credit models and quick payment services. Due to this, the industry would witness growth with further expansion of personal finance and the retail facilities. This has generated the requirement of those leaders who can adopt diverse leadership styles which would help the organisation in achieving its targeted goals.

The previous studies conducted on effective women leadership and the barriers faced by them focused upon the view that women have been more concentrated in jobs which enable them to maintain a balance between work and family life. This is predominant both in the private and Government sectors. In this context, the present study highlighted that theories like the ‘Glass Ceiling’ and ‘Sticky Floor’ hampers women to reach the top-level and confines them at the lower levels in workspaces. Employers are also sometimes judgemental in choosing top-level staff, based on pre-set notions of efficiency of males and females. In this context, the present study evaluated the growth phenomenon of female leadership within FinTech companies in the UK’s start-up sector.

Through the literature review, the researcher identified that there are four broad factors which affect females in reaching the top-level management; social, organisational, technological and personal. In this context, the researcher examined the influence of each of these factors on female leadership in the present study. In addition to this, the study determined the parameters that affect the effective female leadership in the organisations. The study focused to capture the real-life experience and so organised the research analysis in a way that both quantitative and qualitative study could be done to determine the outcome i.e. the actual scenario for females in industries like FinTech.

7.1 Conclusions

The research paper on Women leadership in the UK's FinTech start-up sector makes the following conclusions.

7.1.1 Objective 1: To determine the factors that creates successful leaders amongst females in the UK's Financial Technology (FinTech) start-up sector.

Objective 1 set out to determine the factors that are responsible for the creation of successful female leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK, particularly for start-ups. Primarily, the researcher examined the influence of social, organisational personal, and technological factors on the female leaders. In this context, the findings of the qualitative analysis highlighted certain measures that would encourage equal participation of women. FinTech companies require top management to be able to tap on innovations and drive the company forward in the rapidly changing business environment and should be able to build a strong team of employees working towards the goals. For women leaders to be able to achieve this, they must be able to keep themselves up to date with the financial and technological space. Organisations can provide STEM-related workshops to aspiring women. It is also essential for them to maintain transparency internally with the employees and externally with clients. The leaders must be able to tap on customer demands and adapt accordingly. They must also ensure that task-related priorities are maintained. Also, women need to have active participation in events that are

conducted within the organisation. Such participation will make women visible in the organisation and thus make them known and eventually make them highlight that skills and reach the top level. The researcher believes that upon the incorporation of all the above-mentioned factors in woman's day to day life at FinTech start-ups would help them become a contender to the leadership post. Objective 1 has therefore been achieved.

7.1.2 Objective 2: To determine the role played by these factors in influencing female leadership in the FinTech sector.

Objective 2 set out to determine the role played by the identified factors in influencing female leaders in the FinTech sector of the UK. In terms of gender neutrality, FinTech was found to be more open to women at top management. The companies are growing on to adopting a more gender-neutral work environment which will enable the employees to focus on the basic skills like personality development so to enhance trust and confidence among the women employees. However, there are still issues like unequal pay/ sticky floor if the female employees are considered at the top level of management.

To be able to climb the leadership ladder of FinTech start-up companies in the UK, women need to improve their skill-set to emerge as future leaders in the industry. These skill-set are varied starting from management experience, leadership qualities, technological know-how and last but not the least self-determination. Apart from this, there is also a need for the male and female leaders to think alike so to maintain congruity to attain positive performance results. An organisation consists of different stakeholders, and male and female employees play an equal role in its functioning. Harmony in the approach and goals of all these stakeholders is important to ensure the success of the organisation and to maintain a fruitful and positive atmosphere. Gender diversity is an important constituent of this phenomenon, as emphasises several times in the literature review of this study.

Women employees have brought in more diverse options for effectively managing the strategic decisions based on a broader spectrum. To bring women to the forefront, organisations can

organise general discussions and debates among the employees. In addition to this, women require continuous motivation to follow their career path. Some believe in the structure of 'Quotas' to uplift women in the workspace and bring equality but the quotas should only be limited to that. On the other hand, the others believed that woman at the top level must represent good abilities and should deserve to be at those positions with or without quotas. Women with talent and contextual knowledge of the workspace achieve top management posts irrespective of the quota system. They are also able to achieve higher than their male counterparts because they can break through the glass ceilings created in an organisation by accepting it as a challenge.

There is a certain set of technical expertise required to be at the top level in the FinTech industry as discussed in the previous chapters, which plays a vital role in the determination of the top position. However, women are perceived to be not very tech-savvy and face a lot of social and cultural obstacles in holding those positions. This mindset is widely prevalent among male management, and hence the women often are seen as not in line to be in a management position. Therefore, it is observed that gender in some manner plays a role in selecting top management for the organisations.

Leadership has different forms, and no set form is better than the other. It is how the leaders use those styles to turn opportunities and assign those opportunities to the team members to achieve success. There is no gender dominance in books for who is a better leader. What is seen is that women leaders tend to use diverse leadership styles and this is becoming a growing phenomenon across industries. It is setting an example for future leaders to act as leaders by growing away in their work-life from society created stereotypes.

There is a consensus on the under-representation of women in the FinTech industry. This is attributed to the fact that peer pressure leads to long working hours in these organisations. This is true for the top management level and the lower levels alike. Hence, there is less flexibility in the workplace arrangement for men and women. These factors lead to the existence of gender inequality in the working environment and hence, in choosing top-level management for FinTech industry, fewer opportunities are available for women. Besides, senior partners in

the industry are usually men. This explanation for objective two helps us to come to the inference that Objective 2 has thus been achieved.

7.1.3 Objective 3: To propose a framework that explains the connection between drivers and successful female leadership within the FinTech sector of the UK.

Objective 3 set out to propose a framework that explains the connection between drivers and successful female leadership within the FinTech sector of the UK. In context to the performance of the women leaders in the FinTech industry, the results of the quantitative analysis highlighted that women leaders exist in most of the FinTech companies and are as effective as male leaders. These leaders focus on delivering success by preparing a vision for the organisation they work with. The main focus of these women leaders is on networking and relationship building with the customers and shareholders. They also create and innovate in the organisation by encouraging the creation of new ideas among the employees.

Social factors like glass ceilings impact the leadership of women at the top level. Barriers in organisations restrict women from moving to top-level positions. Organisational factors also impact women leadership wherein it is most important to follow the appropriate leadership style in a specific organisational setting. Further significant differences can be seen among female and male leaderships based on factors like participative decision making, intellect, inspiration, control, etc. women leadership behaviour is found to be different among FinTech organisations. Leadership plays a significant part in influencing this outcome.

Women leaders who can help the employees in coping with the changes in the work environment as well as be empathetic and creative in an organisation can affect organisation and employee performance successfully. In addition to this, the women leaders who can develop a vision and a plan to bring in a change in the organisation can affect organisations performance.

The women leaders need to stand up to the expectations of the organisation in terms of accountability, tasks, processes, people, and outcome rather than focusing just on the result in an organisation. They also should be able to mould according to the requirements of the team

to get the best outcome for the organisation. Based on the above discussion, it is safe to say that, Objective 3 has therefore been achieved.

7.2 Answering Research Questions

7.2.1 What factors are linked to create the contents in which female leaders can emerge/succeed in the FinTech start-up sector of the UK?

Despite the advancement of the economy, globalisation, and technological development, women's participation in the workplace has grown marginally in top-level management and other leadership profiles, which continue to remain mainly male-dominated. There exist various factors like stereotypes, competence, family support issues, organisational culture, expertise in technology, personality differences, and leadership styles which contribute in affecting the appointment of women employees for the leadership profile. The literature review conducted in this research identified five main factors that affect female leadership in any industry- political, organisational, social, technological and individual. However a further examination of empirical evidence about the FinTech start-up sector lacked the context of political factors, hence this was excluded from the study. Qualitative analysis suggests that to cope up with changing business environment and meet the dynamic demands of consumers along with fulfilling the objectives of the organisation, it is necessary to hire the employees having technical expertise, innovativeness and creative skills, and flexibility in decision making.

The interviews also revealed that preference for female leaders is affected mainly due to the perception of personal responsibilities is more important than professional ones in the case of females. Quantitative analysis revealed that although factors like creativity, expertise, and glass ceiling do affect women performance, women leaders are good at networking and strengthening relationships with shareholders and consumers. Their visionary power, creative skills, and dedication level have a significant impact on their functioning. Hence, all these

socio-cultural, organisational, personal, and technological factors do contribute in improving the efficiency of female leaders and creating the opportunity of innovation which in turn leads to successful female leadership in FinTech sector of UK start-ups.

7.2.2 What role are such factors likely to play in influencing leadership behaviour among female leaders in the UK's FinTech sector?

The analysis has identified that social, organisational, personal, and technological factors do contribute to influencing the effectiveness of women leadership. However, the studies suggest that these factors apart from harming the female leaders, also tend to open growth opportunities for women. The existence of gender inequality and glass ceiling, pay scale gap, and sticky floor in organisations discourages female leaders. However, the importance of technological factors such as innovativeness and technical expertise is also emphasised upon by all stakeholders.

Realising the importance of gender diversity, some organisations employ the quota policy for encouraging women leaders in top-level management. Although the primary analysis has shown that the quota system helps in reducing gender inequality and promoting gender neutrality, congruence of the role is gender-based, thus affecting the effectiveness of the leaders. Hence, the capability-based allocation of roles needs to implement. Further, the existence of the glass ceiling and other stereotypes tends to boost the confidence of women towards effective working to prove themselves. When it comes to technological factors, the empirical results showed that possessing technical skills, training and innovativeness play a key role in influencing the success of the female leaders. As for the personal factors, creativity and intuitive ability is the most important determinant.

7.3 Contributions

7.3.1 Empirical contribution

The extent of success of female leadership depends on the environment in which the women function. According to the literature review, there were four categories of factors which impact the female leadership in FinTech organisations. These categories are social factors, organisational factors, technological factors and personal factors. The social factors comprise of gender stereotyping and family-related barriers. The personal factors could capture the creativity and initiative ability of the leader. The technological factors are related to technological know-how acquired by the female employees and Lastly, the organisational factors include the organisational values, ethics and the availability of resources.

In the context of the social factors, the most common barriers faced by women are related to the family. Women often face challenges in maintaining the work-life balance due to which most of them restrict their roles in the lower or management level. Support from the family is an important factor along with the right skill-set and education. Women are known to be dominant in areas of social and health education but not in the IT sector, which is known to be dominated by men. There is also a presence of traditional gender roles in FinTech companies.

Social and organisational factors affect the role of women at top management positions in FinTech organisations. The organisational factors comprise of the formalities, procedures and the standards of the organisation. In addition to this, these factors depend upon the technical, financial and physical resources. In the context of the social factors, the study considered the existence of a glass ceiling, which is considered as a major barrier for women. In this context, organisational factors like work culture and opportunities given to women to develop are important factors to promote female leadership. In addition to this, motivation and coordination of management are some other important organisational factors which can drive females to achieve their set goals and aim for higher status in a FinTech organisation.

Further in terms of the individual factors, the personality, competence, confidence and the courage of the leader affect the female leadership in the FinTech organisations. In personal

skills what is most important for female leaders is to build good networking. It enables good leaders to share, learn, develop and support each other in an organisation. Apart from this, techniques of confidence building, diversification of women in male-dominated sectors, encouragement to take more risks by believing in themselves, and the ability to change are some other personal factors highlighted by literature studies in this research work.

‘The Social Role Theory’ states that men and women were assigned specific roles in society and were expected to work accordingly. Gender roles are defined in such a way that men are to concentrate on material success. On the other hand, women are required to maintain the quality of life and teaching kids to be modest. Although the concept of leadership doesn’t regard any gender as the perfect leader, males are assumed by society to be better leaders than females in FinTech organisations. Leadership qualities like task completion, problem-solving, decision making, confidence, power, and vision are being claimed by society to be present simply in males. The personal traits like competence, emotional consistency, and analytical excellence are not expected out of women and thus makes them inefficient leaders. Therefore, this study looked into different factors affecting women leadership in FinTech organisations. There are factors which can be easily converted to the benefit of a woman leader, and some are part of the mind-sets which are hard, but not impossible to remove if the efforts are in the right direction.

The contribution of these findings is that FinTech organisations must take a multi-layered approach towards improving the role of females in leadership positions. Not only must it work towards encouraging more female employees through the right training and exposure, but it must also educate male employees regarding the achievements and benefits of having a female leader so that the prejudice can be removed.

7.3.2 Theoretical contribution

Organisational biases, sexual discrimination at the workplace and more efforts required to achieve higher posts are all common organisational issues that impact female leadership as

cited by Ilagan-Bian (2004) cited in Njiru, (2013). It also highlights wage discrimination as a factor responsible for less female leaders in FinTech organisations. This study also highlights the need for culture in FinTech organisations that promotes equal participation of the male and female leaders. To this, the study of Klaile (2013) explains how the terms like glass ceilings and sticky floors are prevalent in organisational structure and impact the female leadership.

The glass ceiling is pointed out to be the most prominent personal factor responsible for obstructing the females in leading at the top level as mentioned by (Cotter et al., 2001), and defined by Schedlitzki and Edwards, (2017). Another factor pointed out as an obstruction is the attitude women have towards their own individuality and talent. Women are found to lack determination and self-esteem in their personalities. This could add up to the list of personal factors influencing female leadership in FinTech start-up organisations.

The factors that could be regarded to be important in influencing the female leaderships from the literature review in the study can be enlisted in four important heads. These heads have also been considered in the analysis of the study. These are social factors, organisational factors, technological and personal factors. Factors like lack of family support and the existence of traditional roles in the society are the major social factors that have been pointed out through earlier studies in the research study. However, these studies didn't examine the impact of these factors on the effectiveness of women leadership in FinTech organisations. Further, the studies did not focus on the impact of the effectiveness of women leaders on the performance of FinTech organisations. In this regard, the present study examined the factors that affect the effectiveness of women leadership in organisations.

Moreover, the study examined the impact of women leaders on the overall performance of the FinTech organisations. The researcher conducted a quantitative analysis to examine the perspective of the employees regarding effective leadership behaviour. In addition to this, the researcher studied organisational, social, technological and personal factors that affect the women leadership in the FinTech industry of the UK. Factors like domination of male over female in the society, the existence of glass ceilings, gender stereotypes, family-related barriers women are less technologically savvy and the existence of orthodox and patriarchal society are

considered in the analysis to devise whether social issues exist in FinTech companies and are they significant enough to impact female leaderships in these organisations.

Socio-cultural factors are seen to impact negatively in promoting female leaders. As pointed out by (Kiamba, 2008; Hoyt, 2010; Okafor, Fagbemi and Hassan, 2011), the age-old thinking is continuing even today. These factors are acting as barriers for women who want to step out and work and earn some social status in society. The women are unable to make a career choice and most of them either work as schoolteachers or are involved in household work.

Due to roles assigned to men and women by society, women find it extremely difficult to look for jobs in organisations because they are hesitant to employ women. Therefore, societal factors impact not only individuals but also FinTech organisations. They lead to a negative influence on female leadership, as pointed out by (Sandberg, 2013). In a similar context, the study of (Kiamba, 2008), proves that women are underrepresented in organisation due to the notion of males being superior leaders, as set by society. To this, Lahti, (2013), points out how these social factors hurt female leadership but these factors are uncontrollable in spreading the negative effect of it. They lead to the dominance of males in education and the employment sphere. The study also points out to the separate jobs that are specified by society to be male and female-dominated along with the prevalence of faulty government policies which demotivate women to work.

The study of Moran, (1992), focused on the organisational factors that have a positive impact on female leadership. The study highlighted that organisations can make it possible to create an environment which promotes female leadership and diversity. It was pointed out through a survey by Talouselämä, (2013), that women have certain notions about them which create a hurdle in their career and progress. Women in organisational settings are given work which does not hold any strategic importance and is generally lower in rank and status. Treatment is unequal for women as opposed to men in promotion and mentoring, as acknowledged by Okafor, Fagbemi and Hassan, (2011) in the literature review.

Lahti, (2013), states that the internal culture and policies of the organisation impact female leadership in a positive way. He claims to mentor and coaching as a way to encourage women

to be leaders. Klaile (2013) postulate glass ceilings and sticky floors concepts of the organisational structure in which females are not allowed by organisational complexities to come to top-level posts, besides the lower pay as compared to men.

(Tanhua, 2012), points out to the negative impact of glass ceilings as a method of obstructing females to move ahead even when they have the potential and the skills to get ahead. Talouselämä, (2013), points out that women as species are low on confidence. Which hampers the determination to achieve their career goals, and therefore, obstruct them exclusively in envisaging themselves as good leaders. (Barreto, Ryan, and Schmitt, 2009), points out to the movements of empowering women, feminists struggles and much more and says that these have not been able to remove such personality issues amongst women.

Lack of networking is another personal factor which is negative for women leadership in FinTech organisations. It is regarded to be important for leaders that principally women possess the skills to network and relate so that their career development can happen (Lussier and Achua, 2013). The factors determined by literature review were first determined to be significant in influencing the female leaderships and were later checked individually to devise out the most significant factor in the four categories i.e. social, organisational, technological and personal.

7.3.3 Contribution to practice

Empirical evidence regarding the role of female leaders in the FinTech sector, particularly start-ups, is limited. This is a drawback because, with lack of empirical evidence, there also lacks a sense of direction for all identified stakeholders i.e.: employees, governments, overall organisations, family and peers, etc. in regards to ways the situation can be improved for the aspiring female leaders. FinTech is a rapidly emerging sector, facing multiple challenges in the face of complexity and dynamism in world markets. It is necessary to know how to influence leaders of such organisations, particularly promising individuals so that they can be encouraged in the right direction, i.e. towards organisational success.

This research contributes to practice in the field of FinTech start-up sector as it identifies the meticulous social, organisational, individual and technological parameters that drive female leaders to achieve organisational success. Governments can utilise the findings of this study to implement necessary changes in the education system of the country and encourage the participation of females in STEM education. Governments can help create “Hybrid females”, such females are given education in science, technology, engineering and maths from the very start of their academic life. If they start developing interest, they are given special training in their chosen theme from the four factors above. There should be more proposals such as HM Treasury’s initiative “Women in Finance Charter”, which supports the progression of women into senior roles in the financial service sector.

Organisations can use the findings to make necessary changes to their work structure, primarily by introducing training and awareness camps specifically targeted towards women employees to encourage their participation in technical tasks and to give them a clearer path towards leadership growth. Awareness campaigns can also be run for educating all employees that the widespread prejudice against female leaders is no longer relevant in the workplace. Moreover, the selection criteria for different positions in the company can be modified to identify the right female candidates suited for the organisation’s vision and policies. FinTech start-ups can become a part of “Women in Finance Charter” which is an initiative started by the HM Treasury. By participation, the firm pledges to build a more gender-balanced and fair industry.

The analysis of this study can contribute to the practice in more than one ways. Since this study is tailored for the FinTech start-ups, the counsels can be used by all the FinTech start-ups not just in the UK but all over the world. Three out of the five surveyed companies of this paper i.e.: Monzo, Nutmeg and Starling are already showing promise in promoting women by pledging to the “Women in Finance Charter”. The other surveyed start-ups of the research Truelayer and Transferwise can start with becoming a member of Women in Finance Charter as approximately 87% of the signatories have met their targets for female representation in senior management and females are getting the right exposure in those companies (Assets.publishing.service.gov.uk, 2019). (Appendix VIII shows the list of 123 signatories of the “Women in Finance Charter”)

The analysis of Women in Charter by the researcher sheds some light on the actual figures which can be beneficial to existing and prospective companies that aspire to increase the number of women leaders. It shows that the manager population in these financial companies are approximately 67,000 out of which 21,500 are women. To meet the target figure companies need to add more 2500 or 12% female in a leadership position. Several changes can be made to improve the number of female leaders but according to the researcher in real-world situations the top three changes would help any FinTech start-up. The top three proposed changes are as follows:

1. **Staffing:** Diversity can play a big part when hiring new staffs especially at senior levels, e.g.: equal or higher representation of female panellists while recruiting senior management or leadership candidates, removing favouritism from the career adverts, using blind CV techniques where the personal details are concealed from the recruiter to remove the prejudice etc.
2. **Adaptable Workplace:** Introduction of family-friendly policies that can help employees to maintain a work-life balance. Adapting the approach that, the job is not merely someplace you go to work but anyplace from where you deliver irrespective of whether you are working in the office environment or from home.
3. **Creation of Hybrid Females:** FinTech start-up leaders are required to be a lot of things at one time, therefore the researcher has come up with an idea of Hybrid Females specifically for the FinTech start-ups. The researcher believes that an ordinary working woman can be converted to an all-rounder individual who is ready to become a female leader. The attributes of a Hybrid Female leader therefore are, a technologically savvy female, someone who has leadership qualities, knows about what is going on in the world around her, she is approachable, she can lead by example, and can direct the team and be part of the team when required. So to create such hybrid females, start-ups should introduce effective mentoring, sponsorship, leadership development programmes, and fill any gaps that exist in women's talent pipeline. Figure 7-1 below shows what is required to create Hybrid females, who can be a successful woman leader in any FinTech start-up company.

Figure 7-1: Definition- Creation and Accomplishment of Hybrid Female for FinTech Start-ups (Researcher)

Figure 7-1, is the researcher's model to create Hybrid females, which can be followed by any FinTech start-up to define, create and accomplish the Hybrid Female leaders. It starts with defining what is Hybrid Females? A Hybrid female is someone who is technologically savvy, has leadership skills, knows what is happening in the world around her, someone who is approachable, managing team and seamlessly being part of the team is a second nature to her.

Defining Hybrid female is not enough hence the researcher has suggested ways to create one. The first step in creating a Hybrid female is to inculcate STEM education from the word go in start-ups, leadership skills are not innate they can be instilled hence leadership workshops can be helpful. To keep one up to date with what is happening around them organisations can introduce debates and discussions on general as well as industry-specific topics every week. Personality development workshops can benefit aspiring women leaders to brush up the skills

which they naturally possess by looking after the family and work simultaneously. And lastly, boot camps and team building activities can nurture them as they climb the path of leadership.

The accomplishment stage should see a female leader who is tech-savvy, well informed, a good listener, a great orator, a decision maker, a problem solver, and last but not the least approachable. By following the above model FinTech start-ups can a leader which ticks all the boxes of leadership. This model offers one main feature of each of the four factors this paper has studied i.e.: Social, Organisational, Technological and Individual. Therefore, in a nutshell, a Hybrid female is a people's person, not intimidated by others and most importantly not intimidating to others.

7.3.4 Future of FinTech

The focus on the customer-centric, Business to Customer (B2C) segment such as retail banking over the near-term is perceived to hold the attention of the FinTech industry. The rate of adoption is higher in this space due to the low cost of switching and technology acceptance by customers. Moreover, FinTech will benefit from the collaboration with banks, as it will provide an opportunity to expand the customer base and develop a service ecosystem around the core offerings.

Over the medium to long term, FinTech players need to challenge their business models as regulatory supervision increases along with the Financial Conduct Authority's scrutiny. They will also need to find adjacencies in the Business to Business (B2B) space.

FinTech comes across more like an urban phenomenon, the UK's rural parts should also be made part of this revolution in the future if the FinTech wants to compete with traditional banking, which is prevalent in urban as well as rural parts of the UK. In the context of women leadership, it would mean more power to the urban and rural women.

Additional new FinTech tools are introduced everyday which makes it complicated to explain to the customers. Customers prefer easy to understand tools which will compel FinTech start-ups to come with easy tools to attract new customers. At the same time, cybersecurity will be

needed to keep the user experience safe and secure so innovation and R&D would be required as an ongoing process in any start-up.

Mobile will be the most important service distribution channel in the future, hence alternative to mobile in the absence of mobile network deems vital for the future of FinTech. Thus, these factors force FinTech players to actively engage with customers over the medium-term.

FinTech start-ups are all about technology, so it will be fundamental to foster the human resource which modernises the technology, therefore there will be an increased need like never before to develop, employ and endorse a culture of collaboration to advance and grow the industry. There will be a greater need for IT in all spheres of banking hence advancing human talents to implement and triumph irrespective of their gender will be a 'new normal'.

Further, FinTech will have to invest in novelty, risk management and building effective partnerships with big financial industry players. Collaboration is the way to success for both banks and FinTech players.

7.4 Future direction

Future studies in this field can focus on any or all of the following.

- 1) **Expanding the study to other tech-related sectors:** This study specifically took into consideration FinTech start-ups only, but there are several other technology companies such as telecom, eCommerce, information technology, etc. which are experiencing a growth in women's participation across all verticals of the workplace. Thus further research can be conducted on such industries where the environment is different and factors might differ.
- 2) **Expanding the study to older firms:** This study took into consideration only start-ups. The primary study was conducted on start-ups only. However, the work environment is different in the case of older firms. Therefore further studies can be

conducted on examining the factors responsible for the success of female leaders in case of older firms, and also of different sizes.

- 3) **Studying males' perspectives of female leaders:** Although the empirical findings of this study through survey included the perspectives of male employees, it would be interesting to find a consensus on the perception of success of female leaders based solely on male employees. It would help create landmark strategies for companies to remove their prejudices, if any, and to recognise the positives in their perspectives that bode well for females at the workplace.
- 4) **Role of education in encouraging female leaders and their success:** Education and technical skills were identified as some of the most crucial factors affecting the success of female workers. Further studies can be conducted on examining their role alone, or even that of the individual, social, technological and organisational separately. A more detailed analysis may result in a better formulation of strategies.

7.5 Recommendations

The findings of the study point towards certain changes required in the social, culture and organisational environment that could encourage more women to act as leaders in the organisations. To motivate the women to take up leadership positions, both the external stakeholders and internal stakeholders need to take up new initiatives. External stakeholders mainly comprise of the government and the internal stakeholders include the investors and senior executives of the organisations.

Primarily, the policies within industries regarding gender discrimination at work and in choosing career path need to be revisited. Also, policies relating to addressing traditional gender roles should be developed by the government to bring out more women into the working population. The government needs to ensure that a minimum 50% of the new appointments comprise of women so that the public boards and committees are rebalanced. For this purpose, the government can introduce the legislations for the under-representation of gender. These legislations must include the sanctions which are similar to other company law sanctions.

These resolutions must represent the clear targets set up by the government to legislate on the progress and this progress must be monitored at regular intervals. This will help in excluding gender bias from leadership skills and treat them as two different aspects. More opportunities for women to be at the top management will be ensured and diversity in leadership styles can be embraced, ensuring more trust and confident confidence of the employees in the organisation.

To develop confidence among the female employees, the members of the board including the chief and senior executives must be trained on equality and diversity issues. They must develop new mechanisms for accountability that can create gender equality across the organisations. In addition to this, the senior leaders must set up targets, strategies and action plans that deliver gender equality. Further, a favourable political and social culture must be inculcated in organisations so that women and men get equal opportunities to move ahead in an organisation. This would eventually increase the number of job opportunities for women at the top management level.

Further, the organisations must develop in house networks through which they can encourage women to take up a challenging role and accept new growth opportunities. Organisations should provide female employees with on the job training, coaching and workshops to help them acquire the required skills to be in touch with the changes that have been made in the organisational and business structure. Addressing gender-imposed restrictions and providing more spaces for women to acquire the technical know-how required by the leading industries for their top management should be the priority of the corporate houses. In addition to this, the organisations must offer leadership development programs for their employees that must be gender-balanced. Further, organisations can develop mentoring opportunities for women wherein women could be mentored under successful men leaders. This would help the existing leader to envisage the female mentee as a future leader. And work as an effective approach to gender neutrality and improve the existing organisational culture. For instance, monthly training sessions can be arranged specifically for the best performing female employees to hone their technical skills (in case it is lacking), and improve their exposure to the technical

aspects of workplace such as expertise in operating certain software applications, critical thinking abilities, leadership education, etc.

Another strategy that the organisation must be able to adopt is setting up a voluntary code of conduct that includes setting the required standards and requirement for equal gender selection. In addition to this, organisations must organise seminars and workshops for women employees to encourage equal participation. These seminars and workshops must motivate the women employees to take up challenging roles that would help the organisations in meeting their goals. Further, the senior executives have to ensure equal participation of women employees in terms of sharing of ideas and opinions in the process of strategic decision making. The women employees must be given the equal opportunity of sharing their ideas and opinions regarding the changes needed in the social and cultural environment of the organisation. This would help the organisations achieve gender neutrality in the workspace.

One of the major responsibilities of the senior executives of the organisation is to ensure that the human resource department adopts best practices in context to the job specifications, advertising strategies and appointment of new employees. These practices include the set of principles for ensuring fairness, openness, and transparency. It is important for the organisation because such transparency will attract worthy job seekers to apply to work with the organisation. For this purpose, the organisations must develop a recruitment style wherein the applications are allocated grades based on their skills, aptitude, and capabilities. In addition to this, the working practices adopted by the organisations must be reviewed and must focus upon retaining the women employees.

Opportunities must be undertaken to support the women employees in context to the career progression. For this purpose, the organisations can assist women in taking measures regarding the work-life balance. There must be active encouragement to support the women after their career breaks for maternity and caring. In addition to this, the organisations must offer transport facilities for the women who are employed at night shifts. This would motivate the employees for greater participation within the organisations. Further, the government must also frame legislations to protect the paid leave offered to the women and must outlaw the discriminatory employment practices.

Government has to transform the education system in a manner that develops gender equality at each level of the education system. The education system must promote gender neutrality from the early years of schooling to higher education and career choice. The education system must frame attention to build confidence among the young women that would help in developing their skills and competencies. In addition to this, the social environment needs to be more gender-inclusive towards educating women in the family. Motivating women to move forward and step up and indulge in active listening and speaking can help cut down the gender gap in workspaces. Further, women must be encouraged to learn new technologies and be inclined towards sectors dealing in IT and new age developments. This could be done by raising children in an environment where both girls and boys have the liberty to explore diverse educational options. They must be able to take up any educational or vocational course according to their choice.

One of the most important aspects that affect women at leadership is the level of job satisfaction. Women must be satisfied working in an organisation and to do so, organisations can provide with the facility of day-care at workplaces so that women with young children are not worried of taking care of their children at home, this would also help single mothers. Family support boosts a women's confidence and helps them move forward in their career path to achieve what they desire. Women employees would be satisfied and self-motivated to work in the organisation and would not have to adjust their careers to be supported by their families. These steps can help ambitious women to concentrate more on their careers alongside their family responsibilities. It would also help them to be loyal to the company and in return help the company to retain talent and eventually promote them as a leader. Lastly, mid-age women should be given some consideration at work during menopause as it is unavoidable, unlike pregnancy. (Lambert, 2016) explains in her telegraph article that a quarter of women around 50 consider cutting down their working hours during their menopausal symptoms. Co-workers are generally unsympathetic and difficult, in addition, occupational health does not give consideration to menopause. This study is about women leadership hence it is imperative for the author to suggest that men and women in FinTech companies should be educated about the

side effects of menopause, and special arrangements should be made when required for female colleagues.

Another key recommendation which can be implemented at the macro level is that of implementing measures to encourage the participation of women in STEM education. Although the perspective of women in this respect is changing for the better, more large-scale measures need to take in order to change the demographics of STEM education participants. For instance, schools can run awareness campaigns at the secondary education level for highlighting the success that female leaders have achieved in the tech domain. Governments can undertake large scale policies like providing free education and training sessions for females in the STEM domain. At a household level, campaigns can be run by organisations in the tech domain to educate parents regarding the potential of females in leadership positions. They can undertake drives that seek to change the general perception regarding female leaders in the workplace.

7.6 Need for the Future Research

Even though the study was conducted strategically to determine the growth phenomena of female leaders in FinTech industry of the UK, there is a need of future research in the field that can be explained as follows:-

The present study was only restricted to the FinTech industry in the UK. This limits the scope of the study it targets only one industry in the UK. The results cannot be generalised for other industries or business sectors. The phenomenon of the growth of female leadership could vary across industries like retail, banking, manufacturing and so on. In addition to this, there could be a broad variation in the perspectives of the employees and managers working in these industries. The future studies conducted must explore the role of women leaders in the retail and manufacturing industries.

The study explored the role of female leadership only in the UK which is a developed country. However, FinTech will be the way forward and women are at par with men in every division

hence the future studies could be expanded across the world. The growing phenomenon of female leadership might vary across developing and developed countries. For this purpose, future research must focus upon the comparative analysis in context to female leadership among the developed and developing countries.

The researcher interviewed 5 managers from the five companies in the FinTech start-ups to determine the factors that led them to success in their industry. In addition to this, under the quantitative analysis, the researcher approached 100 employees from the five companies to understand the effectiveness of women leaders, shortcomings and the future outlook under the leader. Thus, the sample size could generate biases in the results to be generalised for the entire industry, care should be taken when future research is taken up in this field.

The present study examined only the social, organisational, technological and personal factors that could impact the women leadership in the FinTech industry. However, political factors could also impact women leadership among organisations. Factors like the political representation of women in Governments have a significant impact on female leadership but were not explored in the present study. Inclusion of more factors would have helped the study dig deeper into the factors influencing female leaders in organisations. Even the social, organisational, technological and personal factors which were not found in the study should be looked into. In developing countries such as India, Pakistan and Bangladesh many women are suppressed by men and are limited to doing only household chores. Although this happens mostly in rural areas but is still persistent so these women cannot come up and work. For this purpose, future studies must consider the political factors that emerge as an opportunity and challenge for the women leaders in the industry.

The questionnaire for the quantitative study was centred on the researcher's understanding of the situations. These situations were based on secondary data in journals and reports. These were then used in listing the factors that might have had an impact on female leadership in the FinTech companies and might suffer from a design constraint. During interviews, the study was restricted due to time and geographical limitation of the researcher. For further studies, the researcher can rely not only on own understanding but can explore through talking to the

employees to set factors first before placing them into the questionnaire, which in itself can be made a little more open by adding an option of ‘any other factors’ in the questions.

The study conducted in this paper was limited to the perspective of the employees working in the management and lower levels. The future research must examine all four factors discussed here plus the other relevant factors such as political factors etc. at all the levels of an organisation to make it more inclusive and relevant to all the females irrespective of their position.

Lastly, a comparative study can be conducted to check the difference in the handling of women employees in traditional banking versus FinTech start-ups. It will be interesting to see how traditional banking is dealing with the new normal of women being at par with their men counterparts.

7.7 Epilogue

In the global competitive era in which the firms compete in terms of modern technology that improves the business operations, the expansion of the digital platforms has widened the scope of the FinTech industry. Due to this, the industry demands highly competent leaders who could help the organisations in achieving their targeted goals.

The literature highlighted that women can function as effective leaders in the FinTech industry. However, the extent of success the women leaders can achieve depends on the social, organisational and personal factors.

The results of the qualitative analysis indicated that the organisations must encourage equal participation of the women. Additionally, women must be competent enough to keep up with technological and financial innovations.

Many studies developed a framework to establish a connection between the drivers and the successful female leaders within the FinTech industry. These studies stated organisations consider men to be a better fit at the leadership position. To this, the findings of the qualitative

analysis highlighted that managers working in the FinTech industry are of the view that the female leaders are equally effective as the male leaders. The women leaders frame a long term vision for the company and correspondingly, have to stand up to the expectations of the organisations in terms of the tasks and outcomes.

In the context of the organisational factors that affect the women leadership, the findings of the study indicated that the glass ceiling is a major barrier that obstructs the females in leading the top-level position. On the other hand, the attitude of the women has emerged to be an important personal factor that impacts the success of female leadership in the organisations.

Concerning the social factors, family support and assignment of traditional roles to the women have emerged to the most important factors that negatively impact the female leadership in the FinTech industry. This is due to the specific roles which are assigned to the men and women which make it extremely difficult for the women to look for better opportunities.

Technological factors are equally important especially as the study is centred around the FinTech start-ups. Hybrid women can equal their score with men as women inherently are considered to be diligent, passionate, punctual and rearing to go if their talent is tapped and utilised at the right time. Progressive sector such as FinTech start-ups can lead and make a difference to many aspiring women's lives and other sectors can follow the lead.

Many personal factors that affect the female leadership include networking, diversification, self-belief and emotional intelligence. These findings indicated that the women must be able to build up strong teams which are goal-oriented. In addition to this, creativity and initiative ability would help the women leaders in generating more ideas which would positively impact the effectiveness of the organisations.

Among these factors, the personal factors were found to be the least influencing. On the other hand, social factors have a major impact on the effectiveness of female leadership. To eradicate these barriers, organisations and society need to focus on the removal of gender stereotypes within the industry. The organisations must frame policies that provide equal opportunities to women. This would create a healthy competition among the employees and would offer greater job satisfaction to the women employees now and in the future.

The researcher would like to end this research in the words of Sarah Williams- Gardener (Fintech Finance issue 8, 2019) who is a co-founder of Starling Bank. (The UK's first all-digital FinTech start-up). She was asked, "You are also a farmer. What can banking learn from farming?" to which she responded: *"What I have learned from this wonderful, hardworking community is- what we do today affects what happens tomorrow. A farmer is always thinking about the environment and the next generation"*. Therefore by making today's women more capable of being leaders in the financial technology start-up sector, which is mainly dominated by men we will make a way forward for the strong women leaders of the future. From "Suffragettes" to "Women in Finance Charter", women of the UK has come a long way and there is no looking back.

The contemporary addition to gender diversity is the statue of a "Fearless Girl" (shown in the picture below) which was presented outside the London Stock Exchange in encouragement of larger female representation on corporate boards.

"If your actions create a legacy that inspires others to dream more, learn more, do more and become more, then, you are an excellent leader."

- Dolly Parton (Rampton, 2019)

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Fearless Girl Statue outside London Stock Exchange: *“Know the Power of Women Leadership”*

by Kristen Visbal

(BBC News, 2019)

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APPENDIX- I

Following are the open-ended questions asked to the respondents in the context of qualitative analysis. This was given to the 5 women managers of the 5 FinTech start-ups companies.

INTERVIEW QUESTIONS FOR FINTECH START-UPS IN THE UK

- 1) What is the best and worst decision you've ever made?
- 2) What was your dream job as a child and why?
- 3) What do you think is the most significant barrier to female leadership?
- 4) What woman inspires you and why?
- 5) What will be the biggest challenge for the generation of women behind you?
- 6) How do you balance work and life responsibilities?
- 7) Do women in your profession face difficulties in getting promoted?
- 8) As a female leader, what has been the most significant barrier in your career?
- 9) Who inspired you irrespective of the gender and why?
- 10) What advice would you give to the next generation of female leaders?
- 11) Have you ever been afraid on the job?
- 12) Do you experience resistance when you are leading men?
- 13) What is some of the advice you share with young women entering a male-dominated profession?
- 14) When you began your career many years ago, did you ever imagine that you would be a leader in a male-dominated profession?
- 15) Define a great leader. What are some traits you think great leaders possess?
- 16) What are some strategies that can help women achieve a more prominent role in their organisations?
- 17) What's one leadership lesson you've learned in your career?
- 18) Tell me a little bit about yourself.
- 19) What's a typical day like for you?
- 20) How do you motivate yourself and stay motivated?

- 21) If you had to start over from scratch, knowing what you know now, what would you do differently?
- 22) What's the most important business or other discovery you've made in the past year?
- 23) What are the three threats to your business, your success, and how are you handling them?
- 24) What's unique about the service that you provide?
- 25) Describe a major business or other challenge you had and how you resolved it.
- 26) What lessons did you learn in the process?
- 27) Describe one of your biggest failures. What lessons did you learn, and how did it contribute to a greater success?
- 28) What has been your biggest disappointment in your life – and what are you doing to prevent its reoccurrence?
- 29) What's one of the toughest decisions you've had to make and how did it impact your life?
- 30) What are the three events that helped to shape your life?
- 31) What's an accomplishment that you are proud of?
- 32) How did mentors influence your life?
- 33) What's one core message you received from your mentors?

APPENDIX II

QUALITATIVE QUESTIONNAIRE

This questionnaire is part of my Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) thesis. It purports to understand the perception of women in the leadership position of this organisation on their strategies to carry on their core responsibilities. Further, this questionnaire includes aspects such as obstacles, challenges, career advancement opportunities, etc. that you have experienced over the due course. Later, certain key factors which have influenced your overall journey as a leader and to become a leader have been included to obtain a holistic purview of your entire journey in the FinTech sector of the United Kingdom.

Section A: Demographic Profile

1. Name: _____
2. Age: _____
3. Organisation Name: _____
4. YearsofExperienceinLeadershipPosition:

5. Your marital status?
 - Single
 - Married
 - Widowed
 - Divorced
6. Do you stay with your family?
 - Yes
 - No
 - Can't say
7. Are there any dependents in your family? If yes, how many?

Yes, <= 3

Yes, >= 3

No

8. Do you have children?

Yes

No

Can't say

9. If yes, how many?

1

2

3

4

>= 5

Section B: Perception on Leadership Strategies

3. Being at a leadership position, how do you think managing a FinTech company differs from other sectors?

4. Is leadership gender neutral in your organisation? Or have you noticed a change in culture of leadership appointment in your organisation?

strongly
disagree

disagree

undecided

agree

strongly agree

5. If no to question 2, why do you think so?

6. If yes to question 2, how that has helped you or similar leaders to availing opportunities to rise to the top?

7. Do you think there is a shift in women's personal characteristics to succeed in leadership roles, in recent period?

8. Do you think there exists gender specific leadership benefits? Like women leaders bring more benefits over their male counterparts or vice-versa?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

9. What benefits do female leaders bring to organisations?

10. What do you think are the best tools to increase the number of women in leadership positions? For example, quotas, mentoring, general discussion, etc.?

	Strongly disagree	disagree	undecided	agree	strongly agree
quotas					
mentoring					
general discussion					
Others, please specify					

11. State reasons behind your answer to question 8, providing an instance from your experience.

—

12. Which aspects or events do you consider to have advanced your career the most?
How?

—

13. Which aspects or events have you considered as obstacles or speed bumps in
your career, if any and in brief how?

—

14. What do you think are the most important qualities and characteristics of a good
leader?

—

15. Have you experienced your gender/femininity to be in the way of your career
development?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

16. With respect to your answer to question 12, state your reasons with instance.

Section C: Factors leading to success in Industry

17. What are the main factors that influence women's rise to leadership positions?

18. Do you think societal standards, expectations and customs towards organisations and individuals help women achieve success in the workplace?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

19. Can you relate any such situations where the above factors (ques. 15) actually helped you achieve success, or otherwise?

-

20. Is gender relevant, or should only professional skills be emphasised when considering leadership and managers? Or is it necessary to better women's position in working life in certain ways, because there are other obstacles, which are not related to professional skills?

-

21. According to a study by McKinsey & company, leadership styles which are more commonly used by women (feminine leadership) are more suitable in facing new trends, such as social and environmental trends, than traditional leadership. Do you think it is easier for women to become managers at the moment and even more so in the future? Why do you think it is / is not?

-

Section D: Challenges faced in the leadership position

22. Do you think women are underrepresented in senior management in FinTech companies of the UK?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

–

23. State the reasons behind your answer for the above question.

–

24. What are the ways do you think to increase the number of women in leadership positions?

–

25. Do you think your team members prefer working under a male leader over female leader?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

–

26. Have you experienced any such instance of male leader preference? If so, what was your way of handling the situation?

–

27. What suggestions would you like to give to the FinTech sector/organisations to make women's rise to the leadership position conducive?

–

Any other comments?

Thanks for participating!

APPENDIX III

QUANTITATIVE QUESTIONNAIRE

This questionnaire is part of my Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) thesis. It purports to understand your perception about the effectiveness of your leader (women) and to derive factors/elements which contribute to their overall success. The entire questionnaire consists of 6 sections (A to F), wherein following your demographic profiles, specific questions have been asked on your organisation and the women leaders you work under. The leader can be your immediate supervisor or department manager. You are not supposed to assume any answer and only provide which resembles the actual reality.

Section 1: Demographic Profile

1. Name: _____
2. Position: _____
3. Organisation Name: _____
4. What is your age?
 - 21-30 years
 - 31-40 years
 - 41-50 years
 - Above 50 years
5. What is your gender?
 - Male
 - Female
6. For how long have you been associated with your present organisation?
 - Less than 5 years
 - 5 – 10 years
 - 10 – 15 years

15 – 20 years

More than 20 years

Section B – General Background

7. Does your organisation have women leaders?

Yes

No

Can't Say

8. Do you think women leaders are better than or as effective as male leaders?

Yes

No

Can't Say

9. Which of the following leadership functions are being performed by your leader? (Tick all those apply)

Developing the Vision,

Sharing the Goals

Gaining Support

Delivering Success

Others (Please specify): _____

10. Which of the following leadership competencies are being possessed by your leader?

(Tick all those apply)

Persuading and Influencing

Communicating

Meeting Customer Needs

Relating and Networking

Taking Risks

Creating and Innovating

Section C: Effective Leadership behaviours

Rate the following on the basis of the effective leadership behaviour possessed by leader in your organisation on a scale on 1-5 with 1 being Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Cannot Say, 4= Agree and 5= Strongly Agree. (Tick the correct alternative).

Behaviours	1	2	3	4	5
1 Participative Decision Making	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2 Role Model	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3 Inspiration	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4 Expectations and Rewards	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5 People Development	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6 Intellectual Stimulation	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7 Efficient Communication	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8 Individualistic Decision Making	<input type="checkbox"/>				
9 Control and Corrective Action	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section D: Factors impacting Women Leader

Factors impacting Women Leader

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Organisational Factors

- | | | | | | |
|------------------------------|--|-------|--|--|--|
| 1 | Organisations have their own particular work environment with its own values, which is a legacy of past leaders, as well as current leadership | | | | |
| 2 | Leaders are dependent on organisational resources, such as staff, technology, finances and physical resources to achieve their goals. | | | | |
| 3 | Organisational culture that establishes rites, such as rituals, routines and a set way of doing things impacts company norms, such as how a worker can be in good standing and how a worker can respond appropriately for various circumstances which then impacts the leaders | | | | |
| 4 | Organisational setting | | | | |
| 5 | Types of Management style (change management, managing conflict, performance indicators and management) followed in organisations that effects the leaders | | | | |
| individual/ personal factors | | <hr/> | | | |
| 7 | Personality of leader | | | | |
| 8 | Individual needs of a leader | | | | |

9 Competence of leader

--	--	--	--	--

10 Confidence and courage of the leader

--	--	--	--	--

11 Creativity and initiative ability of a leader

--	--	--	--	--

Society Factors

12 The women are considered to be inferior to the male counterparts

--	--	--	--	--

13 Existence of phenomenon's like glass ceiling

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14 Gender stereotyping

--	--	--	--	--

15 Family related barriers

--	--	--	--	--

16 Orthodox and believing in patriarchy system

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Section E: Effectiveness of Women Leader

Rate the following on the basis of perception of the women leader in your organisation on a scale on 1-5 with 1 being Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Cannot Say, 4= Agree and 5= Strongly Agree. (Tick the correct alternative)¹

Effectiveness Parameters

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

¹Parameters based on Eagly (2007), Female leadership advantage and disadvantage: resolving the contradictions, *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 31, pp. 1-12

- | | | | | | | |
|---|---|--|--|--|--|--|
| 1 | She is a visionary who challenges the old order and way of doing things. | | | | | |
| 2 | She is competent in managing change and planning and organising | | | | | |
| 3 | She is able to develop a specific vision for and a plan for implementing change. | | | | | |
| 4 | She has the interpersonal skills to inspire employees to embrace and deliver the vision and strategy | | | | | |
| 5 | She is an effective change agent because she is creative, empathetic and able to deal with the concerns of colleagues and employees who may be resistant to change. | | | | | |
| 6 | She understands the importance of achieving corporate objectives in order to advance the organisation | | | | | |
| 7 | She demonstrates qualities that motivate respect and pride from association with him or her | | | | | |
| 8 | She communicates values, purpose, and importance of organisation's mission | | | | | |
| 9 | She exhibits optimism and excitement about goals and future states | | | | | |
-

- | | | | | | | | |
|----|---|--|--|--|--|--|--|
| 10 | She examines new perspectives for solving problems and completing tasks | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 25px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td> </tr> </table> | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | |
| 11 | She focuses on development and mentoring of followers and attends to their individual needs | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 25px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td> </tr> </table> | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | |
| 12 | She provides rewards for satisfactory performance by followers | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 25px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td> </tr> </table> | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | |
| 13 | She attends to followers' mistakes and failures to meet standards | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 25px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td> </tr> </table> | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | |
| 14 | She waits until problems become severe before attending to them and intervening | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 25px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td> </tr> </table> | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | |
| 15 | She exhibits frequent absence and lack of involvement during critical junctures | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 25px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td> </tr> </table> | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | |

Section F: Shortcoming of Women Leader

Rate the following on the basis of shortcoming of the women leader in your organisation on a scale on 1-5 with 1 being Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Cannot Say, 4= Agree and 5= Strongly Agree. (Tick the correct alternative)

- | | | | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| Shortcomings | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 25px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px; text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px; text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px; text-align: center;">3</td> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px; text-align: center;">4</td> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px; text-align: center;">5</td> </tr> </table> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | | |
| 1 She is not intellectually inspiring | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 25px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td> </tr> </table> | | | | | |
| | | | | | | |
| 2 She does not possess the individualistic decision-making competency | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 25px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td> </tr> </table> | | | | | |
| | | | | | | |

- | | | |
|----|--|--|
| 3 | She is not able to control the difficult scenarios and situations that arise. | |
| 4 | She does not take corrective actions for mistakes made | |
| 5 | She Distances herself and behaves arrogantly to those She leads | |
| 6 | She lacks accountability and courage while handling her or the team's performance | |
| 7 | she rarely works collaboratively with her team members and lacks trust over her team | |
| 8 | there is rarely any scope of diversity of thoughts, actions and delegation of responsibilities under my leader | |
| 9 | she is more result-oriented than being considerate on accountability, tasks, processes, people, and outcomes | |
| 10 | She lacks emotional intelligence | |
| 11 | She has limiting abilities to influence, adapt to culture, and "fit-in" organisationally and impersonally | |

Section G: Impact of the leadership on team/organisational performance

Based on your perception of your leaders' behaviour, effectiveness and shortcomings, rate the degree of performance achieved by your team/organisation. Rate on a scale of 1-5 with 1 being

Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Cannot Say, 4= Agree and 5= Strongly Agree. (Tick the correct alternative)²

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

1	Work environment and values Shape employee interactions and foster a shared understanding of values	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2	Vision Articulate where the team/organisation is heading, how to reach goal and align people.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3	Co-ordination And Control Measure and evaluate business performance and risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4	External Orientation Engage in constant two-way interactions with customers, suppliers and other partners	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5	Motivation	<input type="checkbox"/>				

² Questionnaire based on Women Matter (2007) Report by Mckinsey & Company (<https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/organisation/our-insights/gender-diversity-a-corporate-performance-driver>)

Inspire and encourage employees/team members to perform and stay

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6 Capability

--	--	--	--	--

Ensure internal skills and talent to support strategy and create competitive advantage

--	--	--	--	--

7 Accountability

--	--	--	--	--

Design structure/reporting relationships and evaluate individual performance to ensure accountability and responsibility for business results.

--	--	--	--	--

8 Innovation

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Generate flow of ideas to that the team/organisation adapt to dynamic business needs and environmental changes

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9 Inspiration

Ensure shaping and inspiring the actions of others to drive better performance

Thank you!

APPENDIX IV

INTERVIEW TRANSCRIPT (interviewee A)

Section A: Demographic Profile

- 1) Name: _____
- 2) Age: 35 _____
- 3) Organisation Name: _____
- 4) YearsofExperienceinLeadershipPosition:

- 5) Your marital status?
- 6) Single
- 7) Do you stay with your family?
- 8) No
- 9) Are there any dependents in your family? If yes, how many?
- 10) Yes, ≤ 3
- 11) Do you have children?
- 12) No
- 13) If yes, how many?
- 14) 1 2 3 4 ≥ 5
- 15) Section B: Perception on Leadership Strategies
- 16) Being at a leadership position, how do you think managing a FinTech company differs from other sectors?

Managing a FinTech is always different than other sector as change in other company is a one-time phenomenon, but that is not the case in fintech. You always have new technology such as artificial intelligence and big data along with new products to be on a look out for to add value for the customers.

17) Is leadership gender neutral in your organisation? Or have you noticed a change in culture of leadership appointment in your organisation?

STRONGLY disagree undecided agree strongly agree
DISAGREE

Strongly Agree, the organisation that I work for is supportive of gender neutrality. As an organisation we choose to believe that there are different kinds of leadership behaviour that apply to men as well as women. As a firm and as an efficient leader we believe in inclusive organisation and there would not be a change in gender neutral leadership in this organisation.

18) If no to question 2, why do you think so?

19) If yes to question 2, how that has helped you or similar leaders to availing opportunities to rise to the top?

4.1 Having a gender neutral organisation is helpful for leaders that share the vision that gender and leadership skill are exclusive characteristics. It has also help us set a trends and open doors for female managers to advance into the leadership roles. It ensures to set industrial trends and set benchmark in diversity in leadership in different sections of the economy. For similar leaders to availing opportunities to rise to the top having a gender neutral organisation provides them with encouragement. It gives them the confidence of taking more risks and having trust in them.

20) Do you think there is a shift in women's personal characteristics to succeed in leadership roles, in recent period?

I agree that there is a requirement for shift in women personal characteristics for them to succeed as leaders and these changes are slowly happening in UK. As the FinTech segment

needs talent base that can be enhanced by skills of software development, coding, and financial management skills women are required to develop analytical and strategic skills.

21) Do you think there exists gender specific leadership benefits? Like women leaders bring more benefits over their male counterparts or vice-versa?

STRONGLY disagree undecided agree strongly agree
DISAGREE

Strongly Disagree I do not confirm with the notion of gender specific leadership benefits. I Think leadership is style dependent. People point out that women leadership style is coaching and compassionate in nature that allows subordinates to grow. However, I do not agree that coaching style can only be practised by women. There are male leaders in the industry as well that employ coaching leadership to ensure their organisational success.

22) What benefits do female leaders bring to organisations?

Apart from bringing gender diversity, female leadership positively impacts firm's performance positively. Female leadership enhances contemporary diversity for firm in the marketplaces. It brings innovativeness as well as market reputation for the company.

23) What do you think are the best tools to increase the number of women in leadership positions? (For example, quotas, mentoring, general discussion, etc.)?

Strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree
quotas
mentoring
general discussion

Others, please specify

8.1	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Strongly agree – Equal Opportunity
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24) State reasons behind your answer to question 7, providing an instance from your experience.

I think innovation is fundamentally a result of trial and error, in my journey to this leadership position; I have put efforts to contribute creatively to the firm. All firms have products, however, it is only through diversity in the marketplace can leadership be achieved. I have always work towards bringing different skills to the process that has helped guiding my own female leadership journey.

25) Which aspects or events do you consider to have advanced your career the most? How?

Work Environment and value, both these parameter act as guiding principle to ensure gender inclusion in an organisation. With women in leadership position further, these parameters can be augmented to improve overall organisational performance.

26) Which aspects or events have you considered as obstacles or speed bumps in your career? If any? Brief how?

I have been fortunate enough to have been working for a gender neutral organisations throughout my career. These organisations have moulded my leadership positively and ensured that I contribute to organisational growth as well.

27) What do you think are the most important qualities and characteristics of a good leader?

Accountability is the most important qualities for me. As a good leader, when you take personal accountability and are willing to answer for outcomes of actions and choices they present them as role models.

28) Have you experienced your gender/femininity to be in the way of your career development?

STRONGLY disagree undecided agree strongly agree
DISAGREE

strongly disagree

29) With respect to your answer to question 12, state your reasons with instance.

In divisional meetings, often we have to present the summary of innovative and creative products launched in a period of last three months. There was an occasions when there were no new products to present. As a leader it was my accountability to bear the loss.

Section C: Factors leading to success in Industry

30) What are the main factors that influence women's rise to leadership positions?

According to me, talent with respect to the prevailing technology can influence women's rise to leadership position. Contextual knowledge is the key to succeed in any industry and female employees with high knowledge base of industry and talent will surely rise to leadership position.

31) Do you think societal standards, expectations and customs towards organisations and individuals help women achieve success in the workplace?

STRONGLY
DISAGREE

disagree

undecided

agree

strongly agree

16.1 Agree

32) Can you relate any such situations where the above factors (ques. 15) actually helped you achieve success, or otherwise?

Yes, I can relate to several situations where contextual knowledge and know-how of prevailing technology has been of help in my success. Specifically in the technological era that we live in today, as a leader you ought to know about the uses of AI that can help you in predicting consumer behaviour and big data so that you are able to design more relatable FinTech products. These technological usage have helped me grow our product base and enabled me to focus in consumer driven products rather than first designing the product and then choosing the customers.

33) Is gender relevant, or should only professional skills be emphasised when considering leadership and managers? Or is it necessary to better women's position in working life in certain ways, because there are other obstacles, which are not related to professional skills?

As a leader I think gender is an irrelevant factor in deciding leadership. Just chances in form of equal opportunity and professional skills will be enough to guide more female leaders to success.

34) According to a study by Mckinsey & company, leadership styles which are more commonly used by women (feminine leadership) are more suitable in facing new trends, such as social and environmental trends, than traditional leadership. Do you

think it is easier for women to become managers at the moment and even more so in the future? Why do you think it is / is not?

I think with more women in the leadership position and several institutions especially in the FinTech industry now recognising women's growing influence and affluence in leadership, it is becoming a trend. The organisations are aligned to use diversity in leadership in the future as well. I think it is okay to take capitalise the advantage gender diversity has to offer. Although, I would say, it is still time for women leadership to become a phenomenon across different industries.

Section D: Challenges faced in the leadership position

35) Do you think women are underrepresented in senior management in FinTech companies of UK?

STRONGLY
DISAGREE

disagree

undecided

agree

strongly agree

36) State the reasons behind your answer for the above question.

Although, I have been fortunate to have a career with organisations that do not believe in gender disparity, I agree that women are underrepresented in senior management in FinTech companies of UK as I think there are opportunities for both women leaders and organisations to utilise.

37) What are the ways do you think to increase the number of women in leadership positions?

Female population need more of infrastructural support system that is inclined to provide technological know-how. This along with opportunity is needed to mould female leadership.

38) Do you think your team members prefer working under a male leader over female leader?

STRONGLY
DISAGREE

disagree

undecided

agree

strongly agree

39) Have you experienced any such instance of male leader preference? If so, what was your way of handling the situation?

I have never experienced any such instances where my team has preferred to work under male leadership.

40) What suggestions would you like to give to the FinTech sector/organisations to make women's rise to the leadership position conducive?

In FinTech organisations, there is a need to recognise gender imposed restrictions and design gender sensitive policy in the industry.

Interviewee B

Section A: Demographic Profile

- Name: _____
- Age: 36_____
- Organisation Name: _____
- YearsofExperienceinLeadershipPosition:4

- Your marital status?
- Married
- Do you stay with your family?

Yes

- Are there any dependents in your family? If yes, how many?
- Yes, <= 3
- Do you have children?
- Yes
- If yes, how many?

Section B: Perception on Leadership Strategies

1. Being at a leadership position, how do you think managing a FinTech company differs from other sectors?

Fintech, unlike other industry are not for compliant professional. You would have to embrace change as essential parameter for organisational as well as leadership growth.

2. Is leadership gender neutral in your organisation? Or have you noticed a change in culture of leadership appointment in your organisation?

Disagree

3. If no to question 2, why do you think so?

Disagree, although I hold a leadership position in my firm, I don't agree that leadership is gender neutral. But, I would also state that gender diversity is more in the FinTech than other sectors. Leadership is a step-by-step process and gender statistics at executive level only are not equal to provide women an equal chance at leadership. Women employment trends at the base level should be high enough to promote more women at leadership position.

4. If yes to question 2, how that has helped you or similar leaders to availing opportunities to rise to the top?

-

5. Do you think there is a shift in women's personal characteristics to succeed in leadership roles, in recent period?

I would say that this shift is happening unevenly across the sectors and at a slow pace as well. Collaboration of personal characteristic with leadership has to start from junior college. Although, there are more female students opting for STEM (science, technology, engineering and maths) subjects, inclusion of strategic studies can ensure that female leadership is a movement and not a gesture.

6. Do you think there exists gender specific leadership benefits? Like women leaders bring more benefits over their male counterparts or vice-versa?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

6.2 Agree. The gender specific benefits however, are perceived more than in actual. As I think similar behaviour of male and female leaders produces different effects on subordinate outcomes. The leadership become context dependent.

7. What benefits do female leaders bring to organisations?

Female leadership improves decision-making by increasing comprehensive diversity in the firm. Female leadership endows benefits of enhanced productivity and innovativeness. Firms with larger representation of female leaders as board members have seen to have higher return on equity, they demonstrate more frequently people development skill. They act as role model and inspire other women employees in the company to achieve high as well.

8. What do you think are the best tools to increase the number of women in leadership positions? (For example, quotas, mentoring, general discussion, etc.)?

Strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

quotas

mentoring

general discussion

Others, please specify

8.2	disagree	Strongly agree	agree	Strongly agree – Gender inclusion in employee at executive level
-----	----------	----------------	-------	--

9. State reasons behind your answer to question 7, providing an instance from your experience.

When I say women leadership bring innovativeness to the firm it is a result that comes from a wide-ranging set of influences at the decision-making level that female leaders bring to the

firm. People development skill has often enabled me to take the team together in different organisational decision.

10. Which aspects or events do you consider to have advanced your career the most? How?

The aspect of accountability has helped me advance in my career the most. In my early years of training, the first task in which I was appointed to lead provided me an opportunity to see that I have the capability of leading a team.

11. Which aspects or events have you considered as obstacles or speed bumps in your career? If any? Brief how?

11.2 Culture and Mind-set regarding female leadership prevents sustainable environment that is required for more women to take up leadership roles. First need is to provide women with unique opportunity that they can use to succeed.

12. What do you think are the most important qualities and characteristics of a good leader?

Team Building and collaboration ability are qualities of a good leader that I think is most important. Female leaders display horizontal communication style that is based on the principles of equality and team building. It enables the leaders to develop the ability to sense internal conflict and ensure action to resolve difficult situation.

13. Have you experienced your gender/femininity to be in the way of your career development?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

14. With respect to your answer to question 12, state your reasons with instance.

Change is a constant in FinTech without team building and collaborative effort surviving even a day is very difficult. In product feasibility analysis you have to ensure that marketing as well as accounting department are on the same page. Having the capability of horizontal communication comes as an advantage to ensure there are no miscommunications or internal conflict.

Section C: Factors leading to success in Industry

15. What are the main factors that influence women's rise to leadership positions?

The prominent factor that influences the rise of women to leadership roles is presence of glass ceiling in any organisation. The implied restriction that a woman employee feels while disposing her duties enhance individualistic struggle that women go through in their leadership development.

16. Do you think societal standards, expectations and customs towards organisations and individuals help women achieve success in the workplace?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

17. Can you relate any such situations where the above factors (ques. 15) actually helped you achieve success, or otherwise?

Although I have been fortunate that my organisation is among the few that does not aligns disposal of duties as a gender related phenomenon, I have always been aware that there does exists a glass ceiling. The presence of this phenomenon has always ensured that I take those extra bits of effort to ensure my leadership is inclusive.

18. Is gender relevant, or should only professional skills be emphasised when considering leadership and managers? Or is it necessary to better women's position in working life

in certain ways, because there are other obstacles, which are not related to professional skills?

With the kind of disparity that exists between male and female leadership today, I would prefer that women are preferred while considering leadership. It is required to attain equality of representation. I also agree that there are obstacles other than professional skills that have long stood in the path of women leadership success. There is a deep social and cultural change that is required to provide women with equal opportunity in the first place. I think those women who reach the top position in spite of such difficulties are liable for some preferential treatment.

19. According to a study by McKinsey & company, leadership styles which are more commonly used by women (feminine leadership) are more suitable in facing new trends, such as social and environmental trends, than traditional leadership. Do you think it is easier for women to become managers at the moment and even more so in the future? Why do you think it is / is not?

With more women taking up subjects such as mathematics, computer science, and analytics the future of women leaders are brighter. I think it is time that women recognise their promotional and leadership roles this would facilitate the organisations to be informed of their priorities and goals. There are healthy talent in the pipeline that are looking for opportunity. Equality is a boost that female leadership needs to continue growing in the future as well.

Section D: Challenges faced in the leadership position

20. Do you think women are underrepresented in senior management in FinTech companies of UK?

strongly
disagree

disagree

undecided

agree

strongly agree

21. State the reasons behind your answer for the above question.

I strongly agree that women are under-represented as there are more male senior partners in FinTech than women. These statistics have guided my answers to the above question.

22. What are the ways do you think to increase the number of women in leadership positions?

More female students taking up STEM studies will increase their leadership chances as well. Internally in the company, I think female employee should be provided with required motivation that can help them take up challenging roles as well.

23. Do you think your team members prefer working under a male leader over female leader?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

24. Have you experienced any such instance of male leader preference? If so, what was your way of handling the situation?

Men are aggressive and dominant, this instance of preferential male leadership occurred in a team conflict-handling process. When two-members aggravated a personal situation at work, common prejudice of perceived incongruity occurred and the entire team was of the opinion that I would not be the correct person to manage the conflict. I ensured understanding between the two team members and ensured that gender norm stereotypes did not come in the way to my leadership positions.

25. What suggestions would you like to give to the FinTech sector/organisations to make women's rise to the leadership position conducive?

There are several measures that can be adopted to make leadership position conducive to women's rise in organisation. Addressing gender parity in both payment and promotion are contributions that industry can provide to promote female leadership. If the organisations align their internal culture to reduce parameters of social and cultural barrier, it will also have positive impact on acceptance of more women in the industry in leadership roles.

Interviewee C

Section A: Demographic Profile

1. Name: _____
2. Age: 35 _____
3. Organisation Name: _____
4. YearsofExperienceinLeadershipPosition:5

5. Your marital status?
6. Single
7. Do you stay with your family?

No
8. Are there any dependents in your family? If yes, how many?
9. No
10. Do you have children?
11. No
12. If yes, how many?

1 2 3 4 >= 5

Section B: Perception on Leadership Strategies

13. Being at a leadership position, how do you think managing a FinTech company differs from other sectors?

Being at the leadership position for last 5 years, I think that managing FinTech company is essentially about survival. The more you are able to add value to the consumers the more they will depend on you for their different needs and as FinTech encompasses all products of banking and even extend beyond their products such as technical aspects of using big data, the industry will always keep you on your toes.

14. Is leadership gender neutral in your organisation? Or have you noticed a change in culture of leadership appointment in your organisation?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

Disagree

15. If no to question 2, why do you think so?

3.3 Disagree. Business that are reported to have been led by women have helped in improving long term economic gains for the firms. This can also be tied up to the boosted female leadership provides to the nation's GDP. However, to pave the path for female leadership, gender inequality should be addressed at the very beginning at executive level in the firms. Low hiring trends and unequal pay act like inhibitors in the path of female leadership process. Gender parity needs to be addressed from the root level to ensure FinTech as well as other similar sectors get to see more female leaders.

16. If yes to question 2, how that has helped you or similar leaders to availing opportunities to rise to the top?

N/A

17. Do you think there is a shift in women's personal characteristics to succeed in leadership roles, in recent period?

I think that there is no requirement to change personal characteristic of women to ensure that they succeed in leadership roles. They are as capable as their male counterparts to do so provided they are provided with the same opportunities. Environment that we grow into shape who we are if we are able to ensure gender inclusion in the talent base specially in junior college level, we would see more women leaders.

18. Do you think there exists gender specific leadership benefits? Like women leaders bring more benefits over their male counterparts or vice-versa?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

Strongly Agree. I think the gender roles restrict the leadership roles and personal factors, such as domestic responsibility and level of confidence with which she balances her work-life makes women a better leader. Secondly, innovative skills of handling different situation at work that are displayed by female bring more benefit than their male counterparts.

19. What benefits do female leaders bring to organisations?

Female leader are participative decision making they display more expectations and rewards. Apart from bringing diversity in the strategic decision making for the firms, female leadership enhances innovation and creative development.

20. What do you think are the best tools to increase the number of women in leadership positions? (For example, quotas, mentoring, general discussion, etc.)?

Strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

quotas

mentoring

general discussion

Others, please specify

21. State reasons behind your answer to question 7, providing an instance from your experience.

My answer to what female leaders bring to firm is based on my experience of my own firm. Since the beginning of my career journey, I have concentrated my efforts in building a team atmosphere. Throughout my leadership journey I have ensured that all strategic decisions are dealt with in a participative approach to ensure that creativity of each team member is enhanced.

22. Which aspects or events do you consider to have advanced your career the most? How?

Work environment and equal opportunity are two aspects that I would like to highlight as aspects that have helped in advance in my career. Since my first on the job training I had a chance to work with gender neutral leaders.

23. Which aspects or events have you considered as obstacles or speed bumps in your career? If any? Brief how?

Lack of role models, there are only few examples of women who have succeeded in attain important leadership positions. There needs to developmental culture that can provide women with competitive edge and ensure that they are provided with opportunities to succeed.

24. What do you think are the most important qualities and characteristics of a good leader?

As female entrepreneur you also have to display accountability. This accountability is required for both team performance as well as boosting the employment for more woman employee in the organisation. Ensuring inclusion will also ensure that they attain high-ranking leadership roles as well.

25. Have you experienced your gender/femininity to be in the way of your career development?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

26. With respect to your answer to question 12, state your reasons with instance.

One of the situation where I have ensured accountability as a female leader is ensuring a gender neutral hiring process in my organisation. As a woman in leadership position, I think I am liable for developing an inclusive organisation that allows equal chance for both male and female employees in the organisation.

Section C: Factors leading to success in Industry

27. What are the main factors that influence women's rise to leadership positions?

Traditional gender roles are the prominent among all factors to impact leadership amongst women. The common example stated is women work less than men. This can only be encountered by ensuring personal determination of women leaders today.

28. Do you think societal standards, expectations and customs towards organisations and individuals help women achieve success in the workplace?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

29. Can you relate any such situations where the above factors (ques. 15) actually helped you achieve success, or otherwise?

I think the traditional gender roles of women still control attitudes across various business segment. In a chance to represent my firm at a major Fin-tech conference I was made aware of how attitude about gender roles are deeply rooted. Most of the leaders were of the opinion that my attaining the control or leadership is some weird stroke of luck. As a female leader I think you will need both inner fortitude and determination to respond to such mind-set of people.

30. Is gender relevant, or should only professional skills be emphasised when considering leadership and managers? Or is it necessary to better women's position in working life in certain ways, because there are other obstacles, which are not related to professional skills?

If an organisation is ready to provide equal opportunity, pay-scale, and prospects to women, then professional skill should be the only parameter to be considered in the leadership roles. Many organisations are already doing it and if there is equality in all forms of hiring and employee management then skill based leadership is the only method to ensure success of organisations.

31. According to a study by McKinsey & company, leadership styles which are more commonly used by women (feminine leadership) are more suitable in facing new trends, such as social and environmental trends, than traditional leadership. Do you think it is easier for women to become managers at the moment and even more so in the future? Why do you think it is / is not?

With more initiatives like “our time” that has been announced by the mayor in London, we can be a lookout for more opportunities for women to lead. These initiatives are challenging gender disparity in organisations and also countering social and cultural barriers that have existed in the path of women. Also, when a large firm such as McKinsey & company, recognises female leadership as the styles which is more suitable to new trends, it sends a message across organisation that female leadership is not a spur of the moment it is an inclination of the corporate world and is here to stay.

Section D: Challenges faced in the leadership position

32. Do you think women are underrepresented in senior management in FinTech companies of UK?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

33. State the reasons behind your answer for the above question.

I strongly agree that women are under-represented in the higher leadership role. Women are there in administrative jobs, but at senior level due to limited opportunities given to women in the executive role, even few of them get opportunities to lead. Disparity does exist in the gender

balance in organisation that translates to under-representation of women in higher management.

34. What are the ways do you think to increase the number of women in leadership positions?

Equal opportunity to job, similar pay standards, training, assistance in form helping women acquire technological and infrastructural skill are methods that can help women reach leadership position.

35. Do you think your team members prefer working under a male leader over female leader?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

36. Have you experienced any such instance of male leader preference? If so, what was your way of handling the situation?

I don't think my team has ever expected to work under male leader to state an example.

37. What suggestions would you like to give to the FinTech sector/organisations to make women's rise to the leadership position conducive?

I think that organisational settings in which women perform do not present any obstruction to the leadership process. A distribution of opportunity as well as power in the industry is

required. Women do not reach their potential success due to unfair organisational policies are unfair.

Interviewee D

Section A: Demographic Profile

1. Name: _____
2. Age: 36 _____
3. Organisation Name: _____
4. YearsofExperienceinLeadershipPosition:

5. Your marital status?
6. Single
7. Do you stay with your family?
8. Are there any dependents in your family? If yes, how many?
9. Yes, ≥ 3
10. Do you have children?
11. If yes, how many?

1 2 3 4 ≥ 5

Section B: Perception on Leadership Strategies

1. Being at a leadership position, how do you think managing a FinTech company differs from other sectors?

FinTech is a specialised banking segment and along with new ideas there are risks associated with the choices as well. Leading a FinTech requires to keep oneself updated of various changes in technological, such as artificial intelligence and financial sphere it requires survival quality.

2. Is leadership gender neutral in your organisation? Or have you noticed a change in culture of leadership appointment in your organisation?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

N/A

3. If no to question 2, why do you think so?

Strongly Disagree. Even though the representation of female leaders are more in FinTech than other sectors, there still exists gender inequality when it comes to women holding the leadership position. Female leadership can provide the firms with long-time growth, but this is limited by unequal pay standard. Opportunity in form for gender neutral hiring and exclusion of low hiring trends of female employees can address the gap that currently exists.

4. If yes to question 2, how that has helped you or similar leaders to availing opportunities to rise to the top?

5. Do you think there is a shift in women's personal characteristics to succeed in leadership roles, in recent period?

Women have brought more strength to leadership role, strategic vision and mission. Women leaders have the capability of constituting more effective teams and also display more optimistic behaviour that ensures higher team performances.

6. Do you think there exists gender specific leadership benefits? Like women leaders bring more benefits over their male counterparts or vice-versa?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

Strongly Agree. I think female leaders have more compassion towards employees as well as organisations that help them to lead better.

7. What benefits do female leaders bring to organisations?

Women as a leader are more collaborative, they use participative decision making approach. Female leader work with all employees together, as FinTech industry is prone to changes, conflict management is easier.

8. What do you think are the best tools to increase the number of women in leadership positions? (For example, quotas, mentoring, general discussion, etc.)?

Strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

quotas

mentoring

general discussion

Others, please specify

9. State reasons behind your answer to question 7, providing an instance from your experience.

I think male leader adopt the approach of control and corrective action and I have an experience of working in that kind of leadership. I have leaded my team and inculcated in them that individualist decision making has limitation, be it designing new products or leading the team, success is always collaborative.

10. Which aspects or events do you consider to have advanced your career the most? How?

Accountability, innovation, and motivation are aspects that I think have helped me advance in my career. I have always been a leader that also includes the chances when my team failed to

deliver. However, there should be constant motivation that only an open work environment can provide that will help you succeed.

11. Which aspects or events have you considered as obstacles or speed bumps in your career? If any? Brief how?

Unequal Pay structure and lack of gender diversity across firms are inhibitors in path of female leadership. There have to be developed more opportunities that recognise unique leadership qualities of female leaders and enable them to achieve more.

12. What do you think are the most important qualities and characteristics of a good leader?

Strong personal sense with determination is required for female leadership process. I want to ensure that women believe that there is no gender difference in the path to aspiration. You only need willingness to succeed.

13.

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

14. With respect to your answer to question 12, state your reasons with instance.

Personal determination has helped me succeed in each step of leadership. Determination helped me attain my first job in the FinTech industry that helped me paving the path to further success.

Section C: Factors leading to success in Industry

15. What are the main factors that influence women's rise to leadership positions?

The glass ceiling problem and gender disparity restricts women's rise to the top. These factors exist in every industry. The problem particularly comes into play in maintenance of work-life balances as well as parenthood.

16. Do you think societal standards, expectations and customs towards organisations and individuals help women achieve success in the workplace?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

Agree

17. Can you relate any such situations where the above factors (ques. 15) actually helped you achieve success, or otherwise?

The gender disparity across the sectors is such that the higher you climb in the leadership hierarchy, the fewer women you will encounter. However in prospect meetings where I get to represent my company, I think the "different-ness" that I add to the representation comes as a significant advantage to the group. There have been prospective clients that have been able to see beyond the difference in male and female leadership and focused on getting the job done instead.

18. Is gender relevant, or should only professional skills be emphasised when considering leadership and managers? Or is it necessary to better women's position in working life

in certain ways, because there are other obstacles, which are not related to professional skills?

If there is gender disparity in opportunity, then there will automatically be inconsistency in female leadership positions. However, I think that leadership should not be biased on gender. It takes professional skill to guide the team through various organisational decisions, especially in industries like fintech. If a female leader is chosen and a more capable male leader is not given the chance it is still inequality. I think if women as leader are against inequality they should also be against favours.

19. According to a study by McKinsey & company, leadership styles which are more commonly used by women (feminine leadership) are more suitable in facing new trends, such as social and environmental trends, than traditional leadership. Do you think it is easier for women to become managers at the moment and even more so in the future? Why do you think it is / is not?

The study published by McKinsey & company provides a boost to the young talents that are making their way across different industries. Women, who are initiating their corporate journey today have more role models to look up to than we had. I would agree that the present and future although challenging is something worth trying. However, I would still like to say we have a long way to go before I can say that future for leadership is bright.

Section D: Challenges faced in the leadership position

20. Do you think women are underrepresented in senior management in FinTech companies of UK?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

21. State the reasons behind your answer for the above question.

We are living in the corporate world that is built on culture of long working hours that are self-imposed on employees as a result of peer pressure. Flexible working arrangements are also not welcome and I am talking about this factor for either of the gender. With the social mind-set and need for women to play larger roles in family life as well women often get lesser chance to succeed and this lead to their under-representation in higher managements.

22. What are the ways do you think to increase the number of women in leadership positions?

I think removal of social and structural barriers will be influential step in ensuring more women attain the leadership position.

23. Do you think your team members prefer working under a male leader over female leader?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

strongly disagree

24. Have you experienced any such instance of male leader preference? If so, what was your way of handling the situation?

Male leader preference has been a subject around my team. Occasionally, I have been prompted to be lucky to be leading the team. I take my these opinion with grace and let my work speak.

25. What suggestions would you like to give to the FinTech sector/organisations to make women's rise to the leadership position conducive?

Policies that prevent sexual discrimination in workplaces and career path of women need to be addressed. Female leadership should not intimate their colleagues and only an open organisation can enable women to achieve leadership positions.

Interviewee E

Section A: Demographic Profile

1. Name: _____
2. Age: 40 _____
3. Organisation Name: _____
4. Years of Experience in Leadership Position: 8
5. Your marital status?
6. Married
7. Do you stay with your family?

Yes
8. Are there any dependents in your family? If yes, how many?
9. Yes, <= 3
10. Do you have children?

Yes
11. If yes, how many?

2

Section B: Perception on Leadership Strategies

12. Being at a leadership position, how do you think managing a FinTech company differs from other sectors?

Being a woman, leading a growing industry like FinTech comes with its own challenge. You have to be brave enough to occasionally be the change and step into environment of large-scale competition and just enjoy the ride.

13. Is leadership gender neutral in your organisation? Or have you noticed a change in culture of leadership appointment in your organisation?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

2.5 Agree, I would not say I strongly agree as we are yet to achieve an overall gender inclusion in each department of the company. However, as a leader, ignoring all stereotypical characteristics of female and male leadership, I think leadership is all about differences between perception and leadership behaviour of the leaders. Efficient leaders are not gender biased of employees working for them they promote gender neutrality to run the organisation effectively. However, I would like to see more women employee joining at executive level to ensure we have benefit from their perspective as well.

14. If no to question 2, why do you think so?

15. If yes to question 2, how that has helped you or similar leaders to availing opportunities to rise to the top?

4.5 Developing a gender neutral organisation is exemplary and that is all FinTech as a segment is about change and evolution. Having working for a gender neutral organisation, I was provided with the correct start and only had to display leadership skill. An organisation sharing the vision of gender equality enables you to focus only on your core skill and personality development to lead. Sharing a gender neutral vision would help similar leaders to availing opportunities to rise to the top as it provides them with encouragement and opportunity. Ability to see beyond gender help female leaders to take more risks and entrusting themselves of being capable of reaching the leadership positions.

16. Do you think there is a shift in women's personal characteristics to succeed in leadership roles, in recent period?

The proportion of female students in STEM are increasing, however, the numbers in mathematical studies have not increased in similar proportion, the student demography is changing. With ability to see beyond their constricted societal roles, women will be able to establish their leadership further.

17. Do you think there exists gender specific leadership benefits? Like women leaders bring more benefits over their male counterparts or vice-versa?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

Agree. I think apart of being more compassionate, female leader are more inclined towards innovation. This, I think is specifically beneficial in an industry like Fintech.

18. What benefits do female leaders bring to organisations?

Mentorship is one of the quality that female leaders bring on board. They guide their entire team through honest and practical advice. This makes female leaders inspirational as role model for employees as well as amplifies the market reputation of the firm.

19. What do you think are the best tools to increase the number of women in leadership positions? (For example, quotas, mentoring, general discussion, etc.)?

Strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

quotas
mentoring
general discussion

Others, please specify

28. 20. State reasons behind your answer to question 7, providing an instance from your experience.

Incidents of woman leadership fulfilling more mentorship role take place each day at work. The success of the team is dependent on how inclusively you are able to guide them.

29. Which aspects or events do you consider to have advanced your career the most?

How?

The time I chose FinTech as a field. With so many strategic and mathematic calculation involved, I had my doubts, but motivation from my previous mentors enabled me to take this leap.

30. Which aspects or events have you considered as obstacles or speed bumps in your career? If any? Brief how?

I would like to point out towards a number of challenges that women have to encounter in their way to leadership. Mind-set, inequality in opportunity and payment, and lack of role models all present challenges for others who want to succeed in the leadership process.

31. What do you think are the most important qualities and characteristics of a good leader?

Collaborative efforts. Female leadership is a scarce phenomenon and as leaders you have to exemplary. Hear and respond to views of the entire team, you need to steer the ship in correct direction to ensure success.

32. Have you experienced your gender/femininity to be in the way of your career development?

strongly disagree

disagree

undecided

agree

strongly agree

disagree

33. With respect to your answer to question 12, state your reasons with instance.

Internal competition is not a new thing that you observe in growing organisations. In one such situation, as a leader, who stresses on the need for collaborative efforts to develop a knowledge sharing organisation. I ensured that the competitors see the benefit of sharing data and being of help to each other.

Section C: Factors leading to success in Industry

34. What are the main factors that influence women's rise to leadership positions?

Talent and situational awareness are required for women to attain leadership position. Situational awareness allows you to forge correct alliances, encash opportunities, and accomplish goals in a practical manner to attain leadership.

35. Do you think societal standards, expectations and customs towards organisations and individuals help women achieve success in the workplace?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

Agree

36. Can you relate any such situations where the above factors (ques. 15) actually helped you achieve success, or otherwise?

From my experience at the firm have seen that there are a lot of women who have it in them to succeed as a leader. I have encountered executives with tremendous potential however, I have also seen them restricting themselves as they think they need more training or experience. Situational awareness is what they require the most. Awareness to embrace opportunities, survive and thrive in challenges have helped me frame my leadership journey.

37. Is gender relevant, or should only professional skills be emphasised when considering leadership and managers? Or is it necessary to better women's position in working life in certain ways, because there are other obstacles, which are not related to professional skills?

For leadership position I do not agree with playing favouritism. I think the position requires skill that is developed through experiences. It takes development of several parameters, training, and preparation that builds a leader for what is to come. Going by the gender if preference is provided to a women leader it may not fare well with the organisation. Also, I don't think that female leader need any preferential treatment, I think they deserve equality in opportunities to grow and nurture themselves.

38. According to a study by McKinsey & company, leadership styles which are more commonly used by women (feminine leadership) are more suitable in facing new trends, such as social and environmental trends, than traditional leadership. Do

you think it is easier for women to become managers at the moment and even more so in the future? Why do you think it is / is not?

Women leadership is on a rise and studies also suggest that future industries would require qualities of women to lead them better. However for a bright future there should be grass root steps that each organisation need to take. It is not only about the organisation, leaders succeed because of their own personal efforts so it is required of women to take charge of their own actions are prepare themselves to lead better.

Section D: Challenges faced in the leadership position

39. Do you think women are underrepresented in senior management in FinTech companies of UK?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

40. State the reasons behind your answer for the above question.

I have had a chance to coordinate seminars and meetings for different firms in FinTech and I have never found a line for women registration. I think that helps me conclude that women are fewer in comparison to men in the industry.

41. What are the ways do you think to increase the number of women in leadership positions?

Influential way to increase women representation in leadership role is ensuring their inclination towards information technology and new age developments, such as usage of AI and big data.

I think that women are very much capable of balancing their work and life. All they need is opportunity that can motivate them to achieve more and be successful in FinTech leadership.

42. Do you think your team members prefer working under a male leader over female leader?

strongly disagree disagree undecided agree strongly agree

43. Have you experienced any such instance of male leader preference? If so, what was your way of handling the situation?

Even with glass ceiling efforts, my team has never expressed any opinion to be led by male leaders. I think identity issues are common in aspirants, however once your leadership is contextualised there are no gender differentiation.

44. What suggestions would you like to give to the FinTech sector/organisations to make women's rise to the leadership position conducive?

Women can rise to leadership role if organisations are ready to address stereotypes and prejudice. These parameters lead to negative impact on career development for both women as well as men. I even think that organisational policies should be developed to address traditional gender roles and cater to the expectations of women seeking higher management roles.

Any other comments?

I think that organisations limit women leadership as these institutes are new to see female leaders. Across the industrial segment it has been a male dominate world that prefers to make decision based on age-old believes and value system. Male leaders promote other male to

leadership position as that is what has been going on. It is in built in them as a result of their societal understanding. To promote female leadership we need to address these gender based mentality from the very beginning. This starts with building in the children that they can choose a career that is mathematical or analytical in nature and they are sure to succeed in their efforts as well.

APPENDIX V

Cronbach's Alpha α or coefficient alpha, was developed by Lee Cronbach in the year 1951. It measures reliability or internal consistency. Reliability is how well a test measures what it should. In the context of this study Cronbach's alpha tests if multiple question Likert scale surveys are reliable. The formula for Cronbach's Alpha is as follows: (the α calculation for this study is done using SPSS software).

$$\alpha = \frac{N \cdot \bar{c}}{\bar{v} + (N - 1) \cdot \bar{c}}$$

Where:

- N = the number of items.
- \bar{c} = average covariance between item-pairs.
- \bar{v} = average variance.

Figure:

Source: Mohsen Tavakol and Reg Dennick. Making Sense of Cronbach's Alpha. International Journal of Medical Education. 2011; 2:53-55 Editorial

A rule of thumb for interpreting alpha for dichotomous (questions with two answers) questions or Likert Scale question is as follows:

Cronbach's alpha	Internal consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

Source: Mohsen Tavakol and Reg Dennick. Making Sense of Cronbach's Alpha. International Journal of Medical Education. 2011; 2:53-55 Editorial

In general, a score of more than 0.7 is usually okay, in the context of this study we have achieved 0.762 for Effective leadership Behaviours, 0.960 for Factors impacting Women Leader, 0.947 for Effectiveness of Women Leader, 0.967 for Shortcoming of Women Leader and 0.877 for Impact of the leadership on team/organisational performance as depicted in table 47 below:

	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
Effective leadership Behaviours	.762	9
Factors impacting Women Leader	.960	15
Effectiveness of Women Leader	.947	15
Shortcoming of Women Leader	.967	11
Impact of the leadership on team/organisational performance	.877	9

APPENDIX VI

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

University of the West of Scotland

235 Southwark Bridge Road, London SE1 6NP, UK

+44(0) 141 848 3030

Title of the Study: Comprehending the Factors Responsible for Creating Successful Leadership Among Women Leaders in the United Kingdom's FinTech Start-up Sector

PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH

This is an invitation to participate in a study conducted as part of the requirements of my doctoral dissertation. The purpose of the research is to comprehend the factors responsible for creating successful leadership among women leaders in the UK's FinTech Start-up sector.

The study will promote understanding on how women can be a successful leader in Financial Technology start-up sector like. There are challenges and obstacles but there are opportunities and encouragement too. My thesis will attempt to answer some of those questions.

METHOD OF PARTICIPATION

This research paper started in October 2017 and it will be completed by October 2019. As part of the research, surveys will be conducted. If you choose to be included, you will be asked to complete one 30 – 40 minutes interview, during which I will take notes. I shall contact each study participant to schedule the interview for a time that is most convenient to the participant.

POSSIBLE RISKS

Apart from the time you will take to participate in the interview, there are no known risks for participating in this study. If answering some of the questions makes you uncomfortable, please let me know. We can stop the interview for a few moments, you can skip a question or furthermore, you can decide to stop participating at any time.

PRIVACY PROTECTION

All the information collected in the course of this research will be kept strictly confidential. After collection, all data will be recognised to ensure secrecy using letters to identify participants in place of their names. Paper records will be kept under lock and electronic files will be protected by the use of passwords throughout the research process. On completion of the study, all the documentation and recordings used to gather the data will be destroyed.

FINDINGS AND BENEFITS OF THE RESEARCH

This research will provide some useful insight into the factors responsible for the successful leadership of females in the UK's FinTech Start-up sector. Women who are leaders and those aspiring to become one in this industry are my prospective respondents. The findings may also form the basis of articles submitted for publication in appropriate academic journals. Participants would not be referred to individually in any publication arising from this research.

It is entirely up to you to decide whether or not to take part in this research. If you do decide to take part, a consent form will be provided for you to sign. Should you require any further information, please do not hesitate to contact:

Thank you for taking time to read this information sheet.

Ujjwala M Mehta

DBA Cohort- 7, UWS London

APPENDIX VII

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

University of the West of Scotland
235 Southwark Bridge Road, London SE1 6NP, UK
+44(0) 141 848 3030

Name of Researcher: Ujjwala M Mehta

Participant to complete this section: Please initial next to each number

1. I confirm that I have read the Participant Information Sheet and the nature and purpose of the research project has been explained to me. I understand and agree to take part.
2. I understand the purpose of the research project and my involvement in it.
3. I understand that I may withdraw from the research project at any stage and that this will not affect my status now or in the future.
4. I understand that while information gained during the study may be published, I will not be identified and my personal results will remain confidential.
5. I understand that data (including hard and electronic copies of transcripts, or any video or audiotapes used) will be password protected and accessible only by the researcher.
6. I certify that I am 18 years old or older.
7. I agree to the interview being audio recorded.

8. I understand that I may contact the researcher or supervisor if I require further information about the research, and that I may contact the Research Ethics Coordinator of the Cardiff Metropolitan University, if I wish to make a complaint relating to my involvement in the research.

Signature of Participant

.....

Name of person taking consent

.....

Signature of person taking consent

.....

APPENDIX VIII

Following is the list of Financial Organisations in the UK who have signed up for “Women in Finance Charter”.

<p>Banking (global/investment banks) Bank of America Merrill Lynch Barclays BNY Mellon Canadian Imperial Bank of Commerce Citi Credit Suisse Securities Deutsche Bank Mizuho Bank Mizuho International Morgan Stanley International MUFG Northern Trust Global Services Royal Bank of Canada Royal Bank of Scotland SMBCE Standard Chartered State Street Handelsbanken</p> <p>Banking (UK banks) AIB Group Aldermore Bank Cambridge & Counties Bank CYBG HSBC UK Lloyds Banking Group Monzo OneSavings Bank Paragon Banking Group Post Office Santander UK Shawbrook Bank Starling Bank The Co-operative Bank TSB Unity Trust Bank Virgin Money</p> <p>Building societies/credit unions Capital Credit Union East Sussex Credit Union Leeds Building Society Market Harborough Building Society Nationwide Building Society Nottingham Building Society Pioneer Mutual Credit Union Principality Building Society Progressive Building Society West Bromwich Building Society</p>	<p>Fintech 10x Future Technologies Atom Bank Cirde UK Trading FINTECH Circle Landbay Maynard Capital Management Nutmeg Saving and Investments PensionBee RateSetter</p> <p>Government/regulators Financial Conduct Authority Financial Ombudsman Service HM Treasury National Savings and Investments</p> <p>Insurance Ageas Insurance Aviva AXA UK Chartered Insurance Institute Collinson Covéa Insurance Direct Line Group Ecclesiastical Insurance Office esure Group Legal & General Group Lloyd's LV= MetLife National House Building Council Phoenix Group Prudential Royal London Group Simply Business Unum Zurich Insurance UK</p> <p>Investment management BlackRock Charles Stanley & Co Columbia Threadneedle Investments EMEA Fidelity International Hermes Investment Management Janus Henderson Investors Jupiter Asset Management Scalable Capital Schroders Standard Life Aberdeen Tribe Impact Capital</p>	<p>Market infrastructure Thomson Reuters London Stock Exchange Group</p> <p>Payment systems Bacs Payment Schemes Mastercard</p> <p>Professional services Brickendon Consulting Channel Islands Adjusters Cicero Group ClearlySo EY GAAPweb ionStar KPMG Mercer OAC Pinsent Masons PwC Ridgeway Partners Sestini & Co Smith & Williamson</p> <p>Trade associations Association of Accounting Technicians Association of British Insurers Innovate Finance The Investment Association TheCityUK</p> <p>Other BP Supply & Trading Brightstar Financial Capital One (Europe) E2W Independent Women National Skills Academy for Financial Services NEST Corporation ReAssure Sturgeon Ventures Warren Partners</p> <p>NB: The company names listed here include a mixture of group, parent company, subsidiary and trading names. For many companies, the Charter applies to a subsidiary, a specific entity, a branch, a division or region, and not necessarily to all staff at the company name as listed here.</p>
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Source: www.newfinancial.org